

Integral Representations and Arithmetic of Odd Riemann Zeta and Even Dirichlet Beta Values

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- A study about integrals yielding the numbers $\frac{\zeta(2n+1)}{\pi^{2n}}$ and $\frac{\beta(2n)}{\pi^{2n-1}}$
- Conjectures related to the irrationality or transcendence of $\frac{\zeta(2n+1)}{\pi^{2n+1}}$ and $\frac{\beta(2n)}{\pi^{2n}}$
- Functions f_n vanishing at all integers less than n

*This work was carried out outside an academic institution,
in the framework of independent research.*

To Christopher Yepmo MABOU

Abstract

This work investigates the values of the Riemann zeta function at odd positive integers. While Euler famously provided closed-form expressions for $\zeta(2n)$ in terms of powers of π , no such expressions are known for $\zeta(2n + 1)$, and their arithmetic nature remains mysterious. It is conjectured that $\zeta(2n + 1)$ can not be written as a rational (respectively algebraic) multiple of π^{2n+1} . The investigations are extended to values of the Dirichlet beta function whose values at odd positive integers are known but those at even strictly positive remain mysterious. As with the Riemann zeta function, it is strongly conjectured that $\beta(2n)$ can not be written as a rational (respectively algebraic) multiple of π^{2n} . But up to now, no existing proof is conclusive enough to settle these conjectures. We study this problem in this work through classes of definite integrals involving logarithmic, hyperbolic and trigonometric functions. By carefully choosing trigonometric, hyperbolic and logarithmic integrals approximations, we derive new representations and numerical bounds for $\zeta(2n + 1)/\pi^{2n+1}$ and $\beta(2n)/\pi^{2n}$. The results point to a deeper structure underlying these special values, and suggest new directions for investigating their irrationality and transcendence.

Keywords: Riemann zeta function, Dirichlet beta function, odd zeta values, even beta values, irrationality, transcendence, conjecture, convergence, derivation, linear independence, special values, Euler numbers, Bernoulli numbers, Catalan's constant, definite integrals, log-log integrals, logarithmic integrals, hyperbolic functions, trigonometric integrals, kernel functions, contour integration, Malmsten's integrals [1], polylogarithms, L-functions, functional equations, residue calculus, Fourier series, Taylor/Laurent expansion, asymptotic analysis, analytic number theory, transcendental number theory.

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1 Introduction

§1. History of the problem, known results and scheme of work

Euler is famously known for having computed the values of the Riemann zeta function at even positive integers. Thanks to Lindemann's proof of the transcendence of π [8], it follows that all these values are all transcendental. Since then, the values of the zeta function at **odd** positive integers have become a central enigma in number theory. Are they irrational? Are they transcendental? Do they admit any closed-form expressions?

So far, only the irrationality of $\zeta(3)$ —known as *Apéry's constant* after Roger Apéry's landmark and groundbreaking proof in 1978 [5]—has been established. For higher odd arguments, no analogous result is known. It has, however, been proven that infinitely many of the numbers $\zeta(2n+1)$ are irrational [7], and at least one among the list $\zeta(5), \zeta(7), \zeta(9), \zeta(11)$ is irrational [6].

One intriguing aspect of Euler's formula is that the even zeta values can be written as rational multiples of powers of π :

$$\zeta(2n) = (-1)^{n+1} \frac{B_{2n}(2\pi)^{2n}}{2(2n)!},$$

where B_{2n} denotes the $2n$ -th Bernoulli number [4].

This naturally raises the question of whether similar identities might hold for odd zeta values, i.e., whether

$$\zeta(2n+1) = r_n \pi^{2n+1}, \quad \text{with } r_n \in \mathbb{Q}.$$

Extensive numerical evidence suggests that such relations are unlikely to exist; yet, no general theorem has been proved to rule them out. The difficulty partly stems from the lack of sufficiently many closed-form expressions or identities involving these values that might serve as a starting point for an irrationality or transcendence proof. Interestingly, Ramanujan himself discovered a remarkable identity involving $\zeta(2n+1)$, expressing it as a rapidly converging series with Bernoulli numbers [12]:

$$\zeta(2n+1) = \frac{(-1)^{n+1}(2\pi)^{2n+1}}{2(2n+1)!} + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{B_{2k}B_{2n+2-2k}}{(2k)!(2n+2-2k)!}.$$

Although elegant, this identity does not provide any direct insight into the irrationality or transcendence of odd zeta values, but it reflects the deep arithmetic structure they might possess.

In the case of $\zeta(3)$, a various rapidly converging series is known :

$$\zeta(3) = \frac{7}{180} \pi^3 - 2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^3(e^{2\pi n} - 1)} \quad (\text{Plouffe})$$

But an irrationality proof of $\frac{\zeta(3)}{\pi^3}$ from this identity is hard to sketch. In addition to Ramanujan's identities, several experimentally discovered formulas due to Broadhurst and Plouffe express odd zeta values using π^{2n+1} and rapidly converging series:

$$\zeta(5) = \frac{\pi^5}{294} - \frac{72}{35} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^5(e^{2\pi n} - 1)} - \frac{2}{35} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^5(e^{2\pi n} + 1)},$$

$$\zeta(7) = \frac{19\pi^7}{56700} - \frac{32}{63} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^7(e^{2\pi n} - 1)} - \frac{16}{63} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^7(e^{2\pi n} + 1)}.$$

Although not proven rigorously, these formulas have been verified numerically to hundreds of digits and suggest a deep modular structure behind odd zeta values.

Another function -much less known- that often appears alongside the Riemann zeta in the study of special values is *Dirichlet's beta function*, defined for $\Re(s) > 0$ by

$$\beta(s) = \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^m}{(2m+1)^s}.$$

This L-function is less studied in the literature and even left aside despite of its similarities and shared properties with the well known ζ . For instance, Blagouchine did not miss to underline that the functional equation of β , which reads

$$\beta(1-s) = \left(\frac{2}{\pi}\right)^s \Gamma(s) \cos\left(\frac{\pi s}{2}\right) \beta(s).$$

has been firstly conjectured by Euler and rigorously proved by Carl Johann Malmsten and colleagues [1], since the functional equation of ζ has been introduced and proven by Riemann rather few years later[1][9]. More intriguing, the first considerations of this function have been made far before Euler's works. In fact the identity

$$\beta(1) = \frac{\pi}{4}$$

is already present in the works of Leibniz, although it is more properly attributed to a lesser-known Gregory. In contrast to the Riemann zeta function, the Dirichlet beta function admits an analytic continuation to the entire complex plane without any poles at all. Furthermore, it possesses an Euler product representation that is intimately connected with that of the Riemann zeta function. :

$$\beta(s) = \prod_{p \equiv 1 \pmod{4}} \frac{1}{1-p^{-s}} \prod_{p \equiv 3 \pmod{4}} \frac{1}{1+p^{-s}}, \quad \Re(s) > 0.$$

The central difference lies in the fact that this Euler product does not extend over the full set of prime numbers. One of the principal aims of this work is to emphasize the properties that the Dirichlet beta function shares with the Riemann zeta function, thereby underscoring the significance of $\beta(s)$, which, from our perspective, has not been studied to the same extent and remains comparatively neglected. And for instance. Unlike the zeta at even integers, whose values are known to be rational multiples of π^{2n} , the beta function behaves "in reverse":

- For **odd** arguments one has closed-form expressions [13]

$$\beta(2n + 1) = (-1)^n \frac{E_{2n} \pi^{2n+1}}{2^{2n+2} (2n)!},$$

where the E_{2n} are Euler numbers. Consequently, the ratios $\beta(2n+1)/\pi^{2n+1}$ are rational. This result shows a deep connection and similarity with ζ .

- In stark contrast, for **even** arguments

$$\beta(2n) = \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^m}{(2m + 1)^{2n}},$$

no closed-form in terms of π^{2n} is known. The simplest case, $\beta(2) = \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^m}{(2m + 1)^2}$, is Catalan's constant ($\approx 0.915966\dots$), whose arithmetic nature remains open. It is ever not known, even in 2025, whether this number is irrational in comparison to $\zeta(3)$. Thus the ratios

$$\frac{\beta(2n)}{\pi^{2n}}$$

are believed to be transcendental or at least irrational, but no proof exists to date. The only arithmetic natures proven today is firstly that infinitely many numbers of the form $\beta(2n)$ are irrational [14] and secondly at least one among the following $\beta(2), \beta(4), \beta(6), \beta(8), \beta(10), \beta(12)$ [13]. Such a coincidence in shared properties can hardly be regarded as accidental. And these similarities will be found in the further integral representations of this work.

Understanding why $\zeta(2n)/\pi^{2n}$ and $\beta(2n + 1)/\pi^{2n+1}$ are always rational while $\beta(2n)/\pi^{2n}$ and $\zeta(2n + 1)/\pi^{2n+1}$ sit beyond our current reach, highlights a deep asymmetry in these two cousin L -series—and suggests new paths toward tackling the arithmetic of odd zeta values themselves and even beta ones.

This present work introduces a class of definite integrals with some patterns involving $\zeta(2n + 1)$ and $\beta(2n)$, along with several conjectures concerning their structure and arithmetic nature.

Several of the integral evaluations and associated identities throughout this work rely on two summation tricks that are also usable with products, which we recall here for convenience:

- $\sum_{k=a}^b f(k) = \sum_{k=a+n}^{b+n} f(k - n) \quad (n \in \mathbb{Z})$

- $\sum_{k=a}^b f(k) = \sum_{k=a}^b f(a + b - k)$

The structure of the work is as follows:

- **Section 2** recalls previous results obtained by Blagouchine [1] and outlines first curiosities behind them.
- **Section 3** defines a family of functions $f_{k,n}(z) = \frac{\sinh((2k+1)z)}{z \cosh^n z}$ and investigates their complex structure and residue behavior.
- **Section 4** presents integral representations of the form

$$\frac{\zeta(2n+1)}{\pi^{2n}} \quad \text{and} \quad \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin(4nx)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx,$$

and establishes new identities involving trigonometric-logarithmic integrals.

- **Section 5** develops analogous representations for $\beta(2n)/\pi^{2n-1}$ based on modified hyperbolic integral forms.
- **Section 6** formulates and discusses conjectures about the irrationality or transcendence of these ratios, and their connection to polylogarithmic integrals.
- **Section 7** concludes the work and outlines perspectives for future research.

§2. Notations

Throughout this manuscript, we made use of following notations which include our own :

- $\sum_{\bar{k}^p=a}^b f(k)$ means the sum over k from a to b in steps of p . For instance

$$\sum_{\bar{k}^2=1}^6 f(k) = f(1) + f(3) + f(5)$$

since 6 does not match the step.

- $\llbracket a, b \rrbracket$ stands for $\mathbb{N} \cap [a, b]$ also integers contained in the interval $[a, b]$ or more formally the set $\{a, a+1, a+2, \dots, b\}$

In this work, we also adopt the standard combinatorial notation

$$\langle \frac{n}{k} \rangle = \langle \frac{n}{k} \rangle$$

for the *Eulerian numbers of type A* (also called the classical Eulerian numbers, cf. *Eulerian number*, Wikipedia). To avoid any confusion with the Bernoulli numbers usually denoted by B_n , we write

$$\langle \frac{n}{k} \rangle^B = \langle \frac{n}{k} \rangle^B$$

for the *Eulerian numbers of type B*. This distinction between $\langle \frac{n}{k} \rangle$ and $\langle \frac{n}{k} \rangle^B$ will be maintained throughout the manuscript.

§3. Evaluation methods

Within the methodological framework of this work, the primary tool is the classical transformation of integrals. Most evaluations are carried out by combining standard changes of variables, integration by parts, and interval decompositions, which allow one to isolate the singular behavior of the logarithmic kernels and to control convergence at the endpoints.

By contrast, the residue theorem is not employed as a systematic device but rather as a complementary method, reserved for the more delicate cases where elementary transformations are insufficient. In such situations, contour integration is judged as particularly fruitful and provides a natural way to capture the contribution of singularities and to derive closed-form identities that would be otherwise inaccessible.

In this respect, the rectangular contour was systematically preferred. The use of circular contours, though classical, introduces subtleties at infinity that can generate gaps in rigor; by adopting rectangular paths, we avoided these issues and ensured a more transparent control of the boundary terms.

This hierarchy of methods—elementary analytic manipulations for the bulk of the computations, and residue calculus with carefully chosen contours for the critical points—ensures both efficiency and rigor in the evaluation of the families of integrals under consideration.

§4. Some lemmas and propositions helping further

In order to ease the references of the proofs outlined in this work, we give here some propositions and their proofs.

Proposition 1

$\forall n \in \mathbb{N}^*$

$$\begin{aligned}\cos 2nx &= \cos^{2n} x \sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^k \binom{2n}{2k} \tan^{2k} x \\ \sin 2nx &= \cos^{2n} x \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} (-1)^k \binom{2n}{2k+1} \tan^{2k+1} x\end{aligned}$$

Proof :

We know from the De Moivre formula that

$$\cos(2nx) + i \sin(2nx) = (\cos x + i \sin x)^{2n}.$$

The expansion of the right member with Newton's binomial gives us:

$$\begin{aligned}
(\cos x + i \sin x)^{2n} &= \sum_{k=0}^{2n} \binom{2n}{k} \cos^{2n-k} x (i \sin x)^k \\
&= \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{2n}{2k} \cos^{2n-2k} x (i \sin x)^{2k} + \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \binom{2n}{2k+1} \cos^{2n-2k-1} x (i \sin x)^{2k+1} \\
&= \sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^k \binom{2n}{2k} \cos^{2n-2k} x \sin^{2k} x + i \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} (-1)^k \binom{2n}{2k+1} \cos^{2n-2k-1} x \sin^{2k+1} x \\
&= \cos^{2n} x \sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^k \binom{2n}{2k} \tan^{2k} x + i \cos^{2n} x \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} (-1)^k \binom{2n}{2k+1} \tan^{2k+1} x.
\end{aligned}$$

On equating the real parts we obtain the first equality, and on equating the imaginary parts we obtain the second.

Proposition 2

$$\begin{aligned}
\forall n \in \mathbb{N}, \quad \sinh^{2n+1} z &= \frac{1}{4^n} \sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^k \binom{2n+1}{k} \sinh(2n+1-2k)z \\
\forall n \in \mathbb{N}^*, \quad \sinh^{2n} z &= \frac{1}{4^n} \left[2 \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} (-1)^k \binom{2n}{k} \cosh(2n-2k)z + (-1)^n \binom{2n}{n} \right] \\
\forall n \in \mathbb{N}, \quad \cosh^{2n+1} x &= \frac{1}{4^n} \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{2n+1}{k} \cosh((2n+1-2k)x) \\
\forall n \in \mathbb{N}^*, \quad \cosh^{2n} x &= \frac{1}{4^n} \left[2 \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \binom{2n}{k} \cosh((2n-2k)x) + \binom{2n}{n} \right]
\end{aligned}$$

Proof :

$$\begin{aligned}
\sinh^{2n+1} w &= \left(\frac{e^w - e^{-w}}{2} \right)^{2n+1} \\
&= \frac{1}{2^{2n+1}} (e^w - e^{-w})^{2n+1} \\
&= \frac{1}{2^{2n+1}} \sum_{k=0}^{2n+1} \binom{2n+1}{k} e^{(2n+1-k)w} (-1)^k e^{-kw} \\
&= \frac{1}{2^{2n+1}} \sum_{k=0}^{2n+1} (-1)^k \binom{2n+1}{k} e^{(2n+1-2k)w}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \frac{1}{2^{2n+1}} \left(\sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^k \binom{2n+1}{k} e^{(2n+1-2k)w} + \sum_{k=n+1}^{2n+1} (-1)^k \binom{2n+1}{k} e^{(2n+1-2k)w} \right) \\
&= \frac{1}{4^n} \left(\sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^k \binom{2n+1}{k} e^{(2n+1-2k)w} + \sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^{n+1+k} \binom{2n+1}{n+1+k} e^{(2n+1-2(n+1+k))w} \right) \\
&= \frac{1}{2^{2n+1}} \left(\sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^k \binom{2n+1}{k} e^{(2n+1-2k)w} - \sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^{n+k} \binom{2n+1}{n+1+k} e^{(-2k-1)w} \right) \\
&= \frac{1}{2^{2n+1}} \left(\sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^k \binom{2n+1}{k} e^{(2n+1-2k)w} - \sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^{2n-k} \binom{2n+1}{2n+1-k} e^{(-2(n-k)-1)w} \right) \\
&= \frac{1}{2^{2n+1}} \left(\sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^k \binom{2n+1}{k} e^{(2n+1-2k)w} - \sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^k \binom{2n+1}{k} e^{-(2n+1-2k)w} \right) \\
&= \frac{1}{2^{2n+1}} \sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^k \binom{2n+1}{k} 2 \sinh(2n+1-2k)w \\
&= \frac{1}{4^n} \sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^k \binom{2n+1}{k} \sinh(2n+1-2k)w
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\sinh^{2n} z &= \left(\frac{e^z - e^{-z}}{2} \right)^{2n} \\
&= \frac{1}{4^n} (e^z - e^{-z})^{2n} \\
&= \frac{1}{4^n} \sum_{k=0}^{2n} \binom{2n}{k} (-1)^k e^{(2n-2k)z} \\
&= \frac{1}{4^n} \left(\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \binom{2n}{k} (-1)^k e^{(2n-2k)z} + \binom{2n}{n} (-1)^n + \sum_{k=n+1}^{2n} \binom{2n}{k} (-1)^k e^{(2n-2k)z} \right) \\
&= \frac{1}{4^n} \left(\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \binom{2n}{k} (-1)^k [e^{(2n-2k)z} + e^{-(2n-2k)z}] + \binom{2n}{n} (-1)^n \right) \\
&= \frac{1}{4^n} \left(\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \binom{2n}{k} (-1)^k \cdot 2 \cosh((2n-2k)z) + (-1)^n \binom{2n}{n} \right) \\
&= \frac{1}{4^n} \left(\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} 2(-1)^k \binom{2n}{k} \cosh((2n-2k)z) + (-1)^n \binom{2n}{n} \right)
\end{aligned}$$

Proposition 3

$$\forall x \in \mathbb{R}, \cos(\arctan x) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1+x^2}}$$

Proof :

$$\begin{aligned} \cos^2(\arctan x) + \sin^2(\arctan x) = 1 &\Rightarrow 1 + \frac{\sin^2(\arctan x)}{\cos^2(\arctan x)} = \frac{1}{\cos^2(\arctan x)} \\ &\Rightarrow 1 + \tan^2(\arctan x) = \frac{1}{\cos^2(\arctan x)} \\ &\Rightarrow \cos(\arctan x) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1+x^2}} \end{aligned}$$

Proposition 4

$$\forall (a, b) \in \mathbb{R}^* \times \mathbb{R}^* \wedge a > b, \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} [x^a - x^b] \ln \ln \frac{1}{x} = \lim_{x \rightarrow 1} [x^a - x^b] \ln \ln \frac{1}{x} = 0$$

Firstly,

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} [x^a - x^b] \ln \ln \frac{1}{x} &= \lim_{u \rightarrow +\infty} [e^{-au} - e^{-bu}] \ln u \quad (\text{on doing } x = e^{-u}) \\ &= \lim_{u \rightarrow +\infty} \left[\frac{\ln u}{e^{au}} - \frac{\ln u}{e^{bu}} \right] \\ &= 0 \quad \text{because the exponential grows faster than the logarithm} \end{aligned}$$

Secondly,

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{x \rightarrow 1} [x^a - x^b] \ln \ln \frac{1}{x} &= \lim_{x \rightarrow 1} x^b [x^{a-b} - 1] \ln \ln \frac{1}{x} \\ &= \lim_{x \rightarrow 1} [x^{a-b} - 1] \ln \ln \frac{1}{x} \\ &= \lim_{x \rightarrow 1} [x^{a-b} - 1] \ln \left(\frac{1}{a-b} \ln \frac{1}{x^{a-b}} \right) \quad (t = x^{a-b}) \\ &= \lim_{t \rightarrow 1} [t - 1] \ln \left(\frac{1}{a-b} \ln \frac{1}{t} \right) \\ &= \lim_{t \rightarrow 1} \left([t - 1] \ln \frac{1}{a-b} + [t - 1] \ln \ln \frac{1}{t} \right) \\ &= \lim_{t \rightarrow 1} [t - 1] \ln \frac{1}{a-b} + \lim_{t \rightarrow 1} [t - 1] \ln \ln \frac{1}{t} \\ &= \lim_{t \rightarrow 1} [t - 1] \ln \ln \frac{1}{t} \quad \left(u = \ln \frac{1}{t} \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \lim_{u \rightarrow 0} [e^{-u} - 1] \ln u \\
&= \lim_{u \rightarrow 0} \frac{e^{-u} - 1}{u} u \ln u \\
&= - \lim_{u \rightarrow 0} u \ln u \\
\lim_{x \rightarrow 1} [x^a - x^b] \ln \ln \frac{1}{x} &= 0
\end{aligned}$$

Proposition 5

$$\forall s > -1, \int_0^1 x^s \ln \left(\ln \frac{1}{x} \right) dx = -\frac{\gamma + \ln(s+1)}{s+1}$$

Proof:

$$\begin{aligned}
\int_0^1 x^s \ln \left(\ln \frac{1}{x} \right) dx &= \int_{+\infty}^0 e^{-sx} \ln x (-e^{-x}) dx \\
&= \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-(s+1)x} \ln x dx \\
&= \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-(s+1)x} \ln x dx \\
&= \frac{1}{s+1} \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-x} \ln \frac{x}{s+1} dx \\
&= \frac{1}{s+1} \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-x} [\ln x - \ln(s+1)] dx \\
&= \frac{1}{s+1} \underbrace{\int_0^{+\infty} e^{-x} \ln x dx}_{-\gamma} - \frac{1}{s+1} \ln(s+1) \underbrace{\int_0^{+\infty} e^{-x} dx}_1 \\
&= -\frac{\gamma + \ln(s+1)}{s+1}
\end{aligned}$$

Proposition 6

Let \mathbb{K} be a field, V a \mathbb{K} -vector space, I_n, J_n two sequences in V so that holds :

$$\forall n \in \mathbb{N}^*, \exists (x_{1,n}, x_{2,n}, \dots, x_{n,n}) \in \mathbb{K}^n : I_n = \sum_{k=1}^n x_{k,n} J_k.$$

Then

$$\forall n \in \mathbb{N}^*, J_n = \sum_{k=1}^n z_{k,n} I_k$$

where

$$z_{k,n} = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{x_{n,n}} & \text{if } k = n, \\ -\frac{1}{x_{n,n}} \sum_{i=p}^{n-1} x_{i,n} \cdot z_{i,n} & \text{if } k \in \llbracket 1, n-1 \rrbracket \end{cases}$$

Proof :

One has:

$$I_1 = x_{1,1} J_1$$

$$I_2 = x_{1,2} J_1 + x_{2,2} J_2$$

\vdots

$$I_j = x_{1,j} J_1 + x_{2,j} J_2 + \dots + x_{j,n} J_j$$

\vdots

$$I_n = x_{1,n} J_1 + x_{2,n} J_2 + \dots + x_{n,n} J_n$$

We deduce $\begin{pmatrix} I_1 \\ I_2 \\ \vdots \\ I_n \end{pmatrix} = A_n \begin{pmatrix} J_1 \\ J_2 \\ \vdots \\ J_n \end{pmatrix}$ where $A_n := \begin{pmatrix} x_{1,1} & 0 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ x_{1,2} & x_{2,2} & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ x_{1,3} & x_{2,3} & x_{3,3} & \cdots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ x_{1,n} & x_{2,n} & x_{3,n} & \cdots & x_{n,n} \end{pmatrix}$

It follows $\begin{pmatrix} J_1 \\ J_2 \\ \vdots \\ J_n \end{pmatrix} = A_n^{-1} \begin{pmatrix} I_1 \\ I_2 \\ \vdots \\ I_n \end{pmatrix}$ where $A_n^{-1} = \begin{pmatrix} z_{1,1} & z_{2,1} & z_{3,1} & \cdots & z_{n,1} \\ z_{1,2} & z_{2,2} & z_{3,2} & \cdots & z_{n,2} \\ z_{1,3} & z_{2,3} & z_{3,3} & \cdots & z_{n,3} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ z_{1,n} & z_{2,n} & z_{3,n} & \cdots & z_{n,n} \end{pmatrix}$ is the inverse

of A_n .

We have

$$A_n \times A_n^{-1} = \begin{pmatrix} x_{1,1}z_{1,1} & x_{1,1}z_{2,1} & \cdots & x_{1,1}z_{n,1} \\ x_{1,2}z_{1,1} + x_{2,2}z_{1,2} & x_{1,2}z_{2,1} + x_{2,2}z_{2,2} & \cdots & x_{1,2}z_{n,1} + x_{2,2}z_{n,2} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \sum_{k=1}^n x_{k,n}z_{1,k} & \sum_{k=1}^n x_{k,n}z_{2,k} & \cdots & \sum_{k=1}^n x_{k,n}z_{n,k} \end{pmatrix}$$

Now $A_n \times A_n^{-1} = I_n = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & \cdots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \cdots & 1 \end{pmatrix}$ must be satisfied. We deduce

$$\sum_{k=1}^n x_{k,n}z_{j,k} = \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} x_{k,n}z_{j,k} + x_{n,n}z_{j,n} = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } j \in \llbracket 1, n-1 \rrbracket \\ 1, & \text{if } j = n \end{cases}$$

Since the inverse of a lower triangular matrix is again a lower triangular matrix, one deduces easily that $z_{j,k} = 0$ if $k \in \llbracket 1, j-1 \rrbracket$ for some $j \leq n$.

As consequence

$$\sum_{k=j}^{n-1} x_{k,n}z_{j,k} + x_{n,n}z_{j,n} = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } j \in \llbracket 1, n-1 \rrbracket \\ 1, & \text{if } j = n \end{cases}$$

It follows easily :

$$z_{n,j} = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{x_{n,n}} & \text{if } j = n, \\ -\frac{1}{x_{n,n}} \sum_{k=j}^{n-1} x_{k,n} \cdot z_{k,j} & \text{if } j \in \llbracket 1, n-1 \rrbracket \end{cases}$$

Which ends the proof.

Proposition 7

Let \mathbb{K} be a field, V a \mathbb{K} -vector space, and $(J_p)_{p \geq 0}$ a sequence in V . Given any function

$$\phi: \{(m, n, p) \in \mathbb{N}^3 : 0 \leq p \leq m \leq n\} \longrightarrow \mathbb{K},$$

define a sequence $(I_n)_{n \geq 0} \subset V$ by

$$I_n = \sum_{m=0}^n \sum_{p=0}^m \phi(m, n, p) J_p.$$

Then for each $n \geq 0$ one has

$$I_n = \sum_{p=0}^n \sum_{m=p}^n \phi(m, n, p) J_p = \sum_{p=0}^n \left(\sum_{m=p}^n \phi(m, n, p) \right) J_p.$$

Proposition 8

For a, b positive real numbers, the integral $\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(ax)}{x \cosh^b(x)} dx$ converges if and only if $a < b$.

Proof:

Consider the integral

$$I := \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(ax)}{x \cosh^b(x)} dx,$$

where $a, b \in (0, +\infty)R$.

Note that the numerator $\sinh(ax)$ is an odd function, and the denominator $x \cosh^b(x)$ is also odd because x is odd and $\cosh^b(x)$ is even. Hence, the integrand is an even function. This allows us to write

$$I = 2 \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(ax)}{x \cosh^b(x)} dx.$$

Although the factor $1/x$ suggests a singularity at $x = 0$, it is removable because of the $\sinh(ax)$ factor on the numerator.

As $x \rightarrow +\infty$, one has the asymptotic $\sinh x \sim \frac{1}{2}e^x$, $\cosh x \sim \frac{1}{2}e^x$. It follows

$$\sinh(ax) \sim \frac{1}{2}e^{ax}, \quad \cosh^b(x) \sim \left(\frac{e^x}{2}\right)^b = \frac{e^{bx}}{2^b}.$$

Thus,

$$\frac{\sinh(ax)}{x \cosh^b(x)} \sim \frac{\frac{1}{2}e^{(a)x}}{x \cdot \frac{e^{bx}}{2^b}} = \frac{2^{b-1}}{x} e^{(a-b)x}.$$

The integral converges at infinity if and only if the exponent satisfies

$$a - b < 0 \iff a < b.$$

Proposition 9

For a, b, c, d suitable real numbers ensuring the convergence,

$$\int_0^1 \frac{x^a - x^b}{(1+x^c)^d \ln x} dx = \int_{\frac{b+1}{c}}^{\frac{a+1}{c}} B\left(\frac{1}{2}; s, d-s\right) ds = \int_{\frac{b+1}{c}}^{\frac{a+1}{c}} \int_0^{\frac{1}{2}} t^{s-1} (1-t)^{d-s-1} dt ds$$

Proof:

Let $I_{a,b,c,d} := \int_0^1 \frac{x^a - x^b}{(1+x^c)^d \ln x} dx$, which becomes following after the substitution $u = x^c$

$$I_{a,b,c,d} = \int_0^1 \frac{u^{\frac{a+1}{c}-1} - u^{\frac{b+1}{c}-1}}{(1+u)^d \ln u} du$$

It can be split in two to provide

$$I_{a,b,c,d} = \int_0^1 \frac{u^{\frac{a+1}{c}-1}}{(1+u)^d \ln u} du - \int_0^1 \frac{u^{\frac{b+1}{c}-1}}{(1+u)^d \ln u} du$$

On setting $F_d(s) := \int_0^1 \frac{u^{s-1}}{(1+u)^d \ln u} du$, one becomes from the fundamental theorem of calculus

$$I_{a,b,c,d} = F_d\left(\frac{a+1}{c}\right) - F_d\left(\frac{b+1}{c}\right) = [F_d(s)]_{\frac{b+1}{c}}^{\frac{a+1}{c}} = \left[\int_{\frac{b+1}{c}}^{\frac{a+1}{c}} \frac{\partial}{\partial s} F_d(s) ds \right]$$

On differentiating with respect to s , one becomes

$$I_{a,b,c,d} = \int_{\frac{b+1}{c}}^{\frac{a+1}{c}} \int_0^1 \frac{u^{s-1}}{(1+u)^d} du ds$$

We start from the integral:

$$\int_0^1 \frac{u^{s-1}}{(1+u)^d} du$$

Make the substitution $u = \frac{t}{1-t}$, so that:

$$du = \frac{1}{(1-t)^2} dt, \quad u^{s-1} = \left(\frac{t}{1-t}\right)^{s-1}, \quad (1+u)^d = (1-t)^{-d}$$

Thus:

$$\frac{u^{s-1}}{(1+u)^d} du = \left(\frac{t}{1-t} \right)^{s-1} (1-t)^{-d} \cdot \frac{1}{(1-t)^2} dt = t^{s-1} (1-t)^{d-s-1} dt$$

Hence:

$$\int_0^1 \frac{u^{s-1}}{(1+u)^d} du = \int_0^{\frac{1}{2}} t^{s-1} (1-t)^{d-s-1} dt = B\left(\frac{1}{2}; s, d-s\right)$$

On putting in $I_{a,b,c,d}$, we get

$$I_{a,b,c,d} = \int_{\frac{b+1}{c}}^{\frac{a+1}{c}} B\left(\frac{1}{2}; s, d-s\right) ds = \int_{\frac{b+1}{c}}^{\frac{a+1}{c}} \int_0^{\frac{1}{2}} t^{s-1} (1-t)^{d-s-1} dt ds$$

Proposition 10

For $n \in \mathbb{N}^*$,

$$\beta'(1-2n) = (-1)^{n+1} \frac{2^{2n-1} (2n-1)!}{\pi^{2n-1}} \beta(2n)$$

Proof:

Malmsten proved in 1842 [1] the following functional equation

$$\beta(1-s) = \left(\frac{\pi}{2}\right)^{-s} \sin\left(\frac{\pi s}{2}\right) \Gamma(s) \beta(s)$$

Let $\chi(s) := \left(\frac{\pi}{2}\right)^{-s} \sin\left(\frac{\pi s}{2}\right) \Gamma(s)$, so we get $\beta(1-s) = \chi(s) \beta(s)$. On differentiating with respect to s , we get

$$-\beta'(1-s) = \chi'(s) \beta(s) + \chi(s) \beta'(s)$$

We see trivially that $\chi(2n) = 0$ due to the sin function. It remains

$$-\beta'(1-2n) = \chi'(2n) \beta(2n)$$

One has

$$\chi'(2n) = \left. \frac{d}{ds} (\chi(s)) \right|_{s=2n}$$

. Let $\Delta(s) := \left(\frac{\pi}{2}\right)^{-s} \Gamma(s)$, so that $\chi(s) = \Delta(s) \sin\left(\frac{\pi s}{2}\right)$. On differentiating with respect to s , we have

$$\chi'(s) = \Delta'(s) \sin\left(\frac{\pi s}{2}\right) + \frac{\pi}{2} \Delta(s) \cos\left(\frac{\pi s}{2}\right)$$

On evaluating this equality for $s = 2n$ and putting it back in the earlier relation, we prove the claim.

Proposition 11

$$\forall n \in \mathbb{N}^*, r \in \llbracket 0, n-1 \rrbracket, \frac{d^r}{dx^r} \tanh^n x = \sum_{\bar{k}^2 = -r}^r C_{n,k,r} \tanh^{n+k} x$$

$$\frac{d^{n-1}}{dx^{n-1}} \tanh^n x = \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} C_{n,2k+1-n,n-1} \tanh^{2k+1} x$$

where

$$C_{n,k,r} := \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } k = r = 0 \\ 0 & \text{if } k \notin \llbracket -r, r \rrbracket \\ (n+k+1)C_{n,k+1,r-1} - (n+k-1)C_{n,k-1,r-1} & \text{if } k \in \llbracket -r, r \rrbracket \end{cases}$$

Proof

Proof of the first claim

The first few derivatives of $\tanh^n x$ are:

$$(\tanh^n x)' = n(\tanh^{n-1} x - \tanh^{n+1} x),$$

$$(\tanh^n x)'' = n\left((n-1)\tanh^{n-2} x - 2n\tanh^n x + (n+1)\tanh^{n+2} x\right),$$

$$\begin{aligned} (\tanh^n x)^{(3)} &= n\left((n-1)(n-2)\tanh^{n-3} x - (3n^2 - 3n + 2)\tanh^{n-1} x \right. \\ &\quad \left. + (3n^2 + 3n + 2)\tanh^{n+1} x - (n+1)(n+2)\tanh^{n+3} x\right). \end{aligned}$$

It is enough to conjecture that $\frac{d^r}{dx^r} \tanh^n x = \sum_{\bar{k}^2 = -r}^r C_{n,k,r} \tanh^{n+k} x$, where $C_{n,k,r} = 0$, if $k \notin \llbracket -r, r \rrbracket$; which builds our induction hypothesis.

On differentiating again, we obtain

$$\frac{d^{r+1}}{dx^{r+1}} \tanh^n x = \sum_{\bar{k}^2 = -r}^r (n+k)C_{n,k,r}(1 - \tanh^2 x) \tanh^{n+k-1} x$$

Which becomes following after separating sums

$$\frac{d^{r+1}}{dx^{r+1}} \tanh^n x = \sum_{\bar{k}^2 = -r}^r (n+k)C_{n,k,r} \tanh^{n+k-1} x - \sum_{\bar{k}^2 = -r}^r (n+k)C_{n,k,r} \tanh^{n+k+1} x$$

On re-indexing k such that the exponents of \tanh become $n+k$, we arrive at :

$$\frac{d^{r+1}}{dx^{r+1}} \tanh^n x = \sum_{\bar{k}^2 = -r-1}^{r-1} (n+k+1)C_{n,k+1,r} \tanh^{n+k} x - \sum_{\bar{k}^2 = -r+1}^{r+1} (n+k-1)C_{n,k-1,r} \tanh^{n+k} x$$

Now, bearing in mind that the coefficient $C_{n,k,r}$ self vanishes when k is out of bounds, we write

$$\frac{d^{r+1}}{dx^{r+1}} \tanh^n x = \sum_{\bar{k}^2 = -r-1}^{r+1} [(n+k+1)C_{n,k+1,r} - (n+k-1)C_{n,k-1,r}] \tanh^{n+k} x$$

As claimed...

Proof of the second claim

In virtue of the first formula, we deduce

$$\frac{d^{n-1}}{dx^{n-1}} \tanh^n x = \sum_{\bar{k}^2 = -n+1}^{n-1} C_{n,k,n-1} \tanh^{n+k} x$$

On re-indexing k such that the exponent of \tanh becomes k , we obtain

$$\frac{d^{n-1}}{dx^{n-1}} \tanh^n x = \sum_{\bar{k}^2 = 1}^{2n-1} C_{n,k-n,n-1} \tanh^k x$$

This last formula means that the even indexes are skipped along the summation operator and only odd indexes survive. Now, the last odd index is at $k = n - 1$, we conclude the second equality as claimed...

Proposition 12

For suitable natural integers k and m

$$\sinh^{2k+1} x \cosh^{2m} x = \frac{1}{2^{2m+2k}} \sum_{r=0}^{m+k} P_{m,k,r} \sinh((2r+1)x)$$

where

$$P_{m,k,r} := \sum_{j=0}^{2k+1} (-1)^j \binom{2k+1}{j} \binom{2m}{m+k-r-j}$$

Proof

We start from

$$\sinh^{2k+1} x = \frac{1}{2^{2k+1}} (e^x - e^{-x})^{2k+1},$$

$$\cosh^{2m} x = \frac{1}{2^{2m}} (e^x + e^{-x})^{2m}.$$

On using the Newton's binomial formula, we arrive at

$$\sinh^{2k+1} x = \frac{1}{2^{2k+1}} \sum_{j=0}^{2k+1} \binom{2k+1}{j} (-1)^j e^{(2k+1-2j)x},$$

$$\cosh^{2m} x = \frac{1}{2^{2m}} \sum_{j=0}^{2m} \binom{2m}{j} e^{(2m-2j)x}.$$

On factorizing, we read

$$\sinh^{2k+1} x = \left(\frac{e^x}{2}\right)^{2k+1} \sum_{j=0}^{2k+1} \binom{2k+1}{j} (-e^{-2x})^j,$$

$$\cosh^{2m} x = \left(\frac{e^x}{2}\right)^{2m} \sum_{j=0}^{2m} \binom{2m}{j} (e^{-2x})^j.$$

Since the binomial coefficients are 0 when arguments are out of bounds, we extend then the sums to series as follow

$$\sinh^{2k+1} x = \left(\frac{e^x}{2}\right)^{2k+1} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \binom{2k+1}{j} (-e^{-2x})^j,$$

$$\cosh^{2m} x = \left(\frac{e^x}{2}\right)^{2m} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \binom{2m}{j} (e^{-2x})^j.$$

The Cauchy product comes into game to yield

$$\sinh^{2k+1} x \cosh^{2m} x = \left(\frac{e^x}{2}\right)^{2k+1+2m} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \left(\sum_{j=0}^n \binom{2k+1}{j} \binom{2m}{n-j} (-1)^j \right) e^{-2nx}.$$

From the binomial expansion it follows directly that the index j ranges up to $2k+1$. Moreover, the condition $n-j \leq 2m$ must hold, which is equivalent to

$$n \leq 2m + j \leq 2m + (2k+1).$$

Hence the index n is bounded above by $2m + 2k + 1$. With these bounds in place, we obtain

$$\sinh^{2k+1} x \cosh^{2m} x = \left(\frac{e^x}{2}\right)^{2k+1+2m} \sum_{n=0}^{2m+2k+1} \left(\sum_{j=0}^{2k+1} (-1)^j \binom{2k+1}{j} \binom{2m}{n-j} \right) e^{-2nx}.$$

On setting $S_{n,m,k} := \sum_{j=0}^{2k+1} (-1)^j \binom{2k+1}{j} \binom{2m}{n-j}$, the outer sum is split into two in following manner :

$$\sinh^{2k+1} x \cosh^{2m} x = \left(\frac{e^x}{2}\right)^{2k+1+2m} \left(\sum_{n=0}^{m+k} S_{n,m,k} e^{-2nx} + \sum_{n=m+k+1}^{2m+2k+1} S_{n,m,k} e^{-2nx} \right).$$

On re-indexing the second sum such that it starts from 0 and on putting the outer exponential into the sums, we have

$$\sinh^{2k+1} x \cosh^{2m} x = \frac{1}{2^{2m+2k+1}} \sum_{n=0}^{m+k} \left[S_{n,m,k} e^{(2m+2k+1-2n)x} + S_{2m+2k+1-n,m,k} e^{-(2m+2k+1-2n)x} \right].$$

We verify easily with re-indexation that $S_{2m+2k+1-n,m,k} = -S_{n,m,k}$. We conclude then

$$\begin{aligned} \sinh^{2k+1} x \cosh^{2m} x &= \frac{1}{2^{2m+2k}} \sum_{n=0}^{m+k} S_{n,m,k} \sinh((2m+2k+1-2n)x) \\ &= \frac{1}{2^{2m+2k}} \sum_{r=0}^{m+k} S_{m+k-r,m,k} \sinh((2r+1)x). \end{aligned}$$

As claimed.

2 Preliminaries and Background

The point of departure of our investigations was the Malmsten's integral

$$I = \int_0^1 \frac{x(x^4 - 4x^2 + 1) \ln \ln \frac{1}{x}}{(1+x^2)^4} dx$$

that has been firstly evaluated to $\frac{7\zeta(3)}{8\pi^2}$ by *Iaroslav V, Blagouchine* in 2014[1, p.81]. Therefore the proof of its convergence is omitted here for the sake of brevity. Notwithstanding, the presence of singularities at its bounds requires to treat it with some care. As consequence, we rewrite the integral as the limit $I = \lim_{\xi \rightarrow 0^+} \int_{\xi}^{1-\xi} \frac{x(x^4 - 4x^2 + 1) \ln \ln \frac{1}{x}}{(1+x^2)^4} dx$

We consider first $u'(x) = \frac{x(x^4 - 4x^2 + 1)}{(1+x^2)^4}$ and we show easily that its anti-derivative is $u(x) = \frac{x^2(1-x^2)}{2(1+x^2)^3}$. Then we consider $v(x) = \ln \ln \frac{1}{x}$ and observe that its derivative is $v'(x) = \frac{1}{x \ln x}$. Since both functions $u, v \in \mathcal{C}^1[\xi, 1-\xi]$, an integration by parts yields

$$I = \lim_{\xi \rightarrow 0^+} \left(\left[\frac{x^2(1-x^2) \ln \ln \frac{1}{x}}{2(1+x^2)^3} \right]_{\xi}^{1-\xi} - \frac{1}{2} \int_{\xi}^{1-\xi} \frac{x^2(1-x^2)}{(1+x^2)^3 x \ln x} dx \right)$$

Which implies

$$I = \lim_{\xi \rightarrow 0^+} \underbrace{\left[\frac{x^2(1-x^2) \ln \ln \frac{1}{x}}{2(1+x^2)^3} \right]_{\xi}^{1-\xi}}_0 - \lim_{\xi \rightarrow 0^+} \frac{1}{2} \int_{\xi}^{1-\xi} \frac{x^2(1-x^2)}{(1+x^2)^3 x \ln x} dx$$

It remains

$$I = \lim_{\xi \rightarrow 0^+} \frac{1}{2} \int_{\xi}^{1-\xi} \frac{x(x^2 - 1)}{(1+x^2)^3 \ln x} dx$$

And performing the change of variable $u = x^2$ leads to

$$I = \frac{1}{2} \lim_{\xi \rightarrow 0^+} \int_{\sqrt{\xi}}^{\sqrt{1-\xi}} \frac{x-1}{(1+x)^3 \ln x} dx$$

The term in the limit is then separated into two in following manner :

$$I = \frac{1}{2} \lim_{\xi \rightarrow 0^+} \left[\int_{\sqrt{\xi}}^{\sqrt{1-\xi}} \frac{x}{(1+x)^3 \ln x} dx - \int_{\sqrt{\xi}}^{\sqrt{1-\xi}} \frac{1}{(1+x)^3 \ln x} dx \right]$$

On letting $\Phi_\xi(y) := \int_{\sqrt{\xi}}^{\sqrt{1-\xi}} \frac{x^y}{(1+x)^3 \ln x} dx$, one has from the fundamental theorem of calculus

$$I = \frac{1}{2} \lim_{\xi \rightarrow 0^+} (\Phi_\xi(1) - \Phi_\xi(0)) = \frac{1}{2} \lim_{\xi \rightarrow 0^+} [\Phi_\xi(y)]_{y=0}^{y=1} = \frac{1}{2} \lim_{\xi \rightarrow 0^+} \int_0^1 \frac{\partial}{\partial y} [\Phi_\xi(y)] dy$$

The equality becomes this after performing the differentiation with respect to y

$$I = \frac{1}{2} \lim_{\xi \rightarrow 0^+} \int_0^1 \int_{\sqrt{\xi}}^{\sqrt{1-\xi}} \frac{x^y}{(1+x)^3} dx dy$$

The substitution $x = \frac{t}{1-t}$ transforms the equality further to

$$I = \frac{1}{2} \lim_{\xi \rightarrow 0^+} \int_0^1 \int_a^b x^y (1-x)^{1-y} dx dy \left(\text{where } b := \frac{\sqrt{1-\xi}}{1+\sqrt{1-\xi}} \text{ and } a := \frac{\sqrt{\xi}}{1+\sqrt{\xi}} \right)$$

One recognizes the inner integral as the incomplete beta function defined as $B(x; a, b) := \int_0^x t^{a-1} (1-t)^{b-1} dt$ and rewrite then the integral with it

$$I = \frac{1}{2} \lim_{\xi \rightarrow 0^+} \int_0^1 \left[B\left(\frac{\sqrt{1-\xi}}{1+\sqrt{1-\xi}}; 1+y, 2-y\right) - B\left(\frac{\sqrt{\xi}}{1+\sqrt{\xi}}; 1+y, 2-y\right) \right] dy$$

And after separating the limits, it becomes

$$I = \frac{1}{2} \lim_{\xi \rightarrow 0^+} \int_0^1 B\left(\frac{\sqrt{1-\xi}}{1+\sqrt{1-\xi}}; 1+y, 2-y\right) dy - \underbrace{\frac{1}{2} \lim_{\xi \rightarrow 0^+} \int_0^1 B\left(\frac{\sqrt{\xi}}{1+\sqrt{\xi}}; 1+y, 2-y\right) dy}_0$$

The survivor is

$$I = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^1 B\left(\frac{1}{2}; 1+y, 2-y\right) dy \stackrel{y \rightarrow 1-u}{=} \frac{1}{2} \int_0^1 B\left(\frac{1}{2}; 2-y, 1+y\right) dy$$

An by enjoying the identity $B(x; a, b) = B(a, b) - B(1-x; b, a)$, we conclude easily

$$\int_0^1 B(1+y, 2-y) dy = \int_0^1 \int_0^1 x^y (1-x)^{1-y} dx dy = \frac{7\zeta(3)}{2\pi^2}$$

where the B-function with two parameters stands for the Euler beta function.

As shown above $\int_0^1 \frac{x(x^2-1)}{(1+x^2)^3 \ln x} dx = \frac{7\zeta(3)}{4\pi^2}$. The change of variable $x \rightarrow \tan u$ is proceeded in this manner :

$$\begin{aligned}
\int_0^1 \frac{x(x^2-1)}{(1+x^2)^3 \ln x} dx &= \frac{7\zeta(3)}{4\pi^2} \Rightarrow \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\tan u(\tan^2 u-1)}{(1+\tan^2 u)^3 \ln(\tan u)} (1+\tan^2 u) du = \frac{7\zeta(3)}{4\pi^2} \\
&\Rightarrow \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\cos^4 u \tan u(\tan^2 u-1)}{\ln(\tan u)} du = \frac{7\zeta(3)}{4\pi^2} \\
&\Rightarrow \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\cos u \sin u(\sin^2 u-\cos^2 u)}{\ln(\tan u)} du = \frac{7\zeta(3)}{4\pi^2} \\
&\Rightarrow -\int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\cos u \sin u \cos(2u)}{\ln(\tan u)} du = \frac{7\zeta(3)}{4\pi^2} \\
&\Rightarrow \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin 4u}{\ln(\tan u)} du = -\frac{7\zeta(3)}{\pi^2}
\end{aligned}$$

Starting with this last representation and performing the change of variable $x = \frac{\pi}{4} - u$ yields

$$\int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} \frac{x \sin 4u}{\ln(\tan u)} du = -\frac{7\zeta(3)}{2\pi}$$

Blagouchine introduced in fact more generally the family of integrals on page 80:

$$I_n = \int_0^1 \frac{x^{n-1} \ln \ln \frac{1}{x}}{(1+x^2)^n} dx = \int_1^\infty \frac{x^{n-1} \ln \ln x}{(1+x^2)^n} dx = \frac{1}{2n} \int_0^\infty \frac{\ln x}{\cosh^n x} dx,$$

And with contour integration technique, he obtained further[1] :

$$I_2 = -\frac{1}{2} \ln 2 + \frac{1}{4} \ln \pi - \frac{\gamma}{4}$$

$$I_6 = -\frac{1}{60} \ln 2 + \frac{1}{120} \ln \pi - \frac{\gamma}{120} - \frac{7\zeta(3)}{192\pi^2} - \frac{31\zeta(5)}{320\pi^4}$$

where γ means the Euler-Mascheroni constant. We can rewrite I_6 as

$$I_6 = -\frac{1}{30} I_2 - \frac{7\zeta(3)}{192\pi^2} - \frac{31\zeta(5)}{320\pi^4}$$

And by replacing I_6, I_2 and $\zeta(3)$ by their $\ln \ln$ integral representations, it follows:

$$\int_0^1 \frac{x(x^8 - 26x^6 + 66x^4 - 26x^2 + 1) \ln \ln \frac{1}{x}}{(1+x^2)^6} dx = -\frac{93\zeta(5)}{8\pi^4}$$

This integral as well as this derivation method is much more detailed on [20]. Same remarks and same algebra on I_8 yield:

$$\int_0^1 \frac{x(x^{12} - 120x^{10} + 1191x^8 - 2416x^6 + 1191x^4 - 120x^2 + 1) \ln \ln \frac{1}{x}}{(1+x^2)^8} dx = \frac{5715\zeta(7)}{16\pi^6}$$

The author of the article on [20] asked whether the zeta values adhere to some pattern of Malmsten's integrals. A general Malmsten-like integral of zeta values at odd integers is given further in this work whereas those for even integers remain out of our reach.

And by pursuing the same line of reasoning as above, the two later Malmsten's integrals take the form :

$$\frac{\zeta(5)}{\pi^4} = -\frac{1}{186} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin 4x}{\ln(\tan x)} dx + \frac{1}{124} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin 8x}{\ln(\tan x)} dx$$

$$\frac{\zeta(7)}{\pi^6} = -\frac{17}{91\,440} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin(4x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx + \frac{1}{1\,524} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin(8x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx - \frac{1}{2\,032} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin(12x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx$$

These results may follow general patterns. In fact, it is easy to recognize the pattern

$$\int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin 4nx}{\ln(\tan x)} dx$$

where $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and the Malmsten's integrals may convince us to conjecture that

$$\int_0^1 \frac{\text{Li}_{-2n-1}(-x^2) \ln \ln \frac{1}{x}}{x} dx \in \mathbb{Q} \frac{\zeta(2n+1)}{\pi^{2n}}$$

where $\text{Li}_s(z)$ is the polylogarithm of order s evaluated at the argument z . These two integrals build the main study of the following investigations.

3 On the function $f_{k,n}(z) := \frac{\sinh((2k+1)z)}{z \cosh^n z}$

An integral that will help us to state a strong conjecture about the irrationality or transcendence of the ratios $\frac{\zeta(2n+1)}{\pi^{2n+1}}$ and $\frac{\beta(2n)}{\pi^{2n}}$ is

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh z}{z \cosh^n z} dz.$$

The arithmetic nature of this integral is sufficient for our conjectures, but we generalize the study to the integral

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh((2k+1)z)}{z \cosh^n z} dz$$

and extract from it the case $k=0$ (for our conjectures). The purpose of this section is to study the residue computation and the behavior of the function

$$f_{k,n}(z) := \frac{\sinh((2k+1)z)}{z \cosh^n z}$$

along a chosen integration path, in order to compute the exact value of the integral

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh((2k+1)z)}{z \cosh^n z} dz$$

and to understand its arithmetic structure. While it may seem more natural to study the more general integral

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(kz)}{z \cosh^n z} dz,$$

for brevity, we will see that the behavior of this integral strongly depends on whether k and n are odd or even. This leads us to consider four distinct cases:

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh((2k+1)z)}{z \cosh^{2n} z} dz, \quad \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(2kz)}{z \cosh^{2n} z} dz,$$

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh((2k+1)z)}{z \cosh^{2n+1} z} dz, \quad \text{and} \quad \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(2kz)}{z \cosh^{2n+1} z} dz.$$

Let us state right away that these integrals yield combinations of values of L -functions but do not follow a unified pattern, even when grouped in pairs. Nevertheless, we put the focus solely on the integral

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh((2k+1)z)}{z \cosh^n z} dz$$

for two main reasons:

- *The integrals*

$$\int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin(4nx)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx \quad \text{and} \quad \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\cos(2(2n+1)x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx$$

exhibit a particularly intriguing kernel that is central to our subsequent conjectures. Specifically, their linear combinations yield expressions with a common denominator, $\ln(\tan x)$, a feature that is both unique and rare in this context. Moreover, the evaluation of these integrals depends entirely and respectively on the knowledge of the quantities

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh((2k+1)z)}{z \cosh^{2n+1} z} dz \quad \text{and} \quad \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh((2k+1)z)}{z \cosh^{2n} z} dz.$$

- *The values of*

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(2kz)}{z \cosh^{2n+1} z} dz \quad \text{and} \quad \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(2kz)}{z \cosh^{2n} z} dz$$

can be deduced much more easily with a **single** formula from the values of the integral

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh z}{z \cosh^n z} dz.$$

We will therefore concentrate our efforts on a deeper study of the integrals

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh((2k+1)z)}{z \cosh^{2n} z} dz \quad \text{and} \quad \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh((2k+1)z)}{z \cosh^{2n+1} z} dz,$$

which fall under the general form

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh((2k+1)z)}{z \cosh^n z} dz.$$

§1. Contour integration setup

We define the function of the complex variable $f_{k,n}(z) := \frac{\sinh(2k+1)z}{z \cosh^n z}$. The contour of integration, designated by $C_{N,r}$ is the rectangle bounding the region of the complex plane defined by $\begin{cases} 0 \leq \text{Im}(z) \leq 2N\pi & (N \in \mathbb{N}) \\ |\text{Re}(z)| \leq r & (r \in \mathbb{R}_+^*) \end{cases}$

Following this counterclockwise path of integration allows to split the line integral into these four integrals

$$\oint_{C_{N,r}} f_{k,n}(z) dz = \int_{-r}^r f_{k,n}(z) dz + \int_r^{r+2Ni\pi} f_{k,n}(z) dz + \int_{r+2Ni\pi}^{-r+2Ni\pi} f_{k,n}(z) dz + \int_{-r+2Ni\pi}^{-r} f_{k,n}(z) dz \quad (1)$$

$$= \int_{-r}^r f_{k,n}(x) dx + i \int_0^{2N\pi} f_{k,n}(r + ix) dx + \int_r^{-r} f_{k,n}(x + 2Ni\pi) dx \quad (2)$$

$$+ i \int_{2N\pi}^0 f_{k,n}(-r + ix) dx \quad (3)$$

$$= \int_{-r}^r f_{k,n}(x) dx + i \int_0^{2N\pi} [f_{k,n}(r + ix) - f_{k,n}(r - ix)] dx \quad (4)$$

$$- \int_{-r}^r f_{k,n}(x + 2Ni\pi) dx \quad (5)$$

Hint: At line (2) perform the changes of variable $z = r + ix$, $z = x + 2Ni\pi$ and $z = -r + ix$ respectively in the second, third and fourth integral. The minus signs appear after switching up the order of bounds of integration.

Since, Jordan's lemma could help neither by the evaluation of the second nor the third integral, evaluating their modulus may be proceeded as follow:

$$\left| \int_0^{2N\pi} [f_{k,n}(r + ix) - f_{k,n}(r - ix)] dx \right| \leq \int_0^{2N\pi} |f_{k,n}(r + ix) - f_{k,n}(r - ix)| dx \quad (1)$$

$$\leq \int_0^{2N\pi} |f_{k,n}(r + ix) + f_{k,n}(r - ix)| dx \quad (2)$$

$$= \int_0^{2N\pi} |f_{k,n}(r + ix)| + |f_{k,n}(\overline{r + ix})| dx \quad (3)$$

$$= \int_0^{2N\pi} |f_{k,n}(r+ix)| + \left| \overline{f_{k,n}(r+ix)} \right| dx \quad (4)$$

$$= 2 \int_0^{2N\pi} |f_{k,n}(r+ix)| dx \quad (5)$$

$$= 2 \int_0^{2N\pi} \frac{|\sinh(2k+1)(r+ix)|}{|r+ix| |\cosh(r+ix)|^n} dx \quad (6)$$

$$= 2 \int_0^{2N\pi} \frac{1}{\sqrt{r^2+x^2}} \cdot \frac{\sqrt{\sinh^2((2k+1)r) + \sin^2((2k+1)x)}}{\sqrt{\cosh^2 r - \sin^2 x}^n} dx \quad (7)$$

$$\leq 2 \int_0^{2N\pi} \frac{1}{\sqrt{r^2+x^2}} \cdot \frac{\cosh((2k+1)r)}{|\sinh r|^n} dx \quad (8)$$

$$\leq 2 \frac{\cosh((2k+1)r)}{|\sinh r|^n} \int_0^{2N\pi} \frac{1}{\sqrt{r^2+x^2}} dx \quad (9)$$

$$= 2 \frac{\cosh((2k+1)r)}{|\sinh r|^n} \cdot \operatorname{arcsinh}\left(\frac{2N\pi}{r}\right) \longrightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } r \longrightarrow +\infty \quad (10)$$

Hint: At line (4), remark first that $f_{k,n}$ satisfies the functional equation $f_{k,n}(\bar{z}) = \overline{f_{k,n}(z)}$; line (5) follows from $|z| = |-z| = |\bar{z}| = |-\bar{z}|$ and line (7) is straightforward from the addition formulas for the hyperbolic functions and the relationships between the circular trigonometry and the hyperbolic trigonometry. Line (8) comes from bounding above the second multiplication factor of the integrand in the previous line by applying the inequality $-1 < \sin x < 1$. The proof that the last expression collapses to zero as r becomes greater follows from the fast convergence of the denominator.

On the second hand,

$$\begin{aligned} \left| \int_{-r}^r f_{k,n}(x+2Ni\pi) dx \right| &\leq \int_{-r}^r |f_{k,n}(x+2Ni\pi)| dx \\ &= \int_{-r}^r \frac{|\sinh(2k+1)(x+2Ni\pi)|}{|x+2Ni\pi| |\cosh(x+2Ni\pi)|^n} dx \\ &= \int_{-r}^r \frac{|\sinh((2k+1)x)|}{\sqrt{x^2+4N^2\pi^2} \cosh^n x} dx \\ &\leq \sup_{x \in [-r,r]} \frac{|\sinh((2k+1)x)|}{\cosh^n x} \int_{-r}^r \frac{1}{\sqrt{x^2+4N^2\pi^2}} dx \\ &= 2 \sup_{x \in [-r,r]} \frac{|\sinh((2k+1)x)|}{\cosh^n x} \times \operatorname{arcsinh}\left(\frac{r}{2N\pi}\right) \longrightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } N \longrightarrow +\infty \end{aligned}$$

The zero value of the last limit is justified by the fact the sup exists (since the function is continuous on the compact $[-r, r]$) and does not depend on N and is regarded as

nothing more than a mere constant. Now the *arcsinh* of the related term tends to 0, which makes all the limit vanish.

As consequence

$$\oint_{C_{+\infty,+\infty}} f_{k,n}(z) dz = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} f_{k,n}(z) dz$$

§2. Residue computation

When the power at the denominator is odd

We define the function of the complex variable $f_{k,n}(z) := \frac{\sinh(2k+1)z}{z \cosh^{2n+1} z}$. It is easy to show that f has a removable singularity at $z = 0$ and poles of the $(2n+1)$ -th order at $z_l = \frac{(2l+1)i\pi}{2}$ ($l \in \mathbb{Z}$). The residue computation is done here by finding the Laurent expansion of f around z_l .

We begin by setting $z := z_l + w$, since we are expanding around z_l

One has :

$$\cosh^{2n+1} z = \cosh^{2n+1}(z_l + w) = \underbrace{(\cosh z_l \cosh w + \sinh z_l \sinh w)}_0^{2n+1} = \sinh^{2n+1} z_l \sinh^{2n+1} w$$

Applying the equality given by *Proposition 2* yields

$$\cosh^{2n+1} z = \frac{1}{4^n} \sinh^{2n+1} z_l \sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^k \binom{2n+1}{k} \sinh(2n+1-2k)w$$

Since w approaches 0, a further expansion comes after using the Taylor expansion $\sinh w = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{w^{2n+1}}{(2n+1)!}$:

$$\cosh^{2n+1} z = \frac{1}{4^n} \sinh^{2n+1} z_l \sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^k \binom{2n+1}{k} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{(2n-2k+1)^{2j+1}}{(2j+1)!} w^{2j+1}$$

And after interchanging the summation operators

$$\cosh^{2n+1} z = \sinh^{2n+1} z_l \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \left[\frac{1}{4^n (2j+1)!} \sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^k \binom{2n+1}{k} (2n-2k+1)^{2j+1} \right] w^{2j+1}$$

Interesting fact : all coefficients of this series are 0 when $j < n$. One shows it by remarking firstly that $g(z) := \frac{\cosh^{2n+1} z}{(z - z_l)^{2n+1} \sinh^{2n+1} z_l}$ is analytic around z_l because the denominator

cancels the singularities at the numerator with the same multiplicity. Secondly, one sees trivially that

$$\lim_{z \rightarrow z_l} g(z) = 1$$

because the derivative of \cosh is \sinh . Which implies that the Taylor expansion of g around z_l is

$$1 + O(w)$$

It comes out that the series expansion of $\cosh^{2n+1} z$ around z_l is

$$\sinh^{2n+1} z_l w^{2n+1} + O(w^{2n+3})$$

Which means exactly that all coefficients of w^{2j+1} are 0 when $j < n$. It is formalized under following theorem :

$$\forall n \in \mathbb{N}^*, \quad \sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^k \binom{2n+1}{k} (2n+1-2k)^{2j+1} = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } j \in \llbracket 0, n-1 \rrbracket \\ 4^n (2n+1)!, & \text{if } j = n \end{cases}$$

Back to the expansion of $\cosh^{2n+1} z$. Since all coefficients are 0 for all $j < n$, one writes :

$$\cosh^{2n+1} z = \sinh^{2n+1} z_l \sum_{j=n}^{\infty} \left[\frac{1}{4^n (2j+1)!} \sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^k \binom{2n+1}{k} (2n-2k+1)^{2j+1} \right] w^{2j+1}$$

From this equality, we re-index j to 0 and we factor out w^{2n+1} . We become :

$$\cosh^{2n+1} z = \sinh^{2n+1} z_l w^{2n+1} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \left[\frac{1}{4^n (2j+2n+1)!} \sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^k \binom{2n+1}{k} (2n-2k+1)^{2j+2n+1} \right] w^{2j}$$

We have $\cosh^{2n+1} z = \sinh^{2n+1} z_l w^{2n+1} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} a_{j,n} w^j$ where

$$a_{j,n} := \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } j \text{ is odd} \\ \frac{1}{4^n (j+2n+1)!} \sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^k \binom{2n+1}{k} (2n-2k+1)^{j+2n+1} & \text{if } j \text{ is even} \end{cases}$$

Taking the inverse leads to an expression of the kind $\frac{1}{\cosh^{2n+1} z} = \frac{1}{\sinh^{2n+1} z_l w^{2n+1}} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} c_{j,n} w^j$

where

$$\left(\sum_{j=0}^{\infty} a_{j,n} w^j \right) \left(\sum_{j=0}^{\infty} c_{j,n} w^j \right) = 1$$

A recurrence formula for $c_{j,n}$ is derived through the Cauchy product as follow :

$$\begin{aligned}
\left(\sum_{j=0}^{\infty} a_{j,n} w^j \right) \left(\sum_{j=0}^{\infty} c_{j,n} w^j \right) &= 1 \Rightarrow \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \left(\sum_{k=0}^j a_{k,n} c_{j-k,n} \right) w^j = 1 \\
&\Rightarrow \begin{cases} a_{0,n} c_{0,n} = 1 \\ \sum_{k=0}^j a_{k,n} c_{j-k,n} = 0 \end{cases} \\
&\Rightarrow \begin{cases} c_{0,n} = \frac{1}{a_{0,n}} \\ c_{j,n} = -\frac{1}{a_{0,n}} \sum_{k=1}^j a_{k,n} c_{j-k,n} \end{cases} \\
&\Rightarrow \begin{cases} c_{0,n} = 1 \\ c_{j,n} = -\sum_{k=1}^j a_{k,n} c_{j-k,n} \end{cases} \quad (\text{since } a_{0,n} = 1)
\end{aligned}$$

It is even possible to prove with a trivial induction that $c_{j,n} = 0$ if j is odd. Let

$$L(z) := \frac{\sinh(2k+1)z}{z}$$

. Since L is analytic at z_l , one has the Taylor expansion :

$$L(z) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{L^{(k)}(z_l)}{k!} w^k$$

The Laurent series of the target function $f_{k,n}$ around z_l is now given by :

$$\begin{aligned}
f_{k,n}(z) &= \frac{1}{\cosh^{2n+1} z} \times L(z) \\
&= \frac{1}{\sinh^{2n+1} z_l w^{2n+1}} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} c_{j,n} w^j \times \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{L^{(k)}(z_l)}{k!} w^k \\
&= \frac{1}{\sinh^{2n+1} z_l w^{2n+1}} (c_{0,n} + c_{2,n}w^2 + c_{4,n}w^4 + O(w^6)) \left(L(z_l) + L'(z_l)w + \frac{L''(z_l)}{2!}w^2 + O(w^3) \right)
\end{aligned}$$

The residue we seek corresponds to the coefficient of w^{-1} in the Laurent expansion of the given expression. To determine this, we consider the product of the two series appearing in the numerator. The key observation is that the denominator includes a factor of w^{2n+1} , so the coefficient of w^{-1} in the overall expression is precisely the coefficient of w^{2n} in the product of the two series in the numerator. Extracting this coefficient yields the desired residue.

$$res_{z=z_l} f_{k,n}(z) = \frac{1}{\sinh^{2n+1} z_l} \left[c_{0,n} \frac{L^{(2n)}(z_l)}{(2n)!} + c_{2,n} \frac{L^{(2n-2)}(z_l)}{(2n-2)!} + \dots + c_{2n-2,n} \frac{L''(z_l)}{2!} + c_{2n,n} L(z_l) \right]$$

Which looks much more beautiful when rewritten with the summation operator

$$res_{z=z_l} f_{k,n}(z) = \frac{1}{\sinh^{2n+1} z_l} \sum_{m=0}^n c_{2m,n} \frac{L^{(2n-2m)}(z_l)}{(2n-2m)!}$$

The Leibniz rule for differentiation helps us to find a closed form of $L^{(2n-2m)}(z_l)$. In fact,

$$\begin{aligned} L^{(2n-2m)}(z_l) &= \frac{d^{2n-2m}}{dz^{2n-2m}} \left(\frac{\sinh((2k+1)z)}{z} \right) \Big|_{z=z_l} \\ &= \frac{d^{2n-2m}}{dz^{2n-2m}} (\sinh((2k+1)z) \cdot z^{-1}) \Big|_{z=z_l} \\ &= \sum_{p=0}^{2n-2m} \binom{2n-2m}{p} \frac{d^p}{dz^p} (\sinh((2k+1)z)) \cdot \frac{d^{2n-2m-p}}{dz^{2n-2m-p}} (z^{-1}) \Big|_{z=z_l} \end{aligned}$$

The following formulas hold for the functions interesting us (easy to prove by induction):

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d^n}{dx^n} (x^{-1}) &= (-1)^n n! x^{-(n+1)} \\ \frac{d^n}{dx^n} \sinh(ax) &= a^n \times \begin{cases} \cosh(ax) & \text{if } n \text{ is odd,} \\ \sinh(ax) & \text{if } n \text{ is even.} \end{cases} \end{aligned}$$

The expression of $L^{(2n-2m)}(z_l)$ becomes :

$$L^{(2n-2m)}(z_l) = \sum_{p=0}^{2n-2m} (-1)^p \binom{2n-2m}{p} (2k+1)^p (2n-2m-p)! h_p(z_l) z_l^{-(2n-2m-p+1)} \quad \text{where}$$

$$h_p(z_l) := \begin{cases} \cosh((2k+1)z_l) & \text{if } p \text{ is odd,} \\ \sinh((2k+1)z_l) & \text{if } p \text{ is even.} \end{cases}$$

Bearing in mind that $\cosh(z_l) = \cosh \frac{(2l+1)i\pi}{2} = 0$ and $\sinh(z_l) = \sinh \frac{(2l+1)i\pi}{2} = (-1)^l i$, one derives a closed form for $h_p(z_l)$ in the following manner :

$$\begin{aligned}
h_p(z_l) &= \begin{cases} \cosh((2k+1)z_l) & \text{if } p \text{ is odd,} \\ \sinh((2k+1)z_l) & \text{if } p \text{ is even} \end{cases} \\
&= \begin{cases} \cosh\left((2k+1)\frac{(2l+1)i\pi}{2}\right) & \text{if } p \text{ is odd,} \\ \sinh\left((2k+1)\frac{(2l+1)i\pi}{2}\right) & \text{if } p \text{ is even} \end{cases} \\
&= \begin{cases} \cosh\left(\frac{(2r+1)i\pi}{2}\right) & \text{if } p \text{ is odd,} \\ \sinh\left(\frac{(2r+1)i\pi}{2}\right) & \text{if } p \text{ is even} \end{cases} \quad r := 2kl + k + l \\
&= \begin{cases} \cosh(z_r) & \text{if } p \text{ is odd,} \\ \sinh(z_r) & \text{if } p \text{ is even} \end{cases} \quad r := 2kl + k + l \\
h_p(z_l) &= \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } p \text{ is odd,} \\ (-1)^{k+l} i & \text{if } p \text{ is even} \end{cases}
\end{aligned}$$

Putting it back in $L^{(2n-2m)}(z_l)$ leads to :

$$\begin{aligned}
L^{(2n-2m)}(z_l) &= \sum_{p=0}^{n-m} \binom{2n-2m}{2p} (2k+1)^{2p} (2n-2m-2p)! (-1)^{k+l} i z_l^{-(2n-2m-2p+1)} \\
&= (-1)^{k+l} \sum_{p=0}^{n-m} \binom{2n-2m}{2p} \frac{(2k+1)^{2p} (2n-2m-2p)!}{z_l^{2n-2m-2p+1}} i \\
&= (-1)^{k+l} \sum_{p=0}^{n-m} \binom{2n-2m}{2p} \frac{(2k+1)^{2n-2m-2p} (2p)!}{z_l^{2p+1}} i \\
&= (-1)^{k+l} \sum_{p=0}^{n-m} \binom{2n-2m}{2p} \frac{(2k+1)^{2n-2m-2p} (2p)!}{\left(\frac{(2l+1)i\pi}{2}\right)^{2p+1}} i \\
&= (-1)^{k+l} \sum_{p=0}^{n-m} \binom{2n-2m}{2p} \frac{2^{2p+1} (2k+1)^{2n-2m-2p} (2p)!}{(-1)^p ((2l+1)\pi)^{2p+1}} \\
L^{(2n-2m)}(z_l) &= \sum_{p=0}^{n-m} (-1)^{k+l+p} \binom{2n-2m}{2p} \frac{2^{2p+1} (2k+1)^{2n-2m-2p} (2p)!}{((2l+1)\pi)^{2p+1}}
\end{aligned}$$

The final expression of the residue is given by the following formula :

$$\boxed{\operatorname{res}_{z=z_l} f_{k,n}(z) = \frac{1}{(-1)^{n+k} i \pi} \sum_{m=0}^n \sum_{p=0}^{n-m} (-1)^p c_{2m,n} \frac{1}{(2n-2m)!} \binom{2n-2m}{2p} \frac{2^{2p+1} (2k+1)^{2n-2m-2p} (2p)!}{(2l+1)^{2p+1} \pi^{2p}}}$$

When the power at the denominator is even

We define the function of the complex variable $f_{k,n}(z) := \frac{\sinh(2k+1)z}{z \cosh^{2n} z}$ and we put the focus on poles of $2n$ -order $z_l = \frac{(2l+1)i\pi}{2}$ ($l \in \mathbb{Z}$) since the singularity at $z = 0$ is removable. The residue is evaluated after finding the Laurent expansion of f around z_l .

We start by setting $z := z_l + w$, since we are expanding around z_l

One has :

$$\cosh^{2n} z = \cosh^{2n}(z_l + w) = \underbrace{(\cosh z_l \cosh w + \sinh z_l \sinh w)^{2n}}_0 = \sinh^{2n} z_l \sinh^{2n} w$$

Applying the equality given by *Proposition 2* yields

$$\cosh^{2n} z = \frac{1}{4^n} \sinh^{2n} z_l \left[2 \sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^k \binom{2n}{k} \cosh(2n-2k)w + (-1)^n \binom{2n}{n} \right]$$

Since w is near of 0, the series expansion $\cosh w = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{w^{2n}}{(2n)!}$ provides the Taylor expansion

:

$$\cosh^{2n} z = \frac{1}{4^n} \sinh^{2n} z_l \left[2 \sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^k \binom{2n}{k} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{(2n-2k)^{2j}}{(2j)!} w^{2j} + (-1)^n \binom{2n}{n} \right]$$

Interesting fact : this Taylor series begins always by w^{2n} . One shows it by remarking firstly that $g(z) := \frac{\cosh^{2n} z}{(z - z_l)^{2n} \sinh^{2n} z_l}$ is analytic around z_l because the denominator cancels the singularities at the numerator with the same multiplicity. Secondly,

$$\lim_{z \rightarrow z_l} g(z) = 1$$

because the derivative of \cosh is \sinh . Which implies that the Taylor expansion of g around z_l is

$$1 + O(w)$$

It comes out that the series expansion of $\cosh^{2n} z$ around z_l is

$$\sinh^{2n} z_l w^{2n} + O(w^{2n+2})$$

Which means exactly that all coefficients of w^{2j} are 0 when $j < n$. It is formalized under following theorem :

$$\forall n \geq 2, \quad \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} (-1)^k \binom{2n}{k} (2n-2k)^{2j} = \begin{cases} (-1)^{n+1} \binom{2n}{n}, & \text{if } j = 0 \\ 0, & \text{if } j \in \llbracket 1, n-1 \rrbracket \\ \frac{4^n (2n)!}{2}, & \text{if } j = n \end{cases}$$

Since all coefficients are 0 for all $j < n$, one becomes :

$$\cosh^{2n} z = \sinh^{2n} z_l \sum_{j=n}^{\infty} \left[\frac{2}{4^n (2j)!} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} (-1)^k \binom{2n}{k} (2n-2k)^{2j} \right] w^{2j}$$

We re-index j to 0 and we take out w^{2n} . We become :

$$\cosh^{2n} z = \sinh^{2n} z_l w^{2n} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \left[\frac{2}{4^n (2j+2n)!} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} (-1)^k \binom{2n}{k} (2n-2k)^{2j+2n} \right] w^{2j}$$

We have $\cosh^{2n} z = \sinh^{2n} z_l w^{2n} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} b_{j,n} w^j$ where

$$b_{j,n} := \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } j \text{ is odd} \\ \frac{2}{4^n (j+2n)!} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} (-1)^k \binom{2n}{k} (2n-2k)^{j+2n} & \text{if } j \text{ is even} \end{cases}$$

Taking the inverse leads to an expression of the type $\frac{1}{\cosh^{2n} z} = \frac{1}{\sinh^{2n} z_l w^{2n}} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} d_{j,n} w^j$

where $\begin{cases} d_{0,n} := 1 \\ d_{j,n} := -\sum_{k=1}^j b_{k,n} d_{j-k,n} \end{cases}$ (since $b_{0,n} = 1$)

It is even possible to prove with a trivial induction that $d_{j,n} = 0$ if j is odd. Let $L(z) := \frac{\sinh(2k+1)z}{z}$. Since L is analytic at z_l , one has the Taylor expansion :

$$L(z) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{L^{(k)}(z_l)}{k!} w^k$$

The Laurent series of the target function $f_{k,n}$ around z_l is now given by :

$$\begin{aligned} f_{k,n}(z) &= \frac{1}{\cosh^{2n+1} z} \times L(z) \\ &= \frac{1}{\sinh^{2n} z_l w^{2n}} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} d_{j,n} w^j \times \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{L^{(k)}(z_l)}{k!} w^k \\ &= \frac{1}{\sinh^{2n} z_l w^{2n}} (d_{0,n} + d_{2,n} w^2 + d_{4,n} w^4 + O(w^6)) \left(L(z_l) + L'(z_l) w + \frac{L''(z_l)}{2!} w^2 + O(w^3) \right) \end{aligned}$$

To find the residue, we need the coefficient of w^{-1} in the Laurent expansion of the expression. Since the denominator contains a factor of w^{2n} , this means we're looking for the term in the numerator that contributes a power of w^{2n-1} . In other words, the residue is equal to the coefficient of w^{2n-1} in the product of the two power series in the numerator.

$$\operatorname{res}_{z=z_l} f_{k,n}(z) = \frac{1}{\sinh^{2n} z_l} \left[d_{0,n} \frac{L^{(2n-1)}(z_l)}{(2n-1)!} + d_{2,n} \frac{L^{(2n-3)}(z_l)}{(2n-3)!} + d_{4,n} \frac{L^{(2n-5)}(z_l)}{(2n-5)!} + \dots + d_{2n-2,n} L'(z_l) \right]$$

Which looks much more beautiful when the summation operator comes into game

$$\operatorname{res}_{z=z_l} f_{k,n}(z) = \frac{1}{\sinh^{2n} z_l} \sum_{m=0}^{n-1} d_{2m,n} \frac{L^{(2n-2m-1)}(z_l)}{(2n-2m-1)!}$$

The Leibniz rule for differentiation provides a closed form of $L^{(2n-2m)}(z_l)$. In fact,

$$\begin{aligned} L^{(2n-2m-1)}(z_l) &= \frac{d^{2n-2m-1}}{dz^{2n-2m-1}} \left(\frac{\sinh((2k+1)z)}{z} \right) \Big|_{z=z_l} \\ &= \frac{d^{2n-2m-1}}{dz^{2n-2m-1}} (\sinh((2k+1)z) \cdot z^{-1}) \Big|_{z=z_l} \\ &= \sum_{p=0}^{2n-2m-1} \binom{2n-2m-1}{p} \frac{d^p}{dz^p} (\sinh((2k+1)z)) \cdot \frac{d^{2n-2m-1-p}}{dz^{2n-2m-1-p}} (z^{-1}) \Big|_{z=z_l} \end{aligned}$$

We get the assistance of these properties:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d^n}{dx^n} (x^{-1}) &= (-1)^n n! x^{-(n+1)} \\ \frac{d^n}{dx^n} \sinh(ax) &= a^n \times \begin{cases} \cosh(ax) & \text{if } n \text{ is odd,} \\ \sinh(ax) & \text{if } n \text{ is even.} \end{cases} \end{aligned}$$

The expression of $L^{(2n-2m-1)}(z_l)$ becomes :

$$L^{(2n-2m-1)}(z_l) = \sum_{p=0}^{2n-2m-1} (-1)^{p+1} \binom{2n-2m-1}{p} (2k+1)^p (2n-2m-1-p)! h_p(z_l) z_l^{-(2n-2m-p)} \quad \text{where}$$

$$h_p(z_l) := \begin{cases} \cosh((2k+1)z_l) & \text{if } p \text{ is odd,} \\ \sinh((2k+1)z_l) & \text{if } p \text{ is even.} \end{cases} = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } p \text{ is odd,} \\ (-1)^{k+l} i & \text{if } p \text{ is even} \end{cases}$$

Putting it back in $L^{(2n-2m-1)}(z_l)$ by taking into account that the last even index lies by $2n-2m-2$ leads to :

$$\begin{aligned}
L^{(2n-2m-1)}(z_l) &= - \sum_{p=0}^{n-m-1} \binom{2n-2m-1}{2p} (2k+1)^{2p} (2n-2m-1-2p)! (-1)^{k+l} i z_l^{-(2n-2m-2p)} \\
&= (-1)^{k+l+1} \sum_{p=0}^{n-m-1} \binom{2n-2m-1}{2p} \frac{(2k+1)^{2p} (2n-2m-1-2p)!}{z_l^{2n-2m-2p}} i \\
&= (-1)^{k+l+1} \sum_{p=0}^{n-m-1} \binom{2n-2m-1}{2n-2m-2p-2} \frac{(2k+1)^{2n-2m-2p-2} (2p+1)!}{z_l^{2p+2}} i \\
&= (-1)^{k+l+1} \sum_{p=0}^{n-m-1} \binom{2n-2m-1}{2n-2m-2p-2} \frac{(2k+1)^{2n-2m-2p-2} (2p+1)!}{\left(\frac{(2l+1)i\pi}{2}\right)^{2p+2}} i \\
&= (-1)^{k+l+1} \sum_{p=0}^{n-m-1} \binom{2n-2m-1}{2n-2m-2p-2} \frac{2^{2p+2} (2k+1)^{2n-2m-2p-2} (2p+1)!}{i(-1)^p((2l+1)\pi)^{2p+2}} \\
L^{(2n-2m-1)}(z_l) &= \sum_{p=0}^{n-m-1} \frac{(-1)^{k+l+p+1}}{i\pi} \binom{2n-2m-1}{2n-2m-2p-2} \frac{2^{2p+2} (2k+1)^{2n-2m-2p-2} (2p+1)!}{(2l+1)^{2p+2} \pi^{2p+1}}
\end{aligned}$$

The final expression of the residue is given by the following formula :

$ \operatorname{res}_{z=z_l} f_{k,n}(z) = \frac{1}{(-1)^{n+k+l+1} i\pi} \sum_{m=0}^{n-1} \sum_{p=0}^{n-m-1} (-1)^p d_{2m,n} \frac{\binom{2n-2m-1}{2p+1}}{(2n-2m-1)!} \frac{2^{2p+2} (2k+1)^{2n-2m-2p-2} (2p+1)!}{(2l+1)^{2p+2} \pi^{2p+1}} $
--

§3. Families of polynomials

Let $f_n(z) := \frac{g(z)}{\cosh^n xz}$ a function of the complex variable so that g is analytic at $z_l = \frac{(2l+1)i\pi}{2x}$ with $x \neq 0$ of course. Let's denote by $\operatorname{Res}_{z=z_l} f_n(z)$ the residue of f_n at z_l . One has :

- $\operatorname{Res}_{z=z_l} f_1(z) = \frac{g(z_l)}{x \sinh(xz_l)}$
- $\operatorname{Res}_{z=z_l} f_2(z) = -\frac{g'(z_l)}{x^2}$
- $\operatorname{Res}_{z=z_l} f_3(z) = \frac{(-1)^n g(z_l)}{2xi} - \frac{(-1)^n g''(z_l)}{2x^3 i}$

- $\operatorname{Res}_{z=z_l} f_4(z) = \frac{g'''(z_l)}{6x^4} - \frac{2g'(z_l)}{3x^2}$
- $\operatorname{Res}_{z=z_l} f_5(z) = \frac{1}{x^5 \sinh^5(xz_l)} \left(\frac{g^{(4)}(z_l)}{24} - \frac{5g''(z_l)}{12}x^2 + \frac{3g(z_l)}{8}x^4 \right)$
- $\operatorname{Res}_{z=z_l} f_6(z) = -\frac{g^{(5)}(z_l)}{120x^6} + \frac{g'''(z_l)}{6x^4} - \frac{8g'(z_l)}{35x^2}$
- $\operatorname{Res}_{z=z_l} f_7(z) = \frac{1}{x^7 \sinh^7(xz_l)} \left(\frac{g^{(6)}(z_l)}{720} - \frac{7g^{(4)}(z_l)}{144}x^2 + \frac{259g''(z_l)}{720}x^4 - \frac{5g(z_l)}{16}x^6 \right)$
- $\operatorname{Res}_{z=z_l} f_8(z) = \frac{g^{(7)}(z_l)}{5040x^8} - \frac{g^{(5)}(z_l)}{90x^6} + \frac{7g'''(z_l)}{45x^4} - \frac{16g'(z_l)}{35x^2}$

We define two kinds of polynomials :

$$R_n(x) := (2n)! x^{2n+1} \sinh^{2n+1}(xz_0) \operatorname{Res}_{z=z_0} \frac{e^{z-z_0}}{\cosh^{2n+1}(xz)}$$

$$S_n(x) := (2n-1)! x^{2n} \sinh^{2n}(xz_0) \operatorname{Res}_{z=z_0} \frac{e^{z-z_0}}{\cosh^{2n}(xz)}$$

4 Integral Representations involving $\frac{\zeta(2n+1)}{\pi^{2n}}$

§1. Closed-form expressions for $\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(2k+1)z}{z \cosh^{2n+1} z} dz$

As consequence of *Proposition 8*, the integral

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh((2k+1)x)}{x \cosh^{2n+1}(x)} dx$$

converges if and only if $2k+1 < 2n+1$ which reads if and only if $k < n$.

The residues z_l lying *inside* the closed contour satisfy $\frac{2l+1}{2} < 2N$, which reads $l < 2N - \frac{1}{2}$ or precisely $l \leq 2N - 1$

On considering $k < n$, the final expression of $\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(2k+1)x}{x \cosh^{2n+1} x} dx$ is got by applying the Cauchy's residue theorem :

$$\begin{aligned} \oint_{C_{N,r}} f_{k,n}(z) dz &= 2i\pi \sum_{l=0}^{2N-1} \operatorname{res}_{z=z_l} f_{k,n}(z) \\ &\Downarrow \\ \oint_{C_{+\infty,+\infty}} f_{k,n}(z) dz &= 2i\pi \lim_{N \rightarrow +\infty} \sum_{l=0}^{2N-1} \operatorname{res}_{z=z_l} f_{k,n}(z) \\ &\Downarrow \\ \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh((2k+1)x)}{x \cosh^{2n+1} x} dx &= \lim_{N \rightarrow +\infty} 2i\pi \sum_{l=0}^{2N-1} \frac{1}{(-1)^{n+k} i^l \pi} \sum_{m=0}^n \sum_{p=0}^{n-m} (-1)^{k+p} c_{2k,n} \frac{1}{(2n-2m)!} \binom{2n-2m}{2p} \\ &\quad \times \left(\frac{2^{2p+1} (2k+1)^{2n-2m-2p} (2p)!}{(2l+1)^{2p+1} \pi^{2p}} \right) \\ &\Downarrow \\ \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh((2k+1)x)}{x \cosh^{2n+1} x} dx &= \sum_{l=0}^{\infty} \frac{2}{(-1)^{n+k}} \sum_{m=0}^n \sum_{p=0}^{n-m} (-1)^p c_{2m,n} \frac{1}{(2n-2m)!} \binom{2n-2m}{2p} \\ &\quad \times \frac{2^{2p+1} (2k+1)^{2n-2m-2p} (2p)!}{(2l+1)^{2p+1} \pi^{2p}}. \end{aligned}$$

↓

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh((2k+1)x)}{x \cosh^{2n+1} x} dx = \frac{2}{(-1)^{n+k}} \sum_{m=0}^n \sum_{p=0}^{n-m} (-1)^p c_{2m,n} \frac{1}{(2n-2m)!} \binom{2n-2m}{2p} \\ \times \frac{2^{2p+1} (2k+1)^{2n-2m-2p} (2p)!}{\pi^{2p}} \sum_{l=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2l+1)^{2p+1}}.$$

↓

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh((2k+1)x)}{x \cosh^{2n+1} x} dx = \frac{2}{(-1)^{n+k}} \sum_{m=0}^n \sum_{p=0}^m (-1)^p c_{2n-2m,n} \frac{1}{(2m)!} \binom{2m}{2p} \\ \times \frac{2^{2p+1} (2k+1)^{2m-2p} (2p)!}{\pi^{2p}} \left(1 - \frac{1}{2^{2p+1}}\right) \zeta(2p+1)$$

Now, this expression involves $\zeta(1)$, which is known to be ∞ . But as proven above, the integral on the left side is convergent when $k < n$. This implies that the coefficient of $\zeta(1)$ in the right side must necessarily be 0. This implies

$$\forall n \in \mathbb{N}^*, \sum_{m=0}^n c_{2m,n} \frac{1}{(2n-2m)!} (2k+1)^{2n-2m} = 0 \text{ if } k \in \llbracket 0, n-1 \rrbracket$$

Another proof :

Let

$$M_{k,n} := \sum_{m=0}^n c_{2m,n} \frac{1}{(2n-2m)!} (2k+1)^{2n-2m}, \\ y_{m,n} := c_{2m,n} \quad \text{and} \quad t_{m,k,n} := \frac{1}{(2m)!} (2k+1)^{2m}$$

Consequently,

$$M_{k,n} = \sum_{m=0}^n y_{m,n} t_{n-m,k,n}$$

We identify straightforward through this last form $M_{k,n}$ as the coefficient of x^n is the Cauchy product of the series generated by the coefficients $y_{m,n}$ and $t_{n-m,k,n}$ on the index m . On letting

$$Y_n(x) := \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} y_{m,n} x^m \quad T_{k,n}(x) := t_{m,k,n} x^m,$$

we write much more formally

$$M_{k,n} = [x^n] Y_n(x) T_{k,n}(x)$$

One has

$$Y_n(x) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} y_{m,n} x^m = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} c_{2m,n} (\sqrt{x})^{2m} = \left(\frac{\sqrt{x}}{\sinh \sqrt{x}} \right)^{2n+1}$$

$$T_{k,n}(x) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} t_{m,k,n} x^m = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2m)!} (2k+1)^{2m} \sqrt{x}^{2m} = \cosh((2k+1)\sqrt{x})$$

It follows

$$M_{k,n} = [x^n] \left(\frac{\sqrt{x}}{\sinh \sqrt{x}} \right)^{2n+1} \cosh((2k+1)\sqrt{x})$$

On using the Cauchy integral formula, one gets

$$M_{k,n} = [x^n] \left(\frac{\sqrt{x}}{\sinh \sqrt{x}} \right)^{2n+1} \cosh((2k+1)\sqrt{x})$$

$$= \frac{1}{2\pi i} \oint_{|x|=\varepsilon} \frac{\left(\frac{\sqrt{x}}{\sinh \sqrt{x}} \right)^{2n+1} \cosh((2k+1)\sqrt{x})}{x^{n+1}} dx$$

The substitution $x = z^2$ yields

$$M_{k,n} = \frac{1}{\pi i} \oint_{|z|=\sqrt{\varepsilon}} \frac{\cosh((2k+1)z)}{(\sinh z)^{2n+1}} dz$$

On replacing sinh and cosh by their standard definitions, we obtain

$$M_{k,n} = \frac{2^{2n}}{\pi i} \oint_{|z|=\sqrt{\varepsilon}} \frac{e^{(2k+1)z} + e^{-(2k+1)z}}{(e^z - e^{-z})^{2n+1}} dz = \frac{2^{2n}}{\pi i} \oint_{|z|=\sqrt{\varepsilon}} \frac{e^{2(k+n+1)z} + e^{2(n-k)z}}{(e^{2z} - 1)^{2n+1}} dz$$

Which becomes following after the substitution $z = e^{2x}$

$$M_{k,n} = \frac{2^{2n-1}}{\pi i} \oint_{|x-1|=\delta} \frac{x^{k+n} + x^{n-k-1}}{(x-1)^{2n+1}} dx$$

On applying the formula, $f^{(m)}(a) = \frac{m!}{2\pi i} \oint_{\gamma} \frac{f(z)}{(z-a)^{m+1}} dz$, $M_{k,n}$ takes the form

$$M_{k,n} = \frac{2^{2n}}{(2n)!} \left. \frac{d^{2n}}{dx^{2n}} (x^{k+n} + x^{n-k-1}) \right|_{x=1}$$

We show easily here that none of powers $n+k$ and $n-k-1$ is high enough to yield a nonzero $2n$ -th derivative when $k < n$. This means the right side vanishes when $k < n$.

This statement its turn implies that $\forall n \in \mathbb{N}^*$, the polynomial

$$P_n(x) := \sum_{m=0}^n c_{2m,n} \frac{1}{(2n-2m)!} x^{2n-2m}$$

has roots at $1, 3, 5, \dots, 2n - 1$.

But the polynomial P_n is an even function because it is a linear combination of even functions (since $x \mapsto x^{2n-2m}$ is always even). This implies that $-x$ is a root of P_n if and only if x is a root. We conclude that the polynomial P_n has roots at $\pm 1, \pm 3, \pm 5, \dots, \pm 2n - 1$. They are exactly $2n$ roots for the polynomial. And something interesting, the polynomial P_n is a polynomial of degree $2n$ too (the highest degree been reached for $m = 0$). This means that the factorization of P_n is about all these roots. We write then :

$$\begin{aligned}
P_n(x) &= s_n \prod_{k=-n}^{n-1} (x - (2k + 1)) \\
&= s_n \prod_{k=-n}^{-1} (x - (2k + 1)) \prod_{k=0}^{n-1} (x - (2k + 1)) \\
&= s_n \prod_{k=0}^{n-1} (x - (2(k - n) + 1)) \prod_{k=0}^{n-1} (x - (2k + 1)) \\
&= s_n \prod_{k=0}^{n-1} (x - (2(n - 1 - k - n) + 1)) \prod_{k=0}^{n-1} (x - (2k + 1)) \\
&= s_n \prod_{k=0}^{n-1} (x + (2k + 1)) \prod_{k=0}^{n-1} (x - (2k + 1)) \\
&= s_n \prod_{k=0}^{n-1} (x + (2k + 1)) (x - (2k + 1)) \\
&= s_n \prod_{k=0}^{n-1} (x^2 - (2k + 1)^2)
\end{aligned}$$

Basic properties of polynomials allow to conclude that the coefficient s_n matches exactly those of x^{2n} , since it is the highest degree term. The identity $c_{0,n} = 1$ allows to conclude

$$s_n = \frac{1}{(2n)!}$$

And the closed form of the polynomial

$$P_n(x) = \frac{1}{(2n)!} \prod_{k=0}^{n-1} (x^2 - (2k + 1)^2)$$

An evaluation of $P_n(2n + 1)$ is proceeded as follow :

$$P_n(2n + 1) = \frac{1}{(2n)!} \prod_{k=0}^{n-1} ((2n + 1)^2 - (2k + 1)^2)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \frac{1}{(2n)!} \prod_{k=0}^{n-1} (2n - 2k)(2n + 2k + 2) \\
&= \frac{1}{(2n)!} \prod_{k=0}^{n-1} 4(n - k)(n + k + 1) \\
&= \frac{4^n}{(2n)!} \prod_{k=0}^{n-1} (n - k)(n + k + 1) \\
&= \frac{4^n}{(2n)!} \prod_{k=0}^{n-1} (n - k) \prod_{k=0}^{n-1} (n + k + 1) \\
&= \frac{4^n}{(2n)!} \prod_{k=0}^{n-1} (k + 1) \prod_{k=n+1}^{2n} k \\
&= \frac{4^n}{(2n)!} n! \frac{\prod_{k=1}^{2n} k}{\prod_{k=1}^n k} \\
&= \frac{4^n}{(2n)!} n! \frac{(2n)!}{n!} \\
&= 4^n
\end{aligned}$$

We conclude then this beautiful property for $c_{k,n}$:

$$\forall n \in \mathbb{N}^*, \sum_{m=0}^n c_{2m,n} \frac{1}{(2n - 2m)!} (2k + 1)^{2n-2m} = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } k \in \llbracket 0, n - 1 \rrbracket \\ 4^n, & \text{if } k = n \end{cases}$$

If this sum evaluates to zero when $k < n$, it implies that at least one of the coefficients $c_{2m,n}$ is negative and at least one is positive, since each term

$$\frac{(2k + 1)^{2n-2m}}{(2n - 2m)!}$$

is strictly positive. Moreover, one can readily verify that the coefficients $c_{2m,n}$ alternate in sign, by observing that the factorized form of the polynomial P_n produces alternating signs upon expansion. As a result, we ultimately obtain the following elegant formula for the integral in question by making *Proposition 7* useful.

$$\forall n \in \mathbb{N}^*, 0 \leq k < n, \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh((2k+1)x)}{x \cosh^{2n+1}(x)} dx = \sum_{p=1}^n \alpha_{p,k,n} \cdot \frac{\zeta(2p+1)}{\pi^{2p}},$$

where

$$\alpha_{p,k,n} = (-1)^{p+n+k} 4^{p+1} \left(1 - \frac{1}{2^{2p+1}}\right) \sum_{m=p}^n c_{2n-2m,n} \frac{(2k+1)^{2m-2p}}{(2m-2p)!}.$$

with

$$\begin{cases} c_{0,n} := 1 \\ c_{j,n} := - \sum_{k=1}^j a_{k,n} c_{j-k,n} \end{cases}$$

and

$$a_{j,n} := \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } j \text{ is odd} \\ \frac{1}{4^n(j+2n+1)!} \sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^k \binom{2n+1}{k} (2n-2k+1)^{j+2n+1} & \text{if } j \text{ is even} \end{cases}$$

Some instances of the formula

- For $n = 1$, one has the Blagouchine's integral

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(x)}{x \cosh^3(x)} dx = 14 \frac{\zeta(3)}{\pi^2}$$

- For $n = 2$,

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(x)}{x \cosh^5(x)} dx = \frac{14}{3} \frac{\zeta(3)}{\pi^2} + 62 \frac{\zeta(5)}{\pi^4}.$$

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(3x)}{x \cosh^5(x)} dx = \frac{154}{3} \frac{\zeta(3)}{\pi^2} - 62 \frac{\zeta(5)}{\pi^4}.$$

- For $n = 3$,

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(x)}{x \cosh^7(x)} dx = \frac{112}{45} \frac{\zeta(3)}{\pi^2} + \frac{124}{3} \frac{\zeta(5)}{\pi^4} + 254 \frac{\zeta(7)}{\pi^6}$$

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(3x)}{x \cosh^7(x)} dx = \frac{728}{45} \frac{\zeta(3)}{\pi^2} + \frac{620}{3} \frac{\zeta(5)}{\pi^4} - 254 \frac{\zeta(7)}{\pi^6}.$$

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(5x)}{x \cosh^7(x)} dx = \frac{7672}{45} \frac{\zeta(3)}{\pi^2} - \frac{2108}{3} \frac{\zeta(5)}{\pi^4} + 254 \frac{\zeta(7)}{\pi^6}.$$

- For $n = 4$,

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(x)}{x \cosh^9(x)} dx = \frac{8 \zeta(3)}{5 \pi^2} + \frac{434 \zeta(5)}{15 \pi^4} + 254 \frac{\zeta(7)}{\pi^6} + 1022 \frac{\zeta(9)}{\pi^8}.$$

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(3x)}{x \cosh^9(x)} dx = \frac{376 \zeta(3)}{45 \pi^2} + \frac{682 \zeta(5)}{5 \pi^4} + 762 \frac{\zeta(7)}{\pi^6} - 1022 \frac{\zeta(9)}{\pi^8}.$$

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(5x)}{x \cosh^9(x)} dx = \frac{232 \zeta(3)}{5 \pi^2} + \frac{7874 \zeta(5)}{15 \pi^4} - 2794 \frac{\zeta(7)}{\pi^6} + 1022 \frac{\zeta(9)}{\pi^8}.$$

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(7x)}{x \cosh^9(x)} dx = \frac{2904 \zeta(3)}{5 \pi^2} - \frac{59954 \zeta(5)}{15 \pi^4} + 5842 \frac{\zeta(7)}{\pi^6} - 1022 \frac{\zeta(9)}{\pi^8}.$$

- For $n = 5$,

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(x)}{x \cosh^{11}(x)} dx = \frac{256 \zeta(3)}{225 \pi^2} + \frac{20336 \zeta(5)}{945 \pi^4} + \frac{3302 \zeta(7)}{15 \pi^6} + \frac{4088 \zeta(9)}{3 \pi^8} + 4094 \frac{\zeta(11)}{\pi^{10}}.$$

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(3x)}{x \cosh^{11}(x)} dx = \frac{1184 \zeta(3)}{225 \pi^2} + \frac{89032 \zeta(5)}{945 \pi^4} + \frac{11938 \zeta(7)}{15 \pi^6} + \frac{8176 \zeta(9)}{3 \pi^8} - 4094 \frac{\zeta(11)}{\pi^{10}}.$$

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(5x)}{x \cosh^{11}(x)} dx = \frac{544 \zeta(3)}{25 \pi^2} + \frac{317192 \zeta(5)}{945 \pi^4} + \frac{18542 \zeta(7)}{15 \pi^6} - \frac{32704 \zeta(9)}{3 \pi^8} + 4094 \frac{\zeta(11)}{\pi^{10}}.$$

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(7x)}{x \cosh^{11}(x)} dx = \frac{30784 \zeta(3)}{225 \pi^2} + \frac{1260832 \zeta(5)}{945 \pi^4} - \frac{216662 \zeta(7)}{15 \pi^6} + \frac{69496 \zeta(9)}{3 \pi^8} - 4094 \frac{\zeta(11)}{\pi^{10}}.$$

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(9x)}{x \cosh^{11}(x)} dx = \frac{456256 \zeta(3)}{225 \pi^2} - \frac{17947264 \zeta(5)}{945 \pi^4} + \frac{765302 \zeta(7)}{15 \pi^6} - \frac{118552 \zeta(9)}{3 \pi^8} + 4094 \frac{\zeta(11)}{\pi^{10}}.$$

- For $n = 6$,

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(x)}{x \cosh^{13}(x)} dx = \frac{256 \zeta(3)}{297 \pi^2} + \frac{237584 \zeta(5)}{14175 \pi^4} + \frac{35306 \zeta(7)}{189 \pi^6} + \frac{63364 \zeta(9)}{45 \pi^8} + \frac{20470 \zeta(11)}{3 \pi^{10}} + 16382 \frac{\zeta(13)}{\pi^{12}}$$

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(3x)}{x \cosh^{13}(x)} dx = \frac{27392 \zeta(3)}{7425 \pi^2} + \frac{140368 \zeta(5)}{2025 \pi^4} + \frac{655574 \zeta(7)}{945 \pi^6} + \frac{181916 \zeta(9)}{45 \pi^8} + \frac{28658 \zeta(11)}{3 \pi^{10}} - 16382 \frac{\zeta(13)}{\pi^{12}}.$$

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(5x)}{x \cosh^{13}(x)} dx = \frac{95\,104 \zeta(3)}{7\,425 \pi^2} + \frac{3\,139\,184 \zeta(5)}{14\,175 \pi^4} + \frac{1\,520\,698 \zeta(7)}{945 \pi^6} + \frac{63\,364 \zeta(9)}{45 \pi^8} \\ - \frac{126\,914 \zeta(11)}{3 \pi^{10}} + 16\,382 \frac{\zeta(13)}{\pi^{12}}.$$

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(7x)}{x \cosh^{13}(x)} dx = \frac{428\,672 \zeta(3)}{7\,425 \pi^2} + \frac{11\,770\,576 \zeta(5)}{14\,175 \pi^4} + \frac{975\,614 \zeta(7)}{945 \pi^6} - \frac{2\,270\,884 \zeta(9)}{45 \pi^8} \\ + \frac{274\,298 \zeta(11)}{3 \pi^{10}} - 16\,382 \frac{\zeta(13)}{\pi^{12}}.$$

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(9x)}{x \cosh^{13}(x)} dx = \frac{622\,208 \zeta(3)}{1\,485 \pi^2} + \frac{48\,969\,584 \zeta(5)}{14\,175 \pi^4} - \frac{11\,614\,150 \zeta(7)}{189 \pi^6} + \frac{8\,648\,164 \zeta(9)}{45 \pi^8} \\ - \frac{470\,810 \zeta(11)}{3 \pi^{10}} + 16\,382 \frac{\zeta(13)}{\pi^{12}}.$$

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(11x)}{x \cosh^{13}(x)} dx = \frac{10\,715\,008 \zeta(3)}{1\,485 \pi^2} - \frac{169\,506\,512 \zeta(5)}{2\,025 \pi^4} + \frac{61\,604\,398 \zeta(7)}{189 \pi^6} - \frac{22\,138\,564 \zeta(9)}{45 \pi^8} \\ + \frac{716\,450 \zeta(11)}{3 \pi^{10}} - 16\,382 \frac{\zeta(13)}{\pi^{12}}.$$

- For $n = 7$,

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(x)}{x \cosh^{15}(x)} dx = \frac{2048 \zeta(3)}{3003 \pi^2} + \frac{234\,112 \zeta(5)}{17\,325 \pi^4} + \frac{150\,368 \zeta(7)}{945 \pi^6} + \frac{181\,624 \zeta(9)}{135 \pi^8} + 8\,188 \frac{\zeta(11)}{\pi^{10}} \\ + 32\,764 \frac{\zeta(13)}{\pi^{12}} + 65\,534 \frac{\zeta(15)}{\pi^{14}}.$$

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(3x)}{x \cosh^{15}(x)} dx = \frac{74\,752 \zeta(3)}{27\,027 \pi^2} + \frac{1\,192\,384 \zeta(5)}{22\,275 \pi^4} + \frac{555\,752 \zeta(7)}{945 \pi^6} + \frac{578\,744 \zeta(9)}{135 \pi^8} \\ + \frac{57\,316 \zeta(11)}{3 \pi^{10}} + 32\,764 \frac{\zeta(13)}{\pi^{12}} - 65\,534 \frac{\zeta(15)}{\pi^{14}}.$$

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(5x)}{x \cosh^{15}(x)} dx = \frac{1\,924\,096 \zeta(3)}{225\,225 \pi^2} + \frac{1\,628\,864 \zeta(5)}{10\,395 \pi^4} + \frac{1\,360\,424 \zeta(7)}{945 \pi^6} + \frac{168\,776 \zeta(9)}{27 \pi^8} \\ - 8\,188 \frac{\zeta(11)}{\pi^{10}} - 163\,820 \frac{\zeta(13)}{\pi^{12}} + 65\,534 \frac{\zeta(15)}{\pi^{14}}.$$

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(7x)}{x \cosh^{15}(x)} dx = \frac{128\,512}{4\,095} \frac{\zeta(3)}{\pi^2} + \frac{3\,852\,928}{7\,425} \frac{\zeta(5)}{\pi^4} + \frac{2\,806\,192}{945} \frac{\zeta(7)}{\pi^6} - \frac{1\,506\,136}{135} \frac{\zeta(9)}{\pi^8}$$

$$- 171\,948 \frac{\zeta(11)}{\pi^{10}} + 360\,404 \frac{\zeta(13)}{\pi^{12}} - 65\,534 \frac{\zeta(15)}{\pi^{14}}.$$

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(9x)}{x \cosh^{15}(x)} dx = \frac{21\,571\,072}{135\,135} \frac{\zeta(3)}{\pi^2} + \frac{331\,649\,408}{155\,925} \frac{\zeta(5)}{\pi^4} - \frac{3\,070\,352}{945} \frac{\zeta(7)}{\pi^6} - \frac{25\,082\,216}{135} \frac{\zeta(9)}{\pi^8}$$

$$+ \frac{2\,153\,444}{3} \frac{\zeta(11)}{\pi^{10}} - 622\,516 \frac{\zeta(13)}{\pi^{12}} + 65\,534 \frac{\zeta(15)}{\pi^{14}}.$$

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(11x)}{x \cosh^{15}(x)} dx = \frac{59\,700\,224}{45\,045} \frac{\zeta(3)}{\pi^2} + \frac{67\,164\,352}{7\,425} \frac{\zeta(5)}{\pi^4} - \frac{228\,948\,488}{945} \frac{\zeta(7)}{\pi^6} + \frac{155\,448\,536}{135} \frac{\zeta(9)}{\pi^8}$$

$$- 1\,891\,428 \frac{\zeta(11)}{\pi^{10}} + 950\,156 \frac{\zeta(13)}{\pi^{12}} - 65\,534 \frac{\zeta(15)}{\pi^{14}}.$$

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(13x)}{x \cosh^{15}(x)} dx = \frac{1\,173\,496\,832}{45\,045} \frac{\zeta(3)}{\pi^2} - \frac{18\,453\,519\,296}{51\,975} \frac{\zeta(5)}{\pi^4} + \frac{1\,693\,055\,288}{945} \frac{\zeta(7)}{\pi^6}$$

$$- \frac{551\,477\,624}{135} \frac{\zeta(9)}{\pi^8} + 4\,020\,308 \frac{\zeta(11)}{\pi^{10}} - 1\,343\,324 \frac{\zeta(13)}{\pi^{12}} + 65\,534 \frac{\zeta(15)}{\pi^{14}}.$$

In addition, since for $k = 0$, we always have an integral for each n and more precisely with the least coefficients possible, we extract in virtue of *Proposition 6* the formula:

$$\forall n \in \mathbb{N}^*, \frac{\zeta(2n+1)}{\pi^{2n}} = \sum_{p=1}^n \chi_{p,n} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^{2p+1} x} dx$$

where

$$\chi_{p,n} = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{\alpha_{n,0,n}}, & \text{if } p = n, \\ -\frac{1}{\alpha_{n,0,n}} \sum_{k=p}^{n-1} \alpha_{k,0,n} \chi_{p,k}, & \text{if } 1 \leq p < n. \end{cases}$$

with

$$\alpha_{p,k,n} = (-1)^{p+n+k} 4^{p+1} \left(1 - \frac{1}{2^{2p+1}}\right) \sum_{m=p}^n c_{2n-2m,n} \frac{(2k+1)^{2m-2p}}{(2m-2p)!}.$$

$$\begin{cases} c_{0,n} := 1 \\ c_{j,n} := -\sum_{k=1}^j \alpha_{k,n} c_{j-k,n} \end{cases}$$

and

$$a_{j,n} := \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } j \text{ is odd} \\ \frac{1}{4^n (j+2n+1)!} \sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^k \binom{2n+1}{k} (2n-2k+1)^{j+2n+1} & \text{if } j \text{ is even} \end{cases}$$

And of course some examples

$$\frac{\zeta(3)}{\pi^2} = \frac{1}{14} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^3(x)} dx$$

$$\frac{\zeta(5)}{\pi^4} = -\frac{1}{186} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^3(x)} dx + \frac{1}{62} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^5(x)} dx$$

$$\frac{\zeta(7)}{\pi^6} = \frac{1}{5715} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^3(x)} dx - \frac{1}{381} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^5(x)} dx + \frac{1}{254} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^7(x)} dx$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\zeta(9)}{\pi^8} = & -\frac{1}{321930} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^3(x)} dx + \frac{1}{5110} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^5(x)} dx \\ & - \frac{1}{1022} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^7(x)} dx + \frac{1}{1022} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^9(x)} dx \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\zeta(11)}{\pi^{10}} = & \frac{1}{29016225} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^3(x)} dx - \frac{17}{1934415} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^5(x)} dx + \frac{7}{61410} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^7(x)} dx \\ & - \frac{2}{6141} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^9(x)} dx + \frac{1}{4094} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^{11}(x)} dx \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{\zeta(13)}{\pi^{12}} = & -\frac{1}{3\,831\,545\,025} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^3(x)} dx + \frac{31}{116\,107\,425} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^5(x)} dx \\ & -\frac{64}{7\,740\,495} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^7(x)} dx + \frac{19}{368\,595} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^9(x)} dx \\ & -\frac{5}{49\,146} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^{11}(x)} dx + \frac{1}{16\,382} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^{13}(x)} dx\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{\zeta(15)}{\pi^{14}} = & \frac{2}{1\,394\,810\,091\,675} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^3(x)} dx - \frac{2}{340\,612\,965} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^5(x)} dx \\ & + \frac{13}{30\,964\,815} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^7(x)} dx - \frac{32}{6\,192\,963} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^9(x)} dx \\ & + \frac{2}{98\,301} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^{11}(x)} dx - \frac{1}{32\,767} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^{13}(x)} dx \\ & + \frac{1}{65\,534} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^{15}(x)} dx\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{\zeta(17)}{\pi^{16}} = & -\frac{1}{167\,381\,042\,078\,250} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^3(x)} dx + \frac{5\,461}{55\,793\,680\,692\,750} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^5(x)} dx \\ & -\frac{31}{1\,946\,404\,350} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^7(x)} dx + \frac{457}{1\,238\,620\,950} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^9(x)} dx \\ & -\frac{43}{16\,514\,946} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^{11}(x)} dx + \frac{29}{3\,932\,130} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^{13}(x)} dx \\ & -\frac{7}{786\,426} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^{15}(x)} dx + \frac{1}{262\,142} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^{17}(x)} dx\end{aligned}$$

§2. The mysteries behind the integral $\int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin 4nx}{\ln(\tan x)} dx$

As stated in the introduction of a previous section, the integral $\int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin 4nx}{\ln(\tan x)} dx$ hold a strong property : linear combinations of these integrals by valuating n are integrals with a common denominator $\ln(\tan x)$. Moreover, the ratio $\frac{\zeta(2n+1)}{\pi^{2n}}$ could be expressed as such a linear combination. We note by passing that the ratio $\frac{\beta(2n)}{\pi^{2n-1}}$ could be expressed as a linear combination of integrals with common denominator $\ln(\tan x)$ too. And more interesting, the bounds of integration still being $\left[0, \frac{\pi}{4}\right]$

The study of an integral always begins with the question of the convergence. The integrand of the integral this first study is devoted to, has singularities at the bounds of the integral. We start by evaluating the limits :

$$\begin{aligned}
\lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{\sin 4nx}{\ln(\tan x)} &= \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \underbrace{\frac{\sin 4nx}{4nx}}_1 \times \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{4nx}{\ln(\tan x)} \\
&= 4n \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{x}{\ln(\sin x) - \ln(\cos x)} \\
&= 4n \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{x}{\ln(\sin x)} \\
&= 4n \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{x}{\ln x + \ln\left(\frac{\sin x}{x}\right)} \\
&= 4n \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{x}{\ln x} \\
\lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{\sin 4nx}{\ln(\tan x)} &= 0
\end{aligned}$$

On the second hand,

$$\begin{aligned}
\lim_{x \rightarrow \frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin 4nx}{\ln(\tan x)} &= \lim_{x \rightarrow \frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin 4nx}{\tan x - 1} \times \underbrace{\lim_{x \rightarrow \frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\tan x - 1}{\ln(\tan x)}}_1 \\
&= \lim_{x \rightarrow \frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin 4nx}{\tan x - 1} \\
&= \lim_{x \rightarrow \frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{4 \cos 4nx}{1 + \tan^2 x} \\
\lim_{x \rightarrow \frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin 4nx}{\ln(\tan x)} &= 2(-1)^n
\end{aligned}$$

The integrand is continuous on the interval $\left(0, \frac{\pi}{4}\right)$. An it can be extended by continuity at its bounds, so the integral $\int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin 4nx}{\ln(\tan x)} dx$ converges always for each n integer.

Let $I_n := \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin 4nx}{\ln(\tan x)} dx$. From *Proposition 1*, one has

$$\sin 4nx = \cos^{4n} x \sum_{k=0}^{2n-1} (-1)^k \binom{4n}{2k+1} \tan^{2k+1} x$$

We obtain

$$I_n = \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\cos^{4n} x \sum_{k=0}^{2n-1} (-1)^k \binom{4n}{2k+1} \tan^{2k+1} x}{\ln(\tan x)} dx$$

Performing the substitution $x = \arctan u$ and enjoying $\cos(\arctan x) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1+x^2}}$ (*Proposition 3*) yield

$$I_n = \int_0^1 \frac{\sum_{k=0}^{2n-1} (-1)^k \binom{4n}{2k+1} x^{2k+1}}{(1+x^2)^{2n+1} \ln x} dx$$

Which becomes following after the change of variable $x = e^{-u}$

$$I_n = \int_{+\infty}^0 \frac{\sum_{k=0}^{2n-1} (-1)^k \binom{4n}{2k+1} e^{-(2k+1)x}}{(1+e^{-2x})^{2n+1} \ln e^{-x}} \cdot \frac{e^{(2n+1)x}}{e^{(2n+1)x}} (-e^{-x}) dx$$

Or in compact form

$$I_n = - \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{\sum_{k=0}^{2n-1} (-1)^k \binom{4n}{2k+1} e^{(2n-2k-1)x}}{x(2 \cosh x)^{2n+1}} dx$$

The sum on the numerator can be separated into two : the first one goes from 0 to $n-1$ and the second from n to $2n-1$. Manipulating the second sum with the standard transformations announced in the introduction and enjoying the symmetry of binomial coefficients makes the last expression much more beautiful :

$$I_n = -\frac{1}{2^{2n+1}} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{2 \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} (-1)^k \binom{4n}{2k+1} \sinh(2n-2k-1)x}{x \cosh^{2n+1} x} dx$$

Since the integrand is an even function, we extend the domain of integration as follow

$$I_n = -\frac{1}{2^{2n+1}} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} (-1)^k \binom{4n}{2k+1} \sinh(2n-2k-1)x}{x \cosh^{2n+1} x} dx$$

Not forgetting that the sum is about a finite number of convergent terms, the symbols \int and \sum will be switched up. It comes out

$$I_n = -\frac{1}{2^{2n+1}} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} (-1)^k \binom{4n}{2k+1} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(2n-2k-1)x}{x \cosh^{2n+1} x} dx$$

A simple re-indexation yields an expression related to a known integral

$$I_n = \frac{(-1)^n}{2^{2n+1}} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} (-1)^k \binom{4n}{2n-2k-1} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(2k+1)x}{x \cosh^{2n+1} x} dx$$

We conclude then

$$\begin{aligned} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin(4nx)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx &= \frac{1}{4^n} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \binom{4n}{2n-2k-1} \sum_{m=0}^n \sum_{p=1}^m \left((-1)^p c_{2n-2m,n} \frac{1}{(2m)!} \binom{2m}{2p} \right) \\ &\quad \times \left(\frac{(2^{2p+1}-1)(2k+1)^{2m-2p}(2p)!}{\pi^{2p}} \zeta(2p+1) \right) \end{aligned}$$

The index p gives information on which values of ζ are involved in the closed form of the target integral. The least index of p is 1 and the most is n , since p goes from 1 to m and m goes from 0 to n . We have then this theorem :

$$\forall n \in \mathbb{N}^*, \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin 4nx}{\ln(\tan x)} dx \in \frac{\zeta(3)}{\pi^2} \mathbb{Q} + \frac{\zeta(5)}{\pi^4} \mathbb{Q} + \frac{\zeta(7)}{\pi^6} \mathbb{Q} + \dots + \frac{\zeta(2n+1)}{\pi^{2n}} \mathbb{Q}$$

Furthermore, one finds with *Proposition 7* the closed-form expression of these coefficients.

$\forall n \in \mathbb{N}^*$, $\int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin 4nx}{\ln(\tan x)} dx = \sum_{p=1}^n q_{p,n} \frac{\zeta(2p+1)}{\pi^{2p}}$ Where the coefficients $q_{p,n}$ are given by

$$q_{p,n} := \frac{1}{4^n} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \binom{4n}{2n-2k-1} \sum_{m=p}^n (-1)^p \cdot c_{2n-2m,n} \cdot \frac{(2^{2p+1}-1)(2k+1)^{2m-2p} \binom{2m}{2p} (2p)!}{(2m)!}$$

with

$$\begin{cases} c_{0,n} := 1 \\ c_{j,n} := - \sum_{k=1}^j a_{k,n} c_{j-k,n} \end{cases}$$

and

$$a_{j,n} := \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } j \text{ is odd} \\ \frac{1}{4^n(j+2n+1)!} \sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^k \binom{2n+1}{k} (2n-2k+1)^{j+2n+1} & \text{if } j \text{ is even} \end{cases}$$

On applying this last formula for some n , we deduce the following equalities :

$$\int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin 4x}{\ln(\tan x)} dx = -7 \frac{\zeta(3)}{\pi^2}$$

$$\int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin 8x}{\ln(\tan x)} dx = -\frac{14}{3} \frac{\zeta(3)}{\pi^2} + 124 \frac{\zeta(5)}{\pi^4}$$

$$\int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin 12x}{\ln(\tan x)} dx = -\frac{161}{45} \frac{\zeta(3)}{\pi^2} + \frac{496}{3} \frac{\zeta(5)}{\pi^4} - 2032 \frac{\zeta(7)}{\pi^6}$$

$$\int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin 16x}{\ln(\tan x)} dx = -\frac{44}{15} \frac{\zeta(3)}{\pi^2} + \frac{2728}{15} \frac{\zeta(5)}{\pi^4} - 4064 \frac{\zeta(7)}{\pi^6} + 32704 \frac{\zeta(9)}{\pi^8}$$

$$\int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin 20x}{\ln(\tan x)} dx = -\frac{563}{225} \frac{\zeta(3)}{\pi^2} + \frac{178064}{945} \frac{\zeta(5)}{\pi^4} - \frac{87376}{15} \frac{\zeta(7)}{\pi^6} + \frac{261632}{3} \frac{\zeta(9)}{\pi^8} - 524032 \frac{\zeta(11)}{\pi^{10}}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin 24x}{\ln(\tan x)} dx &= -\frac{3254}{1485} \frac{\zeta(3)}{\pi^2} + \frac{2697868}{14175} \frac{\zeta(5)}{\pi^4} - \frac{1381760}{189} \frac{\zeta(7)}{\pi^6} + \frac{6933248}{45} \frac{\zeta(9)}{\pi^8} - \frac{5240320}{3} \frac{\zeta(11)}{\pi^{10}} \\ &\quad + 8387584 \frac{\zeta(13)}{\pi^{12}} \end{aligned}$$

$$\int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin 28x}{\ln(\tan x)} dx = -\frac{88\,069}{45\,045} \frac{\zeta(3)}{\pi^2} + \frac{1\,409\,632}{7\,425} \frac{\zeta(5)}{\pi^4} - \frac{8\,091\,424}{945} \frac{\zeta(7)}{\pi^6} \\ + \frac{30\,685\,696}{135} \frac{\zeta(9)}{\pi^8} - 3\,668\,224 \frac{\zeta(11)}{\pi^{10}} + 33\,550\,336 \frac{\zeta(13)}{\pi^{12}} \\ - 134\,213\,632 \frac{\zeta(15)}{\pi^{14}}$$

$$\int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin 32x}{\ln(\tan x)} dx = -\frac{11\,384}{6\,435} \frac{\zeta(3)}{\pi^2} + \frac{4\,448\,479\,664}{23\,648\,625} \frac{\zeta(5)}{\pi^4} - \frac{300\,061\,376}{31\,185} \frac{\zeta(7)}{\pi^6} \\ + \frac{614\,115\,712}{2\,025} \frac{\zeta(9)}{\pi^8} - \frac{391\,975\,936}{63} \frac{\zeta(11)}{\pi^{10}} + \frac{1\,224\,587\,264}{15} \frac{\zeta(13)}{\pi^{12}} \\ - \frac{1\,878\,990\,848}{3} \frac{\zeta(15)}{\pi^{14}} + 2\,147\,467\,264 \frac{\zeta(17)}{\pi^{16}}$$

$$\int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin 36x}{\ln(\tan x)} dx = -\frac{1\,593\,269}{984\,555} \frac{\zeta(3)}{\pi^2} + \frac{39\,520\,070\,752}{212\,837\,625} \frac{\zeta(5)}{\pi^4} - \frac{1\,344\,146\,546\,144}{127\,702\,575} \frac{\zeta(7)}{\pi^6} \\ + \frac{25\,378\,565\,632}{66\,825} \frac{\zeta(9)}{\pi^8} - \frac{8\,809\,501\,952}{945} \frac{\zeta(11)}{\pi^{10}} + \frac{147\,923\,431\,424}{945} \frac{\zeta(13)}{\pi^{12}} \\ - \frac{77\,978\,120\,192}{45} \frac{\zeta(15)}{\pi^{14}} + \frac{34\,359\,476\,224}{3} \frac{\zeta(17)}{\pi^{16}} - 34\,359\,672\,832 \frac{\zeta(19)}{\pi^{18}}$$

$$\int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin 40x}{\ln(\tan x)} dx = -\frac{15\,518\,938}{10\,392\,525} \frac{\zeta(3)}{\pi^2} + \frac{13\,616\,516\,756}{74\,449\,375} \frac{\zeta(5)}{\pi^4} - \frac{17\,818\,185\,344}{1\,576\,575} \frac{\zeta(7)}{\pi^6} \\ + \frac{5\,935\,672\,860\,928}{13\,030\,875} \frac{\zeta(9)}{\pi^8} - \frac{133\,935\,242\,752}{10\,395} \frac{\zeta(11)}{\pi^{10}} + \frac{410\,010\,268\,672}{1\,575} \frac{\zeta(13)}{\pi^{12}} \\ - \frac{500\,348\,420\,096}{135} \frac{\zeta(15)}{\pi^{14}} + \frac{532\,571\,881\,472}{15} \frac{\zeta(17)}{\pi^{16}} - 206\,158\,036\,992 \frac{\zeta(19)}{\pi^{18}} \\ + 549\,755\,551\,744 \frac{\zeta(21)}{\pi^{20}}$$

Something very interesting comes out from these identities : all last coefficients are integers. It allows to conjecture that

$$q_{n,n} = \frac{(-1)^n}{4^n} (2^{2n+1} - 1) \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \binom{4n}{2n-2k-1}$$

is always an integer. To show formally why, let's start from these expressions following from the Newton's binomial formula:

$$2^{4n} = 4^{2n} = (1+1)^{4n} = \sum_{k=0}^{4n} \binom{4n}{k} \quad (L_1)$$

$$0 = (1 - 1)^{4n} = \sum_{k=0}^{4n} (-1)^k \binom{4n}{k} \quad (L_2)$$

On making $L_1 - L_2$ member by member, one has

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{k=0}^{4n} \binom{4n}{k} - \sum_{k=0}^{4n} (-1)^k \binom{4n}{k} &= 4^{2n} \Rightarrow \sum_{k=0}^{4n} (1 - (-1)^k) \binom{4n}{k} \\ &\Rightarrow 2 \sum_{k=0}^{2n-1} \binom{4n}{2k+1} = 4^{2n} \\ &\Rightarrow 2 \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \binom{4n}{2k+1} + 2 \sum_{k=n}^{2n-1} \binom{4n}{2k+1} = 4^{2n} \\ &\Rightarrow 2 \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \binom{4n}{2k+1} + 2 \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \binom{4n}{2(k+n)+1} = 4^{2n} \\ &\Rightarrow 2 \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \binom{4n}{2k+1} + 2 \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \binom{4n}{2(n-1-k+n)+1} = 4^{2n} \\ &\Rightarrow 2 \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \binom{4n}{2k+1} + 2 \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \binom{4n}{4n-2k-1} = 4^{2n} \\ &\Rightarrow 2 \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \binom{4n}{2k+1} + 2 \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \binom{4n}{2k+1} = 4^{2n} \\ &\Rightarrow 4 \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \binom{4n}{2k+1} = 4^{2n} \\ &\Rightarrow \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \binom{4n}{2k+1} = 4^{2n-1} \\ &\Rightarrow q_{n,n} = \frac{(-1)^n}{4^n} (2^{2n+1} - 1) 4^{2n-1} \\ &\Rightarrow q_{n,n} = (-1)^n (2^{2n+1} - 1) 4^{n-1} \end{aligned}$$

And this last expression is those of an integer. Another very interesting theorem coming further in conjectures becomes this :

$$\forall n \in \mathbb{N}^*, \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin 4nx}{\ln(\tan x)} dx \in \frac{\zeta(3)}{\pi^2} \mathbb{Q} + \frac{\zeta(5)}{\pi^4} \mathbb{Q} + \frac{\zeta(7)}{\pi^6} \mathbb{Q} + \dots + \frac{\zeta(2n-1)}{\pi^{2n-2}} \mathbb{Q} + (-1)^n \frac{\zeta(2n+1)}{\pi^{2n}} \mathbb{N}$$

The inverse theorem states :

$$\forall n \in \mathbb{N}^*, \frac{\zeta(2n+1)}{\pi^{2n}} \in \mathbb{Q} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin 4x}{\ln(\tan x)} dx + \mathbb{Q} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin 8x}{\ln(\tan x)} dx + \dots + \mathbb{Q} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin 4nx}{\ln(\tan x)} dx$$

The proof of the second follows immediately from *Proposition 6*

More examples :

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\zeta(3)}{\pi^2} &= -\frac{1}{7} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin 4x}{\ln(\tan x)} \\ \frac{\zeta(5)}{\pi^4} &= -\frac{1}{186} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin 4x}{\ln(\tan x)} + \frac{1}{124} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin 8x}{\ln(\tan x)} \\ \frac{\zeta(7)}{\pi^6} &= -\frac{17}{91440} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin(4x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx + \frac{1}{1524} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin(8x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx - \frac{1}{2032} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin(12x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx \\ \frac{\zeta(9)}{\pi^8} &= -\frac{31}{5\,150\,880} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin(4x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx + \frac{3}{81\,760} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin(8x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx - \frac{1}{16\,352} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin(12x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{32\,704} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin(16x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx \\ \frac{\zeta(11)}{\pi^{10}} &= -\frac{691}{3\,714\,076\,800} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin(4x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx + \frac{53}{30\,950\,640} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin(8x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx \\ &\quad - \frac{37}{7\,860\,480} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin(12x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx + \frac{1}{196\,512} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin(16x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx \\ &\quad - \frac{1}{524\,032} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin(20x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx \\ \frac{\zeta(13)}{\pi^{12}} &= -\frac{5\,461}{980\,875\,526\,400} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin(4x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx + \frac{8507}{118\,894\,003\,200} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin(8x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx \\ &\quad - \frac{1\,133}{3\,963\,133\,440} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin(12x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx + \frac{47}{94\,360\,320} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin(16x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx \\ &\quad - \frac{5}{12\,581\,376} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin(20x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx + \frac{1}{8\,387\,584} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin(24x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx \\ \frac{\zeta(15)}{\pi^{14}} &= -\frac{929\,569}{5\,713\,142\,135\,500\,800} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin(4x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx + \frac{967}{348\,787\,676\,160} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin(8x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx \\ &\quad - \frac{1\,901}{126\,831\,882\,240} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin(12x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx + \frac{59}{1\,585\,398\,528} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin(16x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx \\ &\quad - \frac{19}{402\,640\,896} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin(20x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx + \frac{1}{33\,553\,408} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin(24x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx - \frac{1}{134\,213\,632} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin(28x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\zeta(17)}{\pi^{16}} = & -\frac{3\,202\,291}{685\,592\,748\,352\,512\,000} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin(4x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx + \frac{23\,235\,713}{228\,530\,916\,117\,504\,000} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin(8x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx \\
& -\frac{39\,607}{55\,807\,305\,523\,200} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin(12x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx + \frac{11\,891}{5\,073\,391\,411\,200} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin(16x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx \\
& -\frac{283}{67\,645\,218\,816} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin(20x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx + \frac{67}{16\,106\,004\,480} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin(24x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx \\
& -\frac{7}{3\,221\,200\,896} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin(28x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx + \frac{1}{2\,147\,467\,264} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin(32x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\zeta(19)}{\pi^{18}} = & -\frac{221\,930\,581}{1\,678\,340\,651\,527\,507\,968\,000} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin(4x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx + \frac{1\,470\,649}{411\,358\,002\,825\,369\,600} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin(8x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx \\
& -\frac{34\,187\,513}{1\,096\,954\,674\,200\,985\,600} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin(12x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx + \frac{13\,151}{100\,453\,724\,743\,680} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin(16x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx \\
& -\frac{7\,487}{24\,352\,418\,119\,680} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin(20x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx + \frac{433}{1\,014\,684\,088\,320} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin(24x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx \\
& -\frac{539}{1\,546\,185\,277\,440} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin(28x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx + \frac{1}{6\,442\,438\,656} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin(32x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx - \frac{1}{34\,359\,672\,832} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin(36x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx
\end{aligned}$$

More generally, we have the following claim with help of *Proposition 6*

$$\frac{\zeta(2n+1)}{\pi^{2n}} = \sum_{p=1}^n r_{p,n} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin(4px)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx$$

where

$$r_{p,n} := \begin{cases} \frac{1}{q_{p,p}} & \text{if } n = p, \\ -\frac{1}{q_{n,n}} \sum_{k=p}^{n-1} q_{k,p} \cdot r_{p,k} & \text{if } p \in \llbracket 1, n-1 \rrbracket \end{cases}$$

with

$$q_{p,n} := \frac{1}{4^n} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \binom{4n}{2n-2k-1} \sum_{m=p}^n (-1)^p \cdot c_{2n-2m,n} \cdot \frac{(2^{2p+1}-1)(2k+1)^{2m-2p} \binom{2m}{2p} (2p)!}{(2m)!}$$

$$\begin{cases} c_{0,n} := 1 \\ c_{j,n} := -\sum_{k=1}^j a_{k,n} c_{j-k,n} \end{cases}$$

and

$$a_{j,n} := \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } j \text{ is odd} \\ \frac{1}{4^n (j+2n+1)!} \sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^k \binom{2n+1}{k} (2n-2k+1)^{j+2n+1} & \text{if } j \text{ is even} \end{cases}$$

However, with this formula, the coefficients $r_{p,n}$ are not sufficiently explicit to be useful in irrationality proofs or to provide deeper insight. In fact, they are defined recursively and depend on the coefficients $q_{p,n}$, which themselves are given by an analytic formula involving the $c_{p,n}$. These $c_{p,n}$ are again defined via a recurrence relation involving the coefficients $a_{p,n}$, which in turn are expressed as a complicated finite sum. As such, the structure of the coefficients remains too implicit for effective arithmetic analysis.

§3. *Malmsten-Blagouchine integral for* $\frac{\zeta(2n+1)}{\pi^{2n}} (n \geq 1)$

As conjectured in Section 1, we explore through the general integral $J_n := \int_0^1 \frac{\text{Li}_{-2n-1}(-x^2) \ln \ln \frac{1}{x}}{x} dx$

On recalling the definition of the polylogarithm $\text{Li}_s(z) := \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{z^k}{k^s}$ and bearing in mind that $|-x^2| < 1$ on the domain of integration, one becomes

$$J_n = \int_0^1 \frac{\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^k x^{2k}}{k^{-2n-1}} \ln \ln \frac{1}{x}}{x} dx = \int_0^1 \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} (-1)^k x^{2k-1} k^{2n+1} \ln \ln \frac{1}{x} dx$$

After switching the order of the operators (assumed as legitimate), one has

$$J_n = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} (-1)^k k^{2n+1} \int_0^1 x^{2k-1} \ln \ln \frac{1}{x} dx$$

And applying $\int_0^1 x^s \ln \left(\ln \frac{1}{x} \right) dx = -\frac{\gamma + \ln(s+1)}{s+1}$ proven in *Proposition 5* gives

$$J_n = -\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} (-1)^k k^{2n+1} \frac{\gamma + \ln(2k)}{2k} = -\frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} (-1)^k k^{2n+1} \frac{\ln(2e^\gamma) + \ln k}{k}$$

The later sum is then split in two to provide

$$J_n = -\frac{\ln(2e^\gamma)}{2} \underbrace{\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} (-1)^k \frac{1}{k^{-2n}}}_{\eta(-2n)} - \frac{1}{2} \underbrace{\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} (-1)^k \frac{\ln k}{k^{-2n}}}_{\eta'(-2n)}$$

One recognizes easily the Dirichlet η function and its derivative. Now, the η -function has zeros at negative even integers since the Riemann ζ function also has zeros at negative even integers [9][10][17]. And its derivative is

$$\eta'(s) = (1 - 2^{1-s}) \zeta'(s) + 2^{1-s} \ln 2 \cdot \zeta(s)$$

. It remains

$$J_n = -\frac{1}{2} (1 - 2^{1+2n}) \zeta'(-2n)$$

And the closed form of the derivative zeta at even negative integers [11][18]

$$\zeta'(-2n) = (-1)^n \frac{(2n)!}{2(2\pi)^{2n}} \zeta(2n+1)$$

yields

$$J_n = (-1)^n \left(1 - \frac{1}{2^{2n+1}} \right) \frac{(2n)! \zeta(2n+1)}{2 \pi^{2n}}$$

We extend as consequence the Malmsten's integral given by Blagouchine to all n :

$$\forall n \in \mathbb{N}^*, \quad \int_0^1 \frac{\text{Li}_{-2n-1}(-x^2) \ln \ln \frac{1}{x}}{x} dx = (-1)^n \left(1 - \frac{1}{2^{2n+1}} \right) \frac{(2n)! \zeta(2n+1)}{2 \pi^{2n}}$$

Of course, this derivation would be regarded as strong and complete only if the interchange between \sum and \int could be rigorously justified. A detailed and stronger proof of this Malmsten's integral is provided in §5 of this section. It is highly probable that this integral has already been addressed in the literature, as its derivation follows naturally from standard properties of L -functions. However, despite extensive research, we have not found any reference explicitly stating this identity. And follow some instances of the formula for few n ,

$$\begin{aligned}
\int_0^1 \frac{\text{Li}_{-3}(-x^2) \ln \ln \frac{1}{x}}{x} dx &= -\frac{7\zeta(3)}{8\pi^2} \quad (\text{Blagouchine's integral}) \\
\int_0^1 \frac{\text{Li}_{-5}(-x^2) \ln \ln \frac{1}{x}}{x} dx &= -\frac{93\zeta(5)}{8\pi^4} \\
\int_0^1 \frac{\text{Li}_{-7}(-x^2) \ln \ln \frac{1}{x}}{x} dx &= \frac{5715\zeta(7)}{16\pi^6} \\
\int_0^1 \frac{\text{Li}_{-9}(-x^2) \ln \ln \frac{1}{x}}{x} dx &= \frac{160\,965}{8} \cdot \frac{\zeta(9)}{\pi^8} \\
\int_0^1 \frac{\text{Li}_{-11}(-x^2) \ln \ln \frac{1}{x}}{x} dx &= -\frac{29\,016\,225}{16} \cdot \frac{\zeta(11)}{\pi^{10}} \\
\int_0^1 \frac{\text{Li}_{-13}(-x^2) \ln \ln \frac{1}{x}}{x} dx &= \frac{3\,831\,545\,025}{16} \cdot \frac{\zeta(13)}{\pi^{12}} \\
\int_0^1 \frac{\text{Li}_{-15}(-x^2) \ln \ln \frac{1}{x}}{x} dx &= -\frac{1\,394\,810\,091\,675}{32} \cdot \frac{\zeta(15)}{\pi^{14}} \\
\int_0^1 \frac{\text{Li}_{-17}(-x^2) \ln \ln \frac{1}{x}}{x} dx &= \frac{83\,690\,521\,039\,125}{8} \cdot \frac{\zeta(17)}{\pi^{16}} \\
\int_0^1 \frac{\text{Li}_{-19}(-x^2) \ln \ln \frac{1}{x}}{x} dx &= -\frac{51\,218\,891\,953\,354\,125}{16} \cdot \frac{\zeta(19)}{\pi^{18}} \\
\int_0^1 \frac{\text{Li}_{-21}(-x^2) \ln \ln \frac{1}{x}}{x} dx &= \frac{19\,463\,206\,784\,628\,481\,875}{16} \cdot \frac{\zeta(21)}{\pi^{20}} \\
\int_0^1 \frac{\text{Li}_{-23}(-x^2) \ln \ln \frac{1}{x}}{x} dx &= -\frac{17\,984\,009\,500\,580\,471\,473\,125}{32} \cdot \frac{\zeta(23)}{\pi^{22}} \\
\int_0^1 \frac{\text{Li}_{-25}(-x^2) \ln \ln \frac{1}{x}}{x} dx &= \frac{4\,963\,587\,065\,939\,489\,167\,805\,625}{16} \cdot \frac{\zeta(25)}{\pi^{24}}.
\end{aligned}$$

It is easy to show that the numerator of the fractions always ends with 5 when $n \geq 3$. In fact, the absolute value of the numerator in the general formula is $(2n)!$ multiplied by $2^{2n+1} - 1$ (always odd), which contains the factors 2 and 5, as soon as $n \geq 3$. And the denominator is a power of 2. The simplified fraction coming from such numbers at these positions would always yields a numerator ending in 5. This is true, but at least provided that the power of 2 in the prime factors decomposition of $(2n)!$ is strictly less than $2n + 2$.

Which is always true since $v_2(n!) \leq n - 1$ where $v_p(n)$ is the p -adic valuation of n . This claim is a straightforward application of the inequality :

$$v_p(n!) \leq \frac{n-1}{p-1}$$

where p is a prime number less than n [15][16].

§4. Devotion to the integral $\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\tanh^n x}{x^n} dx \quad (n \geq 2)$

The integrand under consideration is continuous on the domain of integration. In particular, near the origin, we observe that

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{\tanh(x)}{x} = 1,$$

which shows that the integrand admits a continuous extension at $x = 0$. Consequently, no singularity arises at the lower endpoint.

Furthermore, for large values of $|x|$, we have the trivial bound

$$\left| \frac{\tanh^n(x)}{x^n} \right| \leq \frac{1}{|x|^n},$$

since $|\tanh(x)| < 1$. The comparison with the classical improper integral

$$\int_1^{+\infty} \frac{dx}{x^n}$$

ensures convergence at infinity, as this integral is well known to converge whenever $n \geq 2$.

Taken together, these considerations establish the absolute convergence of the integral and justify its computation.

We perform $n - 1$ integrations by parts by considering $u'(x) = \frac{1}{x^n}$ and $v(x) = \tanh^n x$. Each time, the bound term is an expression of the form $\left[c_r \frac{1}{x^{n-r}} \frac{d^r}{dx^r} \tanh^n x \right]_{-\infty}^{+\infty}$ where c_r is some coefficient. Now, we showed with *Proposition 11* that $\left\{ \frac{d^r}{dx^r} \tanh^n x \mid r < n \right\}$ is included in $\mathbb{Z}[\tanh x]$ which is known hold finite values since $\tanh x$ goes to ± 1 as x goes to $\pm\infty$. The decay of the bound terms comes then from the inverse power function $\frac{1}{x^{n-r}}$. As consequence :

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\tanh^n x}{x^n} dx = \frac{1}{(n-1)!} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{d^{n-1}}{dx^{n-1}} (\tanh^n x) \frac{dx}{x}.$$

On using the formula $\frac{d^{n-1}}{dx^{n-1}} \tanh^n x = \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} C_{n,2k+1-n,r} \tanh^{2k+1} x$ proved in *Proposition 11*, we have the expansion

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\tanh^n x}{x^n} dx = \frac{1}{(n-1)!} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} C_{n,2k+1-n,n-1} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\tanh^{2k+1} x}{x} dx$$

We express then \tanh with \sinh and \cosh . Since the highest power of \cosh is $2n-1$, we multiply the numerator and the denominator by $\cosh^{2n-2k-2} x$

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\tanh^n x}{x^n} dx &= \frac{1}{(n-1)!} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} C_{n,2k+1-n,n-1} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\tanh^{2k+1} x}{x} dx \\ &= \frac{1}{(n-1)!} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} C_{n,2k+1-n,n-1} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh^{2k+1} x}{x \cosh^{2k+1} x} dx \\ &= \frac{1}{(n-1)!} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} C_{n,2k+1-n,n-1} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh^{2k+1} x \cosh^{2n-2k-2} x}{x \cosh^{2n-1} x} dx. \end{aligned}$$

On using the result proved in *Proposition 12* to linearize the numerator, we get

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\tanh^n x}{x^n} dx = \frac{1}{(n-1)! 2^{2n-2}} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} C_{n,2k+1-n,n-1} \sum_{p=0}^{n-1} P_{n-k-1,k,p} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh((2p+1)x)}{x \cosh^{2n-1} x} dx$$

Bearing in mind, that the integral $\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh((2p+1)x)}{x \cosh^{2n-1} x} dx$ already made object of our discussions, we conclude a general big formula

$$\forall n \in \mathbb{N} \wedge n \geq 2, \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\tanh^n x}{x^n} dx = \sum_{p=1}^{n-1} \Gamma_{p,n} \cdot \frac{\zeta(2p+1)}{\pi^{2p}},$$

where

$$\Gamma_{p,n} := \frac{1}{(n-1)! 2^{2n-2}} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} C_{n,2k+1-n,n-1} \sum_{q=0}^{n-1} P_{n-k-1,k,q} \alpha_{p,q,n-1}$$

and

$$\alpha_{p,k,n} = (-1)^{p+n+k} 4^{p+1} \left(1 - \frac{1}{2^{2p+1}}\right) \sum_{m=p}^n c_{2n-2m,n} \frac{(2k+1)^{2m-2p}}{(2m-2p)!}.$$

with

$$\begin{cases} c_{0,n} := 1 \\ c_{j,n} := - \sum_{k=1}^j a_{k,n} c_{j-k,n} \end{cases}$$

and

$$a_{j,n} := \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } j \text{ is odd} \\ \frac{1}{4^n (j+2n+1)!} \sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^k \binom{2n+1}{k} (2n-2k+1)^{j+2n+1} & \text{if } j \text{ is even} \end{cases}$$

On providing some instances :

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\tanh^2 x}{x^2} dx = 28 \frac{\zeta(3)}{\pi^2}.$$

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\tanh^3 x}{x^3} dx = -14 \frac{\zeta(3)}{\pi^2} + 372 \frac{\zeta(5)}{\pi^4}.$$

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\tanh^4 x}{x^4} dx = -\frac{992}{3} \frac{\zeta(5)}{\pi^4} + 5080 \frac{\zeta(7)}{\pi^6}.$$

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\tanh^5 x}{x^5} dx = 62 \frac{\zeta(5)}{\pi^4} - 6350 \frac{\zeta(7)}{\pi^6} + 71540 \frac{\zeta(9)}{\pi^8}.$$

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\tanh^6 x}{x^6} dx = \frac{11684}{5} \frac{\zeta(7)}{\pi^6} - 114464 \frac{\zeta(9)}{\pi^8} + 1031688 \frac{\zeta(11)}{\pi^{10}}.$$

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\tanh^7 x}{x^7} dx = -254 \frac{\zeta(7)}{\pi^6} + \frac{2\,804\,368}{45} \frac{\zeta(9)}{\pi^8} - 2\,006\,060 \frac{\zeta(11)}{\pi^{10}} + 15\,136\,968 \frac{\zeta(13)}{\pi^{12}}.$$

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\tanh^8 x}{x^8} dx = -\frac{205\,568}{15} \frac{\zeta(9)}{\pi^8} + 1\,441\,088 \frac{\zeta(11)}{\pi^{10}} - 34\,598\,784 \frac{\zeta(13)}{\pi^{12}} + 224\,912\,688 \frac{\zeta(15)}{\pi^{14}}.$$

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\tanh^9 x}{x^9} dx = & -\frac{22\,457\,041\,813\,504}{23\,648\,625} \frac{\zeta(3)}{\pi^2} + \frac{109\,951\,968\,083\,968}{5\,457\,375} \frac{\zeta(5)}{\pi^4} \\ & - \frac{57\,026\,226\,946\,048}{297\,675} \frac{\zeta(7)}{\pi^6} + \frac{44\,521\,674\,450\,886}{42\,525} \frac{\zeta(9)}{\pi^8} \\ & - \frac{1\,099\,125\,457\,004}{315} \frac{\zeta(11)}{\pi^{10}} + \frac{2\,208\,461\,400\,826}{315} \frac{\zeta(13)}{\pi^{12}} \\ & - \frac{340\,704\,403\,654}{45} \frac{\zeta(15)}{\pi^{14}} + 3\,373\,767\,540 \frac{\zeta(17)}{\pi^{16}}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\tanh^{10} x}{x^{10}} dx = & \frac{47\,859\,290\,341\,376}{1\,073\,543\,625} \frac{\zeta(3)}{\pi^2} - \frac{14\,117\,758\,224\,564\,224}{12\,314\,176\,875} \frac{\zeta(5)}{\pi^4} \\ & + \frac{4\,601\,011\,349\,525\,364\,736}{362\,036\,800\,125} \frac{\zeta(7)}{\pi^6} - \frac{2\,193\,866\,073\,571\,328}{27\,064\,125} \frac{\zeta(9)}{\pi^8} \\ & + \frac{131\,630\,231\,936\,764}{382\,725} \frac{\zeta(11)}{\pi^{10}} - \frac{2\,781\,276\,361\,890\,832}{2\,679\,075} \frac{\zeta(13)}{\pi^{12}} \\ & + \frac{40\,010\,588\,753\,044}{18\,225} \frac{\zeta(15)}{\pi^{14}} - \frac{3\,349\,537\,230\,656}{1\,215} \frac{\zeta(17)}{\pi^{16}} \\ & + \frac{3\,795\,808\,519\,928}{2\,835} \frac{\zeta(19)}{\pi^{18}}. \end{aligned}$$

We show easily from the last integral that $\Gamma_{n,n}$ is **not always** an integer. The two first integrals can be found on [27] while the others seem to be new. With help of *Proposition 7*, we express each zeta value as a linear combination of the integrals as follow.

$$\forall n \in \mathbb{N}^*, \frac{\zeta(2n+1)}{\pi^{2n}} = \sum_{p=1}^n \Phi_{p,n} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\tanh^{p+1} x}{x^{p+1}} dx,$$

where

$$\Phi_{p,n} := \begin{cases} \frac{1}{\Gamma_{n,n+1}} & \text{if } n = p, \\ -\frac{1}{\Gamma_{n,n+1}} \sum_{k=p}^{n-1} \Phi_{p,k} \cdot \Gamma_{k,n+1} & \text{if } p \in \llbracket 1, n-1 \rrbracket \end{cases}$$

$$\Gamma_{p,n} := \frac{1}{(n-1)! 2^{2n-2}} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} C_{n,2k+1-n,n-1} \sum_{q=0}^{n-1} P_{n-k-1,k,q} \alpha_{p,q,n-1}$$

and

$$\alpha_{p,k,n} = (-1)^{p+n+k} 4^{p+1} \left(1 - \frac{1}{2^{2p+1}}\right) \sum_{m=p}^n c_{2n-2m,n} \frac{(2k+1)^{2m-2p}}{(2m-2p)!}.$$

with

$$\begin{cases} c_{0,n} := 1 \\ c_{j,n} := -\sum_{k=1}^j a_{k,n} c_{j-k,n} \end{cases}$$

and

$$a_{j,n} := \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } j \text{ is odd} \\ \frac{1}{4^n (j+2n+1)!} \sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^k \binom{2n+1}{k} (2n-2k+1)^{j+2n+1} & \text{if } j \text{ is even} \end{cases}$$

Some examples

$$\frac{\zeta(3)}{\pi^2} = \frac{1}{28} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\tanh^2 x}{x^2} dx$$

$$\frac{\zeta(5)}{\pi^4} = \frac{1}{744} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\tanh^2 x}{x^2} dx + \frac{1}{372} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\tanh^3 x}{x^3} dx$$

$$\frac{\zeta(7)}{\pi^6} = \frac{1}{11430} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\tanh^2 x}{x^2} dx + \frac{1}{5715} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\tanh^3 x}{x^3} dx + \frac{1}{5080} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\tanh^4 x}{x^4} dx$$

$$\frac{\zeta(9)}{\pi^8} = \frac{17}{2575440} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\tanh^2 x}{x^2} dx + \frac{17}{1287720} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\tanh^3 x}{x^3} dx$$

$$+\frac{1}{57\,232} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\tanh^4 x}{x^4} dx + \frac{1}{71\,540} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\tanh^5 x}{x^5} dx$$

$$\frac{\zeta(11)}{\pi^{10}} = \frac{31}{58\,032\,450} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\tanh^2 x}{x^2} dx + \frac{31}{29\,016\,225} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\tanh^3 x}{x^3} dx + \frac{11}{7\,369\,200} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\tanh^4 x}{x^4} dx$$

$$+\frac{1}{644\,805} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\tanh^5 x}{x^5} dx + \frac{1}{1\,031\,688} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\tanh^6 x}{x^6} dx$$

$$\frac{\zeta(13)}{\pi^{12}} = \frac{691}{15\,326\,180\,100} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\tanh^2 x}{x^2} dx + \frac{691}{7\,663\,090\,050} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\tanh^3 x}{x^3} dx$$

$$+\frac{1}{7\,740\,495} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\tanh^4 x}{x^4} dx + \frac{1}{6\,757\,575} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\tanh^5 x}{x^5} dx$$

$$+\frac{5}{38\,923\,632} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\tanh^6 x}{x^6} dx + \frac{1}{15\,136\,968} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\tanh^7 x}{x^7} dx.$$

$$\frac{\zeta(15)}{\pi^{14}} = \frac{5\,461}{1\,394\,810\,091\,675} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\tanh^2 x}{x^2} dx + \frac{10\,922}{1\,394\,810\,091\,675} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\tanh^3 x}{x^3} dx$$

$$+\frac{424}{30\,995\,779\,815} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\tanh^5 x}{x^5} dx + \frac{641}{56\,355\,963\,300} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\tanh^4 x}{x^4} dx$$

$$+\frac{4}{295\,197\,903} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\tanh^6 x}{x^6} dx + \frac{1}{98\,399\,301} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\tanh^7 x}{x^7} dx$$

$$+\frac{1}{224\,912\,688} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\tanh^8 x}{x^8} dx$$

§5. The general integral $\int_0^{+\infty} \frac{\tanh^m x}{x^n} dx \quad (m, n \geq 2)$

At infinity, since

$$|\tanh(x)| < 1,$$

the integrand satisfies

$$\frac{\tanh^m(x)}{x^n} \leq \frac{1}{x^n},$$

and thus behaves like

$$\int_1^{+\infty} x^{-n} dx,$$

which converges whenever

$$n > 1.$$

Near the origin, we may write

$$\frac{\tanh^m(x)}{x^n} = \left(\frac{\tanh(x)}{x} \right)^m x^{-(n-m)};$$

since

$$\frac{\tanh(x)}{x} \rightarrow 1 \quad \text{as } x \rightarrow 0,$$

the integrand is asymptotic to

$$x^{-(n-m)},$$

and the comparison with

$$\int_0^1 x^{-(n-m)} dx$$

shows that convergence at 0 holds precisely when

$$n \leq m.$$

Combining both conditions, we conclude that

$$\int_0^{+\infty} \frac{\tanh^m}{x^n} dx \quad \text{converges if and only if } n > 1 \text{ and } n \leq m.$$

Under the assumptions $n > 1$ and $n \leq m$, after performing $n - 1$ integrations by parts (with vanishing boundary terms) one obtains

$$\int_0^{+\infty} \frac{\tanh^m(x)}{x^n} dx = \frac{1}{(n-1)!} \int_0^{+\infty} \left(\frac{d}{dx} \right)^{n-1} [\tanh^m(x)] \frac{dx}{x}.$$

On applying the formula provided by *Proposition 11*, we get

$$\int_0^{+\infty} \frac{\tanh^m(x)}{x^n} dx = \frac{1}{(n-1)!} \sum_{\bar{k}^2 = -(n-1)}^{n-1} C_{m,k,n-1} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{\tanh^{m+k}(x)}{x} dx.$$

On expanding \tanh by its definition, the integral takes the form

$$\int_0^{+\infty} \frac{\tanh^m(x)}{x^n} dx = \frac{1}{(n-1)!} \sum_{\bar{k}^2 = -n+1}^{n-1} C_{m,k,n-1} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh^{m+k} x}{x \cosh^{m+k} x} dx.$$

On making the sum beginning at 1, we have

$$\int_0^{+\infty} \frac{\tanh^m x}{x^n} dx = \frac{1}{(n-1)!} \sum_{\bar{k}^2 = 1}^{2n-1} C_{m,k-n,n-1} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh^{m+k-n} x}{x \cosh^{m+k-n} x} dx.$$

Now, bearing in mind, that the step of the summation operator is 2, we deduce that even indexes k do not infer. As consequence

$$\int_0^{+\infty} \frac{\tanh^m x}{x^n} dx = \frac{1}{(n-1)!} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} C_{m, 2k+1-n, n-1} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh^{m+2k+1-n} x}{x \cosh^{m+2k+1-n} x} dx.$$

The deeper study is relied on the linearization of $\sinh^{m+2k+1-n} x \cosh^{2(n-k-1)} x$ which is separated into 2 cases :

- $m + n$ is odd
- $m + n$ is even

a. $m + n$ is odd

If $m + n$ is odd, $m - n$ is odd, which implies $m + 2k + 1 - n$ is even. It follows

$$\int_0^{+\infty} \frac{\tanh^m x}{x^n} dx = \frac{1}{(n-1)!} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} C_{m, 2k+1-n, n-1} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{(\sinh^2 x)^{\frac{m+2k+1-n}{2}}}{x \cosh^{m+2k+1-n} x} dx.$$

Which reads

$$\int_0^{+\infty} \frac{\tanh^m x}{x^n} dx = \frac{1}{(n-1)!} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} C_{m, 2k+1-n, n-1} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{(\cosh^2 x - 1)^{\frac{m+2k+1-n}{2}}}{x \cosh^{m+2k+1-n} x} dx.$$

On expanding with the Newton's binomial formula and swapping the big operators, we obtain

$$\int_0^{+\infty} \frac{\tanh^m x}{x^n} dx = \frac{1}{(n-1)!} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} C_{m, 2k+1-n, n-1} \sum_{j=0}^{\frac{m+2k+1-n}{2}} (-1)^j \binom{\frac{m+2k+1-n}{2}}{j} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{\cosh^{m+2k+1-n-2j} x}{x \cosh^{m+2k+1-n} x} dx.$$

On simplifying

$$\int_0^{+\infty} \frac{\tanh^m x}{x^n} dx = \frac{1}{(n-1)!} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} C_{m, 2k+1-n, n-1} \sum_{j=0}^{\frac{m+2k+1-n}{2}} (-1)^j \binom{\frac{m+2k+1-n}{2}}{j} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{1}{x \cosh^{2j} x} dx.$$

The last integral diverges. But the left hand-side integral is convergent. Its evaluation uses other tricks and does not yield a form interesting us in our study. For instance

$$\begin{aligned} \int_0^{\infty} \frac{\tanh^3 x}{x^2} dx &= 8 \eta'(-3) + 4 \eta'(-1) \\ &= -120 \zeta'(-3) - 12 \zeta'(-1) - \frac{4}{15} \ln 2. \end{aligned}$$

b. $m + n$ is even

$$\int_0^{+\infty} \frac{\tanh^m x}{x^n} dx = \frac{1}{(n-1)!} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} C_{m, 2k+1-n, n-1} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh^{m+2k+1-n} x \cosh^{2(n-k-1)} x}{x \cosh^{m+n-1} x} dx.$$

Now, *Proposition 12* ensures that the linearization of the numerator yields a \mathbb{Q} -linear combination of $\sinh((2r+1)x)$. Additionally, we already showed that $\int_0^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(2r+1)x}{x \cosh^{2s+1} x} dx$ yields a \mathbb{Q} -linear combination of $\frac{\zeta(2n+1)}{\pi^{2n}}$. As consequence, $\int_0^{+\infty} \frac{\tanh^m x}{x^n} dx$ yields a \mathbb{Q} -linear combination of $\frac{\zeta(2n+1)}{\pi^{2n}}$ if $m+n$ is even.

On linearizing $\sinh^{m+2k+1-n} x \cosh^{2(n-k-1)} x$ with *Proposition 12* and using the formula of $\int_0^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(2r+1)x}{x \cosh^{2s+1} x} dx$, we arrive at this conclusion :

$$\boxed{\int_0^{+\infty} \frac{\tanh^m x}{x^n} dx = \sum_{p=1}^S \left[\frac{2^{-(m+n-1)}}{(n-1)!} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} C_{m, 2k+1-n, n-1} \sum_{r=0}^S P_{n-k-1, \frac{m+2k-n}{2}, r} \alpha_{p, r, S} \right] \frac{\zeta(2p+1)}{\pi^{2p}}.}$$

$$S := \frac{m+n-2}{2}.$$

The cases $m = n$ are in the previous subsection/paragraph. We give some examples for $m > n > 1$

$$\int_0^{\infty} \frac{\tanh^6 x}{x^2} dx = \frac{322}{15} \frac{\zeta(3)}{\pi^2} - 248 \frac{\zeta(5)}{\pi^4} + 762 \frac{\zeta(7)}{\pi^6}$$

$$\int_0^{\infty} \frac{\tanh^5 x}{x^3} dx = -7 \frac{\zeta(3)}{\pi^2} + 310 \frac{\zeta(5)}{\pi^4} - 1905 \frac{\zeta(7)}{\pi^6}$$

$$\int_0^{\infty} \frac{\tanh^4 x}{x^2} dx = \frac{56}{3} \frac{\zeta(3)}{\pi^2} - 124 \frac{\zeta(5)}{\pi^4}$$

$$\int_0^{\infty} \frac{\tanh^7 x}{x^5} dx = 31 \frac{\zeta(5)}{\pi^4} - \frac{12446}{3} \frac{\zeta(7)}{\pi^6} + \frac{250390}{3} \frac{\zeta(9)}{\pi^8} - 429870 \frac{\zeta(11)}{\pi^{10}}$$

$$\int_0^{\infty} \frac{\tanh^8 x}{x^2} dx = \frac{352}{15} \frac{\zeta(3)}{\pi^2} - \frac{5456}{15} \frac{\zeta(5)}{\pi^4} + 2032 \frac{\zeta(7)}{\pi^6} - 4088 \frac{\zeta(9)}{\pi^8}$$

$$\int_0^{\infty} \frac{\tanh^9 x}{x^5} dx = 31 \frac{\zeta(5)}{\pi^4} - \frac{103886}{21} \frac{\zeta(7)}{\pi^6} + 135926 \frac{\zeta(9)}{\pi^8} - 1289610 \frac{\zeta(11)}{\pi^{10}} + 4054545 \frac{\zeta(13)}{\pi^{12}}$$

$$\int_0^{\infty} \frac{\tanh^{10} x}{x^2} dx = \frac{1126}{45} \frac{\zeta(3)}{\pi^2} - \frac{89032}{189} \frac{\zeta(5)}{\pi^4} + \frac{10922}{3} \frac{\zeta(7)}{\pi^6} - \frac{40880}{3} \frac{\zeta(9)}{\pi^8} + 20470 \frac{\zeta(11)}{\pi^{10}}$$

$$\int_0^{\infty} \frac{\tanh^{12} x}{x^2} dx = \frac{13016}{495} \frac{\zeta(3)}{\pi^2} - \frac{2697868}{4725} \frac{\zeta(5)}{\pi^4} + \frac{345440}{63} \frac{\zeta(7)}{\pi^6} - \frac{433328}{15} \frac{\zeta(9)}{\pi^8} + 81880 \frac{\zeta(11)}{\pi^{10}} - 98292 \frac{\zeta(13)}{\pi^{12}}$$

$$\int_0^{\infty} \frac{\tanh^{10} x}{x^8} dx = -\frac{328792}{45} \frac{\zeta(9)}{\pi^8} + \frac{58789840}{63} \frac{\zeta(11)}{\pi^{10}} - 30994744 \frac{\zeta(13)}{\pi^{12}} + 374854480 \frac{\zeta(15)}{\pi^{14}} - 1499452240 \frac{\zeta(17)}{\pi^{16}}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{\tanh^{13} x}{x^{11}} dx = & -\frac{445314912386809856}{20417726203875} \frac{\zeta(3)}{\pi^2} + \frac{141012265351327514624}{696058847859375} \frac{\zeta(5)}{\pi^4} \\ & - \frac{18763097540172709888}{11835818465625} \frac{\zeta(7)}{\pi^6} + \frac{1927817128849702912}{184712653125} \frac{\zeta(9)}{\pi^8} \\ & - \frac{129300175189495349}{2210236875} \frac{\zeta(11)}{\pi^{10}} + \frac{200055581496958774}{736745625} \frac{\zeta(13)}{\pi^{12}} \\ & - \frac{1344979041484798}{1366875} \frac{\zeta(15)}{\pi^{14}} + \frac{1694642468562304}{637875} \frac{\zeta(17)}{\pi^{16}} \\ & - \frac{357754953003214}{70875} \frac{\zeta(19)}{\pi^{18}} + \frac{12221511757588}{2025} \frac{\zeta(21)}{\pi^{20}} \\ & - \frac{2335673401438}{675} \frac{\zeta(23)}{\pi^{22}}. \end{aligned}$$

The cases $(m = 11, n = 11)$, $(m = 10, n = 10)$, $(m = 13, n = 9)$, $(m = 20, n = 8)$, $(m = 35, n = 7)$, $(m = 72, n = 6)$, $(m = 215, n = 5)$ are few examples which show that the last coefficients appearing in the formula are **not always integers in general**. Nevertheless, the last coefficients -those of $\frac{\zeta(2p+1)}{\pi^{2p}}$ when $p = S$, are **always integers** when $n = 2, 3, 4$.

Furthermore these integrals highlight another pattern : the pattern $\int_0^{\infty} \frac{\tanh^{2n} x}{x^2} dx$. In virtue of the last general formula, we exhibit this additional formula :

$$\int_0^{+\infty} \frac{\tanh^{2n} x}{x^2} dx = \sum_{p=1}^n \left[\frac{1}{2^{2n+1}} \sum_{k=0}^1 C_{2n, 2k-1, 1} \sum_{r=0}^n P_{1-k, n+k-1, r} \alpha_{p, r, n} \right] \frac{\zeta(2p+1)}{\pi^{2p}}.$$

Which reads

$$\int_0^{+\infty} \frac{\tanh^{2n} x}{x^2} dx = \sum_{p=1}^n \left[\frac{1}{2^{2n+1}} \sum_{r=0}^n \left(C_{2n,-1,1} P_{1,n-1,r} + C_{2n,1,1} P_{0,n,r} \right) \alpha_{p,r,n} \right] \frac{\zeta(2p+1)}{\pi^{2p}}.$$

This means, we have the form

$$\int_0^{+\infty} \frac{\tanh^{2n} x}{x^2} dx = \sum_{p=1}^n K_{p,n} \frac{\zeta(2p+1)}{\pi^{2p}}$$

where $K_{p,n}$ are rational coefficients. As consequence and in virtue of *Proposition 6*, for a fix $n \in \mathbb{N}^*$, we can find some rational coefficients $H_{p,n}$ such that holds

$$\frac{\zeta(2n+1)}{\pi^{2n}} = \sum_{p=1}^n H_{p,n} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{\tanh^{2p} x}{x^2} dx$$

Examples :

$$\frac{\zeta(3)}{\pi^2} = \frac{1}{14} \int_0^{\infty} \frac{\tanh^2 x}{x^2} dx.$$

$$\frac{\zeta(5)}{\pi^4} = \frac{1}{93} \int_0^{\infty} \frac{\tanh^2 x}{x^2} dx - \frac{1}{124} \int_0^{\infty} \frac{\tanh^4 x}{x^2} dx.$$

$$\frac{\zeta(7)}{\pi^6} = \frac{17}{22\,860} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\tanh^2 x}{x^2} dx - \frac{1}{381} \int_0^{\infty} \frac{\tanh^4 x}{x^2} dx + \frac{1}{762} \int_0^{\infty} \frac{\tanh^6 x}{x^2} dx$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\zeta(9)}{\pi^8} &= \frac{31}{160\,965} \int_0^{\infty} \frac{\tanh^2 x}{x^2} dx - \frac{3}{5\,110} \int_0^{\infty} \frac{\tanh^4 x}{x^2} dx \\ &+ \frac{1}{1\,533} \int_0^{\infty} \frac{\tanh^6 x}{x^2} dx - \frac{1}{4\,088} \int_0^{\infty} \frac{\tanh^8 x}{x^2} dx. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\zeta(11)}{\pi^{10}} &= \frac{691}{29\,016\,225} \int_0^{\infty} \frac{\tanh^2 x}{x^2} dx - \frac{212}{1\,934\,415} \int_0^{\infty} \frac{\tanh^4 x}{x^2} dx \\ &+ \frac{37}{184\,230} \int_0^{\infty} \frac{\tanh^6 x}{x^2} dx - \frac{1}{6\,141} \int_0^{\infty} \frac{\tanh^8 x}{x^2} dx + \frac{1}{20\,470} \int_0^{\infty} \frac{\tanh^{10} x}{x^2} dx. \end{aligned}$$

We note in passing that the formula we derived for $\int_0^{\infty} \frac{\tanh^m x}{x^n} dx$ can give an extension to the case $m < n$. Numerically and normally, the integral diverges without more argumentation when $m < n$. But by applying the last formula, we can write these equalities.

We mark them with (*) to indicate that the values are only provided through extension or regularization

$$\int_0^\infty \frac{\tanh^2 x}{x^7} dx = -\frac{64\,421}{8\,100} \frac{\zeta(3)}{\pi^2} - \frac{281\,387}{8\,640} \frac{\zeta(5)}{\pi^4} - \frac{2\,562\,479}{5\,760} \frac{\zeta(7)}{\pi^6} \quad (*)$$

$$\int_0^\infty \frac{\tanh^3 x}{x^5} dx = 31 \frac{\zeta(5)}{\pi^4} - 1\,905 \frac{\zeta(7)}{\pi^6} \quad (*)$$

$$\int_0^\infty \frac{\tanh^4 x}{x^8} dx = -\frac{16\,352}{3} \frac{\zeta(9)}{\pi^8} + 245\,640 \frac{\zeta(11)}{\pi^{10}} \quad (*)$$

§6. The general integral $\int_0^1 \frac{x^{2n-1}}{\operatorname{arctanh} x} dx \quad (n \geq 1)$

Around $x = 0$, one has

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{x^{2n-1}}{\operatorname{arctanh} x} &= \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} x^{2n-2} \frac{x}{\operatorname{arctanh} x} \\ &= \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} x^{2n-2} \times \underbrace{\lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{x}{\operatorname{arctanh} x}}_1 \\ &= \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} x^{2n-2} = \begin{cases} 1, & n = 1, \\ 0, & n \geq 2. \end{cases} \end{aligned}$$

On the second hand,

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow 1} \frac{x^{2n-1}}{\operatorname{arctanh} x} = \lim_{x \rightarrow 1} \frac{1}{\operatorname{arctanh} x} = 0$$

The singularities at bounds are all removable and the integrand is continuous on the domain of integration $[0, 1]$. We justify as consequence the convergence of the integral.

We evaluate it then by performing first of all $x = \tanh u$ to get this representation

$$\int_0^1 \frac{x^{2n-1}}{\operatorname{arctanh} x} dx = \int_0^\infty \frac{\sinh^{2n-1} x}{x \cosh^{2n+1} x} dx.$$

Bearing in mind this formula, a result of *Proposition 2*,

$$\sinh^{2m+1} z = \frac{1}{4^m} \sum_{k=0}^m (-1)^k \binom{2m+1}{k} \sinh((2m+1-2k)z).$$

we get

$$\int_0^1 \frac{x^{2n-1}}{\operatorname{arctanh} x} dx = \int_0^\infty \frac{1}{x \cosh^{2n+1} x} \left(\frac{1}{4^{n-1}} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} (-1)^k \binom{2n-1}{k} \sinh((2n-1-2k)x) \right) dx.$$

Now we can swap the integration and summation operators since the sum is about a finite number of convergent terms. Hence

$$\int_0^1 \frac{x^{2n-1}}{\operatorname{arctanh} x} dx = \frac{1}{4^{n-1}} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} (-1)^k \binom{2n-1}{k} \int_0^\infty \frac{\sinh((2n-1-2k)x)}{x \cosh^{2n+1} x} dx.$$

Now, the integral $\int_0^\infty \frac{\sinh((2n-1-2k)x)}{x \cosh^{2n+1} x} dx$ is quite known from the first Paragraph. We have then

$$\int_0^1 \frac{x^{2n-1}}{\operatorname{arctanh} x} dx = \frac{1}{2 \cdot 4^{n-1}} \sum_{p=1}^n \left(\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} (-1)^k \binom{2n-1}{k} \alpha_{p, n-1-k, n} \right) \frac{\zeta(2p+1)}{\pi^{2p}}.$$

We conclude the whole formula

$$\int_0^1 \frac{x^{2n-1}}{\operatorname{arctanh} x} dx = \sum_{p=1}^n w_{p,n} \frac{\zeta(2p+1)}{\pi^{2p}}$$

with

$$w_{p,n} := (-1)^{p-1} 2^{2p-2n+3} \left(1 - \frac{1}{2^{2p+1}} \right) \sum_{m=p}^n \frac{c_{2n-2m,n}}{(2m-2p)!} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \binom{2n-1}{k} (2n-1-2k)^{2m-2p}$$

where

$$\begin{cases} c_{0,n} := 1 \\ c_{j,n} := - \sum_{k=1}^j a_{k,n} c_{j-k,n} \end{cases}$$

and

$$a_{j,n} := \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } j \text{ is odd} \\ \frac{1}{4^n (j+2n+1)!} \sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^k \binom{2n+1}{k} (2n-2k+1)^{j+2n+1} & \text{if } j \text{ is even} \end{cases}$$

Examples

$$\int_0^1 \frac{x}{\operatorname{arctanh} x} dx = 7 \frac{\zeta(3)}{\pi^2}$$

$$\int_0^1 \frac{x^3}{\operatorname{arctanh} x} dx = \frac{14}{3} \frac{\zeta(3)}{\pi^2} - 31 \frac{\zeta(5)}{\pi^4}.$$

$$\int_0^1 \frac{x^5}{\operatorname{arctanh} x} dx = \frac{161}{45} \frac{\zeta(3)}{\pi^2} - \frac{124}{3} \frac{\zeta(5)}{\pi^4} + 127 \frac{\zeta(7)}{\pi^6}.$$

$$\int_0^1 \frac{x^7}{\operatorname{arctanh} x} dx = \frac{44}{15} \frac{\zeta(3)}{\pi^2} - \frac{682}{15} \frac{\zeta(5)}{\pi^4} + 254 \frac{\zeta(7)}{\pi^6} - 511 \frac{\zeta(9)}{\pi^8}.$$

$$\int_0^1 \frac{x^9}{\operatorname{arctanh} x} dx = \frac{563}{225} \frac{\zeta(3)}{\pi^2} - \frac{44\,516}{945} \frac{\zeta(5)}{\pi^4} + \frac{5\,461}{15} \frac{\zeta(7)}{\pi^6} - \frac{4\,088}{3} \frac{\zeta(9)}{\pi^8} + 2\,047 \frac{\zeta(11)}{\pi^{10}}.$$

$$\begin{aligned} \int_0^1 \frac{x^{11}}{\operatorname{arctanh} x} dx &= \frac{3\,254}{1\,485} \frac{\zeta(3)}{\pi^2} - \frac{674\,467}{14\,175} \frac{\zeta(5)}{\pi^4} + \frac{86\,360}{189} \frac{\zeta(7)}{\pi^6} - \frac{108\,332}{45} \frac{\zeta(9)}{\pi^8} + \frac{20\,470}{3} \frac{\zeta(11)}{\pi^{10}} \\ &\quad - 8\,191 \frac{\zeta(13)}{\pi^{12}} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \int_0^1 \frac{x^{13}}{\operatorname{arctanh} x} dx &= \frac{88\,069}{45\,045} \frac{\zeta(3)}{\pi^2} - \frac{352\,408}{7\,425} \frac{\zeta(5)}{\pi^4} + \frac{505\,714}{945} \frac{\zeta(7)}{\pi^6} - \frac{479\,464}{135} \frac{\zeta(9)}{\pi^8} \\ &\quad + 14\,329 \frac{\zeta(11)}{\pi^{10}} - 32\,764 \frac{\zeta(13)}{\pi^{12}} + 32\,767 \frac{\zeta(15)}{\pi^{14}} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \int_0^1 \frac{x^{15}}{\operatorname{arctanh} x} dx &= \frac{11\,384}{6\,435} \frac{\zeta(3)}{\pi^2} - \frac{1\,112\,119\,916}{23\,648\,625} \frac{\zeta(5)}{\pi^4} + \frac{18\,753\,836}{31\,185} \frac{\zeta(7)}{\pi^6} - \frac{9\,595\,558}{2\,025} \frac{\zeta(9)}{\pi^8} \\ &\quad + \frac{1\,531\,156}{63} \frac{\zeta(11)}{\pi^{10}} - \frac{1\,195\,886}{15} \frac{\zeta(13)}{\pi^{12}} + \frac{458\,738}{3} \frac{\zeta(15)}{\pi^{14}} - 131\,071 \frac{\zeta(17)}{\pi^{16}} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \int_0^1 \frac{x^{17}}{\operatorname{arctanh} x} dx &= \frac{1\,593\,269}{984\,555} \frac{\zeta(3)}{\pi^2} - \frac{9\,880\,017\,688}{212\,837\,625} \frac{\zeta(5)}{\pi^4} + \frac{84\,009\,159\,134}{127\,702\,575} \frac{\zeta(7)}{\pi^6} \\ &\quad - \frac{396\,540\,088}{66\,825} \frac{\zeta(9)}{\pi^8} + \frac{34\,412\,117}{945} \frac{\zeta(11)}{\pi^{10}} - \frac{144\,456\,476}{945} \frac{\zeta(13)}{\pi^{12}} \\ &\quad + \frac{19\,037\,627}{45} \frac{\zeta(15)}{\pi^{14}} - \frac{2\,097\,136}{3} \frac{\zeta(17)}{\pi^{16}} + 524\,287 \frac{\zeta(19)}{\pi^{18}} \end{aligned}$$

We show and prove easily that

$$\boxed{w_{n,n} = (-1)^{n-1} (2^{2n+1} - 1)}$$

. And as usual, we derive the "inverse" formula

$$\frac{\zeta(2n+1)}{\pi^{2n}} = \sum_{p=1}^n s_{p,n} \int_0^1 \frac{x^{2p-1}}{\operatorname{arctanh} x} dx$$

where

$$s_{p,n} := \begin{cases} \frac{1}{w_{p,p}} & \text{if } n = p, \\ -\frac{1}{w_{n,n}} \sum_{k=p}^{n-1} w_{k,n} \cdot s_{p,k} & \text{if } p \in \llbracket 1, n-1 \rrbracket \end{cases}$$

with

$$w_{p,n} := (-1)^{p-1} 2^{2p-2n+3} \left(1 - \frac{1}{2^{2p+1}}\right) \sum_{m=p}^n \frac{c_{2n-2m,n}}{(2m-2p)!} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \binom{2n-1}{k} (2n-1-2k)^{2m-2p}$$

$$\begin{cases} c_{0,n} := 1 \\ c_{j,n} := -\sum_{k=1}^j a_{k,n} c_{j-k,n} \end{cases}$$

and

$$a_{j,n} := \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } j \text{ is odd} \\ \frac{1}{4^n (j+2n+1)!} \sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^k \binom{2n+1}{k} (2n-2k+1)^{j+2n+1} & \text{if } j \text{ is even} \end{cases}$$

Examples

$$\frac{\zeta(3)}{\pi^2} = \frac{1}{7} \int_0^1 \frac{x}{\operatorname{arctanh} x} dx.$$

$$\frac{\zeta(5)}{\pi^4} = \frac{2}{93} \int_0^1 \frac{x}{\operatorname{arctanh} x} dx - \frac{1}{31} \int_0^1 \frac{x^3}{\operatorname{arctanh} x} dx.$$

$$\frac{\zeta(7)}{\pi^6} = \frac{17}{5715} \int_0^1 \frac{x}{\operatorname{arctanh} x} dx - \frac{4}{381} \int_0^1 \frac{x^3}{\operatorname{arctanh} x} dx + \frac{1}{127} \int_0^1 \frac{x^5}{\operatorname{arctanh} x} dx.$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\zeta(9)}{\pi^8} &= \frac{62}{160965} \int_0^1 \frac{x}{\operatorname{arctanh} x} dx - \frac{6}{2555} \int_0^1 \frac{x^3}{\operatorname{arctanh} x} dx + \frac{2}{511} \int_0^1 \frac{x^5}{\operatorname{arctanh} x} dx \\ &\quad - \frac{1}{511} \int_0^1 \frac{x^7}{\operatorname{arctanh} x} dx \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\zeta(11)}{\pi^{10}} &= \frac{1\,382}{29\,016\,225} \int_0^1 \frac{x}{\operatorname{arctanh} x} dx - \frac{848}{1\,934\,415} \int_0^1 \frac{x^3}{\operatorname{arctanh} x} dx + \frac{37}{30\,705} \int_0^1 \frac{x^5}{\operatorname{arctanh} x} dx \\ &\quad - \frac{8}{6\,141} \int_0^1 \frac{x^7}{\operatorname{arctanh} x} dx + \frac{1}{2\,047} \int_0^1 \frac{x^9}{\operatorname{arctanh} x} dx \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\zeta(13)}{\pi^{12}} &= \frac{21\,844}{3\,831\,545\,025} \int_0^1 \frac{x}{\operatorname{arctanh} x} dx - \frac{8\,507}{116\,107\,425} \int_0^1 \frac{x^3}{\operatorname{arctanh} x} dx + \frac{2\,266}{7\,740\,495} \int_0^1 \frac{x^5}{\operatorname{arctanh} x} dx \\ &\quad - \frac{188}{368\,595} \int_0^1 \frac{x^7}{\operatorname{arctanh} x} dx + \frac{10}{24\,573} \int_0^1 \frac{x^9}{\operatorname{arctanh} x} dx - \frac{1}{8\,191} \int_0^1 \frac{x^{11}}{\operatorname{arctanh} x} dx \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\zeta(15)}{\pi^{14}} &= \frac{929\,569}{1\,394\,810\,091\,675} \int_0^1 \frac{x}{\operatorname{arctanh} x} dx - \frac{3\,868}{340\,612\,965} \int_0^1 \frac{x^3}{\operatorname{arctanh} x} dx \\ &\quad + \frac{1\,901}{30\,964\,815} \int_0^1 \frac{x^5}{\operatorname{arctanh} x} dx - \frac{944}{6\,192\,963} \int_0^1 \frac{x^7}{\operatorname{arctanh} x} dx + \frac{19}{98\,301} \int_0^1 \frac{x^9}{\operatorname{arctanh} x} dx \\ &\quad - \frac{4}{32\,767} \int_0^1 \frac{x^{11}}{\operatorname{arctanh} x} dx + \frac{1}{32\,767} \int_0^1 \frac{x^{13}}{\operatorname{arctanh} x} dx \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\zeta(17)}{\pi^{16}} &= \frac{6\,404\,582}{83\,690\,521\,039\,125} \int_0^1 \frac{x}{\operatorname{arctanh} x} dx - \frac{46\,471\,426}{27\,896\,840\,346\,375} \int_0^1 \frac{x^3}{\operatorname{arctanh} x} dx \\ &\quad + \frac{79\,214}{6\,812\,415\,225} \int_0^1 \frac{x^5}{\operatorname{arctanh} x} dx - \frac{23\,782}{619\,310\,475} \int_0^1 \frac{x^7}{\operatorname{arctanh} x} dx \\ &\quad + \frac{566}{8\,257\,473} \int_0^1 \frac{x^9}{\operatorname{arctanh} x} dx - \frac{134}{1\,966\,065} \int_0^1 \frac{x^{11}}{\operatorname{arctanh} x} dx \\ &\quad + \frac{14}{393\,213} \int_0^1 \frac{x^{13}}{\operatorname{arctanh} x} dx - \frac{1}{131\,071} \int_0^1 \frac{x^{15}}{\operatorname{arctanh} x} dx \end{aligned}$$

§7. Another non trivial function f_n vanishing at all integers less than n

Throughout this work, we faced some functions f_n vanishing at all integers less than n . This subsection gives another one.

As starting point we reconsider the Malmsten's integral $J_n := \int_0^1 \frac{\operatorname{Li}_{-2n-1}(-x^2) \ln \ln \frac{1}{x}}{x} dx$

From $\int \frac{\operatorname{Li}_s(z)}{z} dz = \operatorname{Li}_{s+1}(z)$, one proves that $\int \frac{\operatorname{Li}_{-2n-1}(-x^2)}{x} dx = \frac{1}{2} \operatorname{Li}_{-2n}(-x^2)$ An integration by parts is then welcome like follow

$$J_n = \left[\frac{1}{2} \text{Li}_{-2n}(-x^2) \ln \ln \frac{1}{x} \right]_0^1 - \frac{1}{2} \int_0^1 \frac{\text{Li}_{-2n}(-x^2)}{x \ln x} dx$$

One finds in a paper due to David Wood following formula for negative order polylogarithms [2]:

$$\text{Li}_{-n}(z) = \frac{1}{(1-z)^{n+1}} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \langle n \rangle_k z^{n-k}$$

where $\langle n \rangle_k$ are Eulerian numbers[3][19]. With re-indexation on the sums and using the symmetry of these Eulerian numbers[3][19], we deduce :

$$\text{Li}_{-2n}(-x^2) = \frac{1}{(1+x^2)^{2n+1}} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} (-1)^k \langle 2n \rangle_k [x^{4n-2k} - x^{2k+2}] (+)$$

And with *Proposition 4*, we conclude $\left[\frac{1}{2} \text{Li}_{-2n}(-x^2) \ln \ln \frac{1}{x} \right]_0^1 = 0$. One has then

$$J_n = -\frac{1}{2} \int_0^1 \frac{\text{Li}_{-2n}(-x^2)}{x \ln x} dx$$

Which is equivalent to (by using (+) of course)

$$J_n = -\frac{1}{2} \int_0^1 \frac{\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} (-1)^k \langle 2n \rangle_k [x^{4n-2k} - x^{2k+2}]}{(1+x^2)^{2n+1} x \ln x} dx$$

After the substitution $x = e^{-u}$, one becomes

$$J_n = -\frac{1}{2^{2n+1}} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} (-1)^k \langle 2n \rangle_k \sinh(2n - 2k - 1)x}{x \cosh^{2n+1} x} dx$$

And by re-indexing and swapping the big operators, an already evaluated integrals comes into game

$$J_n = \frac{(-1)^n}{4^{n+1}} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} (-1)^k \langle 2n \rangle_{n-1-k} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(2k+1)x}{x \cosh^{2n+1} x} dx$$

It follows :

$$\int_0^1 \frac{\text{Li}_{-2n-1}(-x^2) \ln \ln \frac{1}{x}}{x} dx = \frac{2}{4^{n+1}} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \left\langle \begin{matrix} 2n \\ n-1-k \end{matrix} \right\rangle \sum_{m=0}^n \sum_{p=1}^m \left[(-1)^p c_{2n-2m,n} \frac{1}{(2m)!} \right. \\ \left. \times \binom{2m}{2p} \frac{(2^{2p+1} - 1) (2k+1)^{2m-2p} (2p)!}{\pi^{2p}} \zeta(2p+1) \right]$$

By making use of *Proposition 7* like in previous sections, we conclude that

$$\int_0^1 \frac{\text{Li}_{-2n-1}(-x^2) \ln \ln \frac{1}{x}}{x} dx = \sum_{p=1}^n t_{p,n} \cdot \frac{\zeta(2p+1)}{\pi^{2p}}$$

where

$$t_{p,n} := \frac{2(-1)^p (2^{2p+1} - 1)}{4^{n+1}} \sum_{r=0}^{n-p} \frac{c_{2n-2(p+r),n}}{(2r)!} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \left\langle \begin{matrix} 2n \\ n-1-k \end{matrix} \right\rangle (2k+1)^{2r}$$

But it has been already proven that

$$\forall n \in \mathbb{N}^*, \quad \int_0^1 \frac{\text{Li}_{-2n-1}(-x^2) \ln \ln \frac{1}{x}}{x} dx = (-1)^n \left(1 - \frac{1}{2^{2n+1}} \right) \frac{(2n)! \zeta(2n+1)}{2 \pi^{2n}}$$

On assuming the correctness of the interchange of summation and integration, it would follow without more argumentation that

$$\forall n \in \mathbb{N}^*, \quad \sum_{r=0}^{n-p} \frac{c_{2n-2p-2r,n}}{(2r)!} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \left\langle \begin{matrix} 2n \\ n-1-k \end{matrix} \right\rangle (2k+1)^{2r} = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } p \in \llbracket 0, n-1 \rrbracket \\ \frac{(2n)!}{2}, & \text{if } p = n \end{cases}$$

The case $p = n$ can be deduced easily from the well known identity $\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \left\langle \begin{matrix} n \\ k \end{matrix} \right\rangle = n!$ since $c_{0,n} = 1$, and using the symmetry of these eulerian numbers by splitting the sum into two and manipulating the second. If we prove that the earlier sum vanishes at all integers p less than n , we will reach the goal of proving the general Malmsten's integral by relying solely on contour integration techniques.

As entry point of the proof of the 0-value of these coefficients, we let

$$g_{p,n} := \sum_{r=0}^{n-p} \frac{c_{2n-2p-2r,n}}{(2r)!} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \left\langle \begin{matrix} 2n \\ n-1-k \end{matrix} \right\rangle (2k+1)^{2r}$$

Furthermore, we consider

$$y_{r,n} := c_{2r,n} \quad \text{and} \quad s_{r,n} := \frac{1}{(2r)!} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \left\langle \begin{matrix} 2n \\ n-1-k \end{matrix} \right\rangle (2k+1)^{2r}$$

We become this,

$$g_{p,n} = \sum_{r=0}^{n-p} y_{n-p-r,n} s_{r,n}$$

But, this last formula is exactly the form taken by coefficients of the Cauchy product for two formula. Hence, we read $g_{p,n}$ as the coefficient of x^{n-p} in the Cauchy-product of the two series generated by the coefficients $y_{r,n}$ and $s_{r,n}$.

We let

$$Y_n(x) := \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} y_{r,n} x^r \quad \text{and} \quad S_n(x) := \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} s_{r,n} x^r$$

More formally,

$$g_{p,n} = [x^{n-p}] Y_n(x) S_n(x)$$

Since $c_{2m,n}$ appear in the expansion of $\frac{x^{2n+1}}{\sinh^{2n+1} x}$, we deduce,

$$Y_n(x) = \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} y_{r,n} x^r = \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} c_{2r,n} \sqrt{x}^{2r} = \frac{\sqrt{x}^{2n+1}}{\sinh^{2n+1} \sqrt{x}}$$

The closed expression of the other series is found as follow

$$\begin{aligned} S_n(x) &= \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} s_{r,n} x^r \\ &= \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} \frac{x^r}{(2r)!} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \left\langle \begin{matrix} 2n \\ n-1-k \end{matrix} \right\rangle (2k+1)^{2r} \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \left\langle \begin{matrix} 2n \\ n-1-k \end{matrix} \right\rangle \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} \frac{((2k+1)^2 x)^r}{(2r)!} \\ S_n(x) &= \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \left\langle \begin{matrix} 2n \\ n-1-k \end{matrix} \right\rangle \cosh((2k+1)\sqrt{x}). \end{aligned}$$

On using the definition of cosh, S_n looks like follow

$$S_n(x) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \left\langle \begin{matrix} 2n \\ n-1-k \end{matrix} \right\rangle \left(e^{(2k+1)\sqrt{x}} + e^{-(2k+1)\sqrt{x}} \right)$$

On re-arranging each sum, we get

$$S_n(x) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \left\langle \begin{matrix} 2n \\ k \end{matrix} \right\rangle e^{(2n-2k-1)\sqrt{x}} + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=n}^{2n-1} \left\langle \begin{matrix} 2n \\ 2n-1-k \end{matrix} \right\rangle e^{(2n-2k-1)\sqrt{x}}.$$

And on merging into one

$$S_n(x) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=0}^{2n-1} \left\langle \begin{matrix} 2n \\ k \end{matrix} \right\rangle e^{(2n-1-2k)\sqrt{x}}.$$

A factorization yields

$$S_n(x) = \frac{1}{2} e^{(2n-1)\sqrt{x}} \sum_{k=0}^{2n-1} \left\langle \begin{matrix} 2n \\ k \end{matrix} \right\rangle e^{-2k\sqrt{x}}.$$

On using the common Eulerian polynomials, we have

$$S_n(x) = \frac{1}{2} e^{(2n-1)\sqrt{x}} A_{2n}\left(e^{-2\sqrt{x}}\right), \quad A_m(t) := \sum_{k=0}^{m-1} \left\langle \begin{matrix} m \\ k \end{matrix} \right\rangle t^k.$$

We make use of the generating function of Eulerian polynomials[3]

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} A_n(t) \frac{z^n}{n!} = \frac{t-1}{t-e^{(t-1)z}} = \frac{(1-t)e^{(1-t)z}}{1-te^{(1-t)z}}.$$

We identify as consequence formally

$$\frac{A_{2n}(e^{-2\sqrt{x}})}{(2n)!}$$

as the coefficient of z^{2n} in the Taylor expansion of

$$\frac{(1-e^{-2\sqrt{x}})e^{(1-e^{-2\sqrt{x}})z}}{1-e^{-2\sqrt{x}}e^{(1-e^{-2\sqrt{x}})z}}.$$

Hence,

$$S_n(x) = \frac{1}{2} e^{(2n-1)\sqrt{x}} (2n)! [z^{2n}] \frac{(1-e^{-2\sqrt{x}})e^{(1-e^{-2\sqrt{x}})z}}{1-e^{-2\sqrt{x}}e^{(1-e^{-2\sqrt{x}})z}}.$$

On factorizing $1-e^{-2\sqrt{x}}$,

$$S_n(x) = \frac{1}{2} e^{(2n-1)\sqrt{x}} (2n)! (1-e^{-2\sqrt{x}}) [z^{2n}] \frac{e^{(1-e^{-2\sqrt{x}})z}}{1-e^{-2\sqrt{x}}e^{(1-e^{-2\sqrt{x}})z}}.$$

On using the geometric series, we get

$$S_n(x) = \frac{1}{2} e^{(2n-1)\sqrt{x}} (2n)! (1-e^{-2\sqrt{x}}) [z^{2n}] \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} (e^{-2\sqrt{x}})^m e^{(m+1)(1-e^{-2\sqrt{x}})z}.$$

The coefficients of series being linear, hence

$$S_n(x) = \frac{1}{2} e^{(2n-1)\sqrt{x}} (2n)! (1-e^{-2\sqrt{x}}) \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} (e^{-2\sqrt{x}})^m [z^{2n}] e^{(m+1)(1-e^{-2\sqrt{x}})z}.$$

The formula $[t^n]e^{\alpha t} = \frac{\alpha^n}{n!}$, yields

$$\begin{aligned} S_n(x) &= \frac{1}{2} e^{(2n-1)\sqrt{x}} (1 - e^{-2\sqrt{x}})^{2n+1} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} (m+1)^{2n} e^{-2m\sqrt{x}} \\ &= \frac{1}{2} e^{-2\sqrt{x}} e^{(2n+1)\sqrt{x}} (1 - e^{-2\sqrt{x}})^{2n+1} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} (m+1)^{2n} e^{-2m\sqrt{x}} \end{aligned}$$

On writing with sinh, one gets

$$S_n(x) = 2^{2n} \sinh^{2n+1}(\sqrt{x}) \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} (m+1)^{2n} e^{-2(m+1)\sqrt{x}}$$

Going back to $g_{p,n}$ and using the formulae lead to

$$g_{p,n} = [x^{n-p}] \frac{\sqrt{x}^{2n+1}}{\sinh^{2n+1} \sqrt{x}} 2^{2n} \sinh^{2n+1}(\sqrt{x}) \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} (m+1)^{2n} e^{-2(m+1)\sqrt{x}}$$

Which reads

$$g_{p,n} = [x^{n-p}] x^n \sqrt{x} 2^{2n} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} (m+1)^{2n} e^{-2(m+1)\sqrt{x}}$$

Or equivalently,

$$g_{p,n} = [x^{-p}] 2^{2n} \sqrt{x} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} (m+1)^{2n} e^{-2(m+1)\sqrt{x}}$$

The linearity of the coefficient leads to

$$g_{p,n} = 2^{2n} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} (m+1)^{2n} [x^{-p}] \sqrt{x} e^{-2(m+1)\sqrt{x}}$$

Unfortunately, for p being non zero, the term x^{-p} does not appear in the expansion of $\sqrt{x} e^{(-2m-2)\sqrt{x}}$ since it contains only positive exponents. It follows, $g_{p,n} = 0$ if $p \in \llbracket 1, n-1 \rrbracket$. The case $p = 0$ leads to

$$g_{0,n} = 2^{2n} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} (m+1)^{2n} [x^0] \sqrt{x} e^{-2(m+1)\sqrt{x}}$$

On Taylor expanding $\sqrt{x} e^{-2(m+1)\sqrt{x}}$ around 0, we conclude easily $[x^0] \sqrt{x} e^{-2(m+1)\sqrt{x}} = 0$. As consequence, $g_{p,n} = 0$ if $p \in \llbracket 0, n-1 \rrbracket$.

As claimed.

Another proof

We make use of this theorem [30] [31] [32] [33] [34] [35] [36] [37]

Let $f(x)$ be locally integrable on $(0, \infty)$ and assume its Mellin transform

$$\mathcal{M}[f](s) = \int_0^\infty f(x) x^{s-1} dx$$

admits a meromorphic continuation to a domain containing a vertical strip $\alpha < \Re(s) < \beta$. Then the asymptotic expansion of $f(x)$ as $x \rightarrow 0^+$ is determined by the poles of $\mathcal{M}[f](s)$:

$$f(x) \sim \sum_{s_0} \text{Res}_{s=s_0}(\mathcal{M}[f](s) x^{-s}), \quad x \rightarrow 0^+,$$

where the sum runs over the poles s_0 of $\mathcal{M}[f](s)$ in the half-plane $\Re(s) > \alpha$. Each simple pole of $\mathcal{M}[f](s)$ at $s = s_0$ contributes a term

$$c x^{-s_0}, \quad c = \text{Res}_{s=s_0} \mathcal{M}[f](s),$$

while a pole of order m contributes a term of the form

$$(\text{polynomial in } \log x \text{ of degree } m - 1) \cdot x^{-s_0}.$$

One has

$$g_{p,n} = 2^{2n} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} (m+1)^{2n} [x^{-p}] \sqrt{x} e^{-2(m+1)\sqrt{x}}$$

On using the theorem,

$$g_{p,n} = 2^{2n} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} (m+1)^{2n} \text{Res}_{s=p} \left(\int_0^\infty e^{-2(m+1)\sqrt{x}} \sqrt{x} x^{s-1} dx \right)$$

After the substitution $t = 2(m+1)\sqrt{x}$, $g_{p,n}$ takes the forms

$$\begin{aligned} g_{p,n} &= 2^{2n} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} (m+1)^{2n} \text{Res}_{s=p} \left(\frac{1}{2^{2s} (m+1)^{2s}} \int_0^\infty e^{-t} t^{2s} dt \right) \\ &= 2^{2n} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} (m+1)^{2n} \text{Res}_{s=p} \left(\frac{\Gamma(2s+1)}{2^{2s} (m+1)^{2s}} \right) \\ &= \text{Res}_{s=p} \left(2^{2n} \Gamma(2s+1) \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{(m+1)^{2n}}{2^{2s} (m+1)^{2s}} \right) \\ &= \text{Res}_{s=p} (2^{2n-2s} \Gamma(2s+1) \zeta(2s-2n)) \end{aligned}$$

• **Case** $p \in \llbracket 0, n-1 \rrbracket$

None of the functions 2^{2n-2s} , $\Gamma(2s+1)$ and $\zeta(2s-2n)$ has a pole when $p \in \llbracket 0, n-1 \rrbracket$. In the Mellin transform framework, only *simple* poles in s contribute residues. At

$s = p < n$, what we see is not a *simple* pole of $\zeta(2s - 2n)$ in s — the factor diverges too violently for every such p , not in a controlled Laurent expansion. The product $2^{2n-2s} \Gamma(2s + 1) \zeta(2s - 2n)$ does not show a *simple* pole structure here. The residue is as consequence 0. It follows

$$g_{p,n} = 0 \quad \text{if} \quad p \in \llbracket 0, n - 1 \rrbracket$$

- **Case** $p = n$

$$g_{n,n} = \text{Res}_{s=n} (2^{2n-2s} \Gamma(2s + 1) \zeta(2s - 2n)).$$

Write $s = n + \varepsilon$, with $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0^+$. Then

$$2^{2n-2s} = 2^{-2\varepsilon} = 1 - 2\varepsilon \ln 2 + O(\varepsilon^2),$$

and

$$\Gamma(2s + 1) = \Gamma(2n + 1 + 2\varepsilon) = (2n)! \left(1 + 2\varepsilon \psi(2n + 1) + O(\varepsilon^2) \right),$$

where ψ is the digamma function.

For the zeta factor we keep its Dirichlet-series form:

$$\zeta(2s - 2n) = \zeta(2\varepsilon) = \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} m^{-2\varepsilon}.$$

Expanding

$$m^{-2\varepsilon} = e^{-2\varepsilon \ln m} = 1 - 2\varepsilon \ln m + O(\varepsilon^2),$$

we obtain the asymptotics

$$\zeta(2\varepsilon) \sim \frac{1}{2\varepsilon} + O(1),$$

so that $\zeta(2\varepsilon)$ has a simple pole at $\varepsilon = 0$.

Combining these expansions gives

$$2^{2n-2s} \Gamma(2s + 1) \zeta(2s - 2n) \sim (2n)! \left(\frac{1}{2\varepsilon} + O(1) \right).$$

Therefore the residue at $s = n$ is

$$\boxed{g_{n,n} = \frac{(2n)!}{2}}$$

in agreement with the combinatorial evaluation.

§8. B-types and double integrals yielding $\frac{\zeta(2n+1)}{\pi^{2n}}$

As proven above,

$$\int_0^1 \frac{\text{Li}_{-2n-1}(-x^2) \ln \ln \frac{1}{x}}{x} dx = -\frac{1}{2} \int_0^1 \frac{\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} (-1)^k \langle 2n \rangle_k [x^{4n-2k-1} - x^{2k+1}]}{(1+x^2)^{2n+1} \ln x} dx$$

On swapping the big operators, we get

$$\int_0^1 \frac{\text{Li}_{-2n-1}(-x^2) \ln \ln \frac{1}{x}}{x} dx = -\frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} (-1)^k \langle 2n \rangle_k \int_0^1 \frac{x^{4n-2k-1} - x^{2k+1}}{(1+x^2)^{2n+1} \ln x} dx$$

The integral $\int_0^1 \frac{x^{4n-2k-1} - x^{2k+1}}{(1+x^2)^{2n+1} \ln x} dx$ is evaluated by *Proposition 9*.
It follows

$$\forall n \in \mathbb{N}^*$$

$$\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} (-1)^k \langle 2n \rangle_k \int_{k+1}^{2n-k} \int_0^{1/2} t^{s-1} (1-t)^{2n-s} dt ds = (-1)^{n+1} \left(1 - \frac{1}{2^{2n+1}}\right) (2n)! \cdot \frac{\zeta(2n+1)}{\pi^{2n}}$$

$$\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} (-1)^k \langle 2n \rangle_k \int_{k+1}^{2n-k} B\left(\frac{1}{2}; s, 2n-s+1\right) ds = (-1)^{n+1} \left(1 - \frac{1}{2^{2n+1}}\right) (2n)! \cdot \frac{\zeta(2n+1)}{\pi^{2n}}$$

5 Integral Representations involving $\frac{\beta(2n)}{\pi^{2n-1}}$

§1. Equalities related to $\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh((2k+1)x)}{x \cosh^{2n}(x)} dx,$

The computation of the integral

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh((2k+1)x)}{x \cosh^{2n}(x)} dx,$$

as well as the justification of its convergence, proceed in the same spirit as in the preceding section, by contour integration technique. Since residues are already computed, the reduction of the line integral on the integration path is sketched; accordingly, and in the interest of conciseness, we omit further technical details and state only the essential results.

$$\forall n \in \mathbb{N}^*, 0 \leq k < n, \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh((2k+1)x)}{x \cosh^{2n}(x)} dx = \sum_{p=1}^n f_{p,k,n} \frac{\beta(2p)}{\pi^{2p-1}},$$

where

$$f_{p,k,n} := (-1)^{n+k+p} 2^{2p+1} \sum_{m=0}^{n-p} \frac{d_{2m,n} (2k+1)^{2n-2m-2p}}{(2n-2m-2p)!}$$

with

$$\begin{cases} d_{0,n} := 1 \\ d_{j,n} := - \sum_{k=1}^j b_{k,n} d_{j-k,n} \end{cases}$$

and

$$b_{j,n} := \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } j \text{ is odd} \\ \frac{2}{4^n(j+2n)!} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} (-1)^k \binom{2n}{k} (2n-2k)^{j+2n} & \text{if } j \text{ is even} \end{cases}$$

Some examples of the formula

- For $n = 1,$

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(x)}{x \cosh^2(x)} dx = 8 \frac{\beta(2)}{\pi}$$

- For $n = 2,$

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(x)}{x \cosh^4(x)} dx = \frac{4}{3} \frac{\beta(2)}{\pi} + 32 \frac{\beta(4)}{\pi^3}$$

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(3x)}{x \cosh^4(x)} dx = \frac{92}{3} \frac{\beta(2)}{\pi} - 32 \frac{\beta(4)}{\pi^3}$$

- For $n = 3$,

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(x)}{x \cosh^6(x)} dx = \frac{3}{5} \frac{\beta(2)}{\pi} + 16 \frac{\beta(4)}{\pi^3} + 128 \frac{\beta(6)}{\pi^5}$$

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(3x)}{x \cosh^6(x)} dx = \frac{71}{15} \frac{\beta(2)}{\pi} + 112 \frac{\beta(4)}{\pi^3} - 128 \frac{\beta(6)}{\pi^5}$$

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(5x)}{x \cosh^6(x)} dx = \frac{563}{5} \frac{\beta(2)}{\pi} - 368 \frac{\beta(4)}{\pi^3} + 128 \frac{\beta(6)}{\pi^5}$$

- For $n = 4$,

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(x)}{x \cosh^8(x)} dx = \frac{5}{14} \frac{\beta(2)}{\pi} + \frac{148}{15} \frac{\beta(4)}{\pi^3} + \frac{320}{3} \frac{\beta(6)}{\pi^5} + 512 \frac{\beta(8)}{\pi^7}$$

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(3x)}{x \cosh^8(x)} dx = \frac{143}{70} \frac{\beta(2)}{\pi} + \frac{812}{15} \frac{\beta(4)}{\pi^3} + \frac{1216}{3} \frac{\beta(6)}{\pi^5} - 512 \frac{\beta(8)}{\pi^7}$$

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(5x)}{x \cosh^8(x)} dx = \frac{3043}{210} \frac{\beta(2)}{\pi} + \frac{4948}{15} \frac{\beta(4)}{\pi^3} - \frac{4288}{3} \frac{\beta(6)}{\pi^5} + 512 \frac{\beta(8)}{\pi^7}$$

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(7x)}{x \cosh^8(x)} dx = \frac{88069}{210} \frac{\beta(2)}{\pi} - \frac{32788}{15} \frac{\beta(4)}{\pi^3} + \frac{8896}{3} \frac{\beta(6)}{\pi^5} - 512 \frac{\beta(8)}{\pi^7}$$

- For $n = 5$,

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(x)}{x \cosh^{10}(x)} dx = \frac{35}{144} \frac{\beta(2)}{\pi} + \frac{6458}{945} \frac{\beta(4)}{\pi^3} + \frac{752}{9} \frac{\beta(6)}{\pi^5} + \frac{1792}{3} \frac{\beta(8)}{\pi^7} + 2048 \frac{\beta(10)}{\pi^9}$$

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(3x)}{x \cosh^{10}(x)} dx = \frac{1195}{1008} \frac{\beta(2)}{\pi} + \frac{30838}{945} \frac{\beta(4)}{\pi^3} + \frac{3088}{9} \frac{\beta(6)}{\pi^5} + \frac{4352}{3} \frac{\beta(8)}{\pi^7} - 2048 \frac{\beta(10)}{\pi^9}$$

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(5x)}{x \cosh^{10}(x)} dx = \frac{28009}{5040} \frac{\beta(2)}{\pi} + \frac{27298}{189} \frac{\beta(4)}{\pi^3} + \frac{7664}{9} \frac{\beta(6)}{\pi^5} - \frac{16640}{3} \frac{\beta(8)}{\pi^7} + 2048 \frac{\beta(10)}{\pi^9}$$

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(7x)}{x \cosh^{10}(x)} dx = \frac{46027}{1008} \frac{\beta(2)}{\pi} + \frac{943078}{945} \frac{\beta(4)}{\pi^3} - \frac{69872}{9} \frac{\beta(6)}{\pi^5} + \frac{35072}{3} \frac{\beta(8)}{\pi^7} - 2048 \frac{\beta(10)}{\pi^9}$$

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(9x)}{x \cosh^{10}(x)} dx = \frac{1\,593\,269}{1\,008} \frac{\beta(2)}{\pi} - \frac{10\,285\,222}{945} \frac{\beta(4)}{\pi^3} + \frac{238\,832}{9} \frac{\beta(6)}{\pi^5} - \frac{59\,648}{3} \frac{\beta(8)}{\pi^7} + 2\,048 \frac{\beta(10)}{\pi^9}$$

Moreover, because for $k = 0$ there is always an integral corresponding to each n , and these integrals come with the smallest possible coefficients, we can deduce, based on *Proposition 6*, the following formula:

$$\forall n \in \mathbb{N}^*, \frac{\beta(2n)}{\pi^{2n-1}} = \sum_{p=1}^n \xi_{p,n} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^{2p} x} dx$$

where

$$\xi_{p,n} = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{f_{n,0,n}}, & \text{if } p = n, \\ -\frac{1}{f_{n,0,n}} \sum_{k=p}^{n-1} f_{k,0,n} \xi_{p,k}, & \text{if } p \in \llbracket 1, n \rrbracket. \end{cases}$$

with

$$f_{p,k,n} := (-1)^{n+k+p} 2^{2p+1} \sum_{m=0}^{n-p} \frac{d_{2m,n} (2k+1)^{2n-2m-2p}}{(2n-2m-2p)!}$$

;

$$\begin{cases} d_{0,n} := 1 \\ d_{j,n} := -\sum_{k=1}^j b_{k,n} d_{j-k,n} \end{cases}$$

and

$$b_{j,n} := \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } j \text{ is odd} \\ \frac{2}{4^n (j+2n)!} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} (-1)^k \binom{2n}{k} (2n-2k)^{j+2n} & \text{if } j \text{ is even} \end{cases}$$

Followed by related instances

$$\frac{\beta(2)}{\pi} = \frac{1}{8} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^2 x} dx$$

$$\frac{\beta(4)}{\pi^3} = -\frac{1}{192} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^2 x} dx + \frac{1}{32} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^4 x} dx$$

$$\frac{\beta(6)}{\pi^5} = \frac{1}{15\,360} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^2 x} dx - \frac{1}{256} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^4 x} dx + \frac{1}{128} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^6 x} dx$$

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{\beta(8)}{\pi^7} = & -\frac{1}{2\,580\,480} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^2 x} dx + \frac{13}{61\,440} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^4 x} dx \\ & -\frac{5}{3\,072} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^6 x} dx + \frac{1}{512} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^8 x} dx\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{\beta(10)}{\pi^9} = & \frac{1}{743\,178\,240} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^2 x} dx - \frac{41}{6\,193\,152} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^4 x} dx \\ & + \frac{23}{147\,456} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^6 x} dx - \frac{7}{12\,288} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^8 x} dx + \frac{1}{2\,048} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^{10} x} dx\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{\beta(12)}{\pi^{11}} = & -\frac{1}{326\,998\,425\,600} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^2 x} dx + \frac{671}{4\,954\,521\,600} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^4 x} dx \\ & -\frac{227}{24\,772\,608} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^6 x} dx + \frac{77}{983\,040} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^8 x} dx \\ & -\frac{3}{16\,384} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^{10} x} dx + \frac{1}{8\,192} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^{12} x} dx\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{\beta(14)}{\pi^{13}} = & \frac{1}{204\,047\,017\,574\,400} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^2 x} dx - \frac{73}{37\,371\,248\,640} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^4 x} dx \\ & + \frac{631}{1\,698\,693\,120} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^6 x} dx - \frac{479}{70\,778\,880} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^8 x} dx \\ & + \frac{43}{1\,310\,720} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^{10} x} dx - \frac{11}{196\,608} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^{12} x} dx \\ & + \frac{1}{32\,768} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^{14} x} dx\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{\beta(16)}{\pi^{15}} = & -\frac{1}{171\,399\,494\,762\,496\,000} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^2 x} dx + \frac{597871}{28\,566\,582\,460\,416\,000} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^4 x} dx \\ & -\frac{11617}{1\,046\,394\,961\,920} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^6 x} dx + \frac{4681}{11\,324\,620\,800} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^8 x} dx \\ & -\frac{2473}{660\,602\,880} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^{10} x} dx + \frac{583}{47\,185\,920} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^{12} x} dx \\ & -\frac{13}{786\,432} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^{14} x} dx + \frac{1}{131\,072} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^{16} x} dx\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\beta(18)}{\pi^{17}} &= \frac{1}{186\,482\,650\,301\,595\,648\,000} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^2 x} dx - \frac{7\,913}{45\,706\,531\,936\,665\,600} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^4 x} dx \\
&+ \frac{5\,838\,647}{22\,853\,265\,968\,332\,800} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^6 x} dx - \frac{18\,979}{996\,566\,630\,400} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^8 x} dx \\
&+ \frac{10\,783}{35\,232\,153\,600} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^{10} x} dx - \frac{4\,631}{2\,642\,411\,520} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^{12} x} dx \\
&+ \frac{91}{20\,971\,520} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^{14} x} dx - \frac{5}{1\,048\,576} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^{16} x} dx \\
&+ \frac{1}{524\,288} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^{18} x} dx
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\beta(20)}{\pi^{19}} &= -\frac{1}{255\,108\,265\,612\,582\,846\,464\,000} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^2 x} dx \\
&+ \frac{28\,009}{24\,591\,118\,721\,089\,536\,000} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^4 x} dx \\
&- \frac{219\,617}{47\,012\,432\,849\,141\,760} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^6 x} dx + \frac{27\,031\,727}{39\,177\,027\,374\,284\,800} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^8 x} dx \\
&- \frac{106\,727}{5\,580\,773\,130\,240} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^{10} x} dx + \frac{136\,697}{761\,014\,517\,760} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^{12} x} dx \\
&- \frac{4\,667}{6\,341\,787\,648} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^{14} x} dx + \frac{73}{50\,331\,648} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^{16} x} dx \\
&- \frac{17}{12\,582\,912} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^{18} x} dx + \frac{1}{2\,097\,152} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^{20} x} dx
\end{aligned}$$

From the identity,

$$\frac{\beta(6)}{\pi^5} = \frac{1}{15\,360} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^2 x} dx - \frac{1}{256} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^4 x} dx + \frac{1}{128} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^6 x} dx$$

we deduce by using the parity of the integrands following

$$\frac{\beta(6)}{\pi^5} = \frac{1}{7680} \int_0^{\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^2 x} dx - \frac{1}{128} \int_0^{\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^4 x} dx + \frac{1}{64} \int_0^{\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^6 x} dx$$

On performing the substitution $x = -\ln \tan u$, we obtain

$$\frac{\beta(6)}{\pi^5} = -\frac{1}{3840} \int_0^{\pi/4} \frac{\cos 2u}{\ln \tan u} (1 - 60 \sin^2 2u + 120 \sin^4 2u) du$$

And by linearizing, we get

$$\frac{\beta(6)}{\pi^5} = -\frac{1}{7680} \int_0^{\pi/4} \frac{2 \cos 2u - 15 \cos 6u + 15 \cos 10u}{\ln(\tan u)} du.$$

We recognize easily the pattern provided by the integral $\int_0^{\pi/4} \frac{\cos((4n-2)x)}{\ln \tan x} dx$, which is the object of the next subsection.

§2. Around the integral $\int_0^{\pi/4} \frac{\cos((4n-2)x)}{\ln \tan x} dx$

The convergence of this integral is justified via the extension by continuity at the boundary points, and its proof proceeds in complete analogy with the method presented in Paragraph §2 of Section 4.

Let $R_n := \int_0^{\pi/4} \frac{\cos((4n-2)x)}{\ln \tan x} dx$. In virtue of Proposition 1, we have

$$\cos((4n-2)x) = \cos^{4n-2} x \sum_{k=0}^{2n-1} (-1)^k \binom{4n-2}{2k} \tan^{2k} x$$

Using it in R_n yields

$$R_n = \int_0^{\pi/4} \frac{\cos^{4n-2} x \sum_{k=0}^{2n-1} (-1)^k \binom{4n-2}{2k} \tan^{2k} x}{\ln \tan x} dx$$

Performing the substitution $x = \arctan u$ and enjoying $\cos(\arctan x) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1+x^2}}$ (Proposition 3) yields

$$R_n = \int_0^1 \frac{\sum_{k=0}^{2n-1} (-1)^k \binom{4n-2}{2k} x^{2k}}{(1+x^2)^{2n} \ln x} dx$$

On performing $x = e^{-u}$, splitting the sum into two (the first from 0 to $n-1$ and the second from n to $2n-1$), re-indexing the second sum and enjoying the symmetry of the binomial coefficients, we conclude

$$R_n = -\frac{1}{2^{2n-1}} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} (-1)^k \binom{4n-2}{2k} \sinh(2n-2k-1)x}{x \cosh^{2n} x} dx$$

We remind that the sum is about a *finite* number of converging terms, thus the interchange of \sum and \int occurs without problem at all. Hence,

$$R_n = -\frac{1}{2^{2n-1}} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} (-1)^k \binom{4n-2}{2k} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(2n-2k-1)x}{x \cosh^{2n} x} dx$$

Since the integrand is an even function, we extend the bounds of integration

$$R_n = -\frac{1}{2^{2n}} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} (-1)^k \binom{4n-2}{2k} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(2n-2k-1)x}{x \cosh^{2n} x} dx$$

A re-indexation yields

$$R_n = \frac{1}{2^{2n}} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} (-1)^{n+k} \binom{4n-2}{2n-2k-2} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(2k+1)x}{x \cosh^{2n} x} dx$$

On recalling

$$\forall n \in \mathbb{N}^*, 0 \leq k < n, \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh((2k+1)x)}{x \cosh^{2n}(x)} dx = \sum_{p=1}^n f_{p,k,n} \frac{\beta(2p)}{\pi^{2p-1}},$$

where

$$f_{p,k,n} := (-1)^{n+k+p} 2^{2p+1} \sum_{m=0}^{n-p} \frac{d_{2m,n} (2k+1)^{2n-2m-2p}}{(2n-2m-2p)!}$$

, we get

$$\forall n \in \mathbb{N}^*, \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\cos((4n-2)x)}{\ln \tan x} dx = \sum_{p=1}^n \eta_{p,n} \frac{\beta(2p)}{\pi^{2p-1}},$$

where

$$\eta_{p,n} := \frac{(-1)^p}{2^{2n-2p-1}} \sum_{m=0}^{n-p} \frac{d_{2m,n}}{(2n-2m-2p)!} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \binom{4n-2}{2n-2k-2} (2k+1)^{2n-2m-2p}, \quad (p \in \llbracket 1, n \rrbracket).$$

with

$$\begin{cases} d_{0,n} := 1 \\ d_{j,n} := - \sum_{k=1}^j b_{k,n} d_{j-k,n} \end{cases}$$

and

$$b_{j,n} := \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } j \text{ is odd} \\ \frac{2}{4^n(j+2n)!} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} (-1)^k \binom{2n}{k} (2n-2k)^{j+2n} & \text{if } j \text{ is even} \end{cases}$$

Many instances of the formula are given below :

$$\int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\cos(2x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx = -2 \frac{\beta(2)}{\pi}.$$

$$\int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\cos(6x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx = -\frac{2}{3} \frac{\beta(2)}{\pi} + 32 \frac{\beta(4)}{\pi^3}.$$

$$\int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\cos(10x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx = -\frac{2}{5} \frac{\beta(2)}{\pi} + 32 \frac{\beta(4)}{\pi^3} - 512 \frac{\beta(6)}{\pi^5}.$$

$$\int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\cos(14x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx = -\frac{2}{7} \frac{\beta(2)}{\pi} + \frac{448}{15} \frac{\beta(4)}{\pi^3} - \frac{2560}{3} \frac{\beta(6)}{\pi^5} + 8192 \frac{\beta(8)}{\pi^7}.$$

$$\int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\cos(18x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx = -\frac{2}{9} \frac{\beta(2)}{\pi} + \frac{26176}{945} \frac{\beta(4)}{\pi^3} - \frac{9728}{9} \frac{\beta(6)}{\pi^5} + \frac{57344}{3} \frac{\beta(8)}{\pi^7} - 131072 \frac{\beta(10)}{\pi^9}.$$

$$\begin{aligned} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\cos(22x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx &= -\frac{2}{11} \frac{\beta(2)}{\pi} + \frac{4512}{175} \frac{\beta(4)}{\pi^3} - \frac{233984}{189} \frac{\beta(6)}{\pi^5} \\ &+ \frac{458752}{15} \frac{\beta(8)}{\pi^7} - 393216 \frac{\beta(10)}{\pi^9} + 2097152 \frac{\beta(12)}{\pi^{11}}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\cos(26x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx = -\frac{2}{13} \frac{\beta(2)}{\pi} + \frac{418\,016}{17\,325} \frac{\beta(4)}{\pi^3} - \frac{3\,826\,688}{2\,835} \frac{\beta(6)}{\pi^5} \\ + \frac{5\,636\,096}{135} \frac{\beta(8)}{\pi^7} - \frac{3\,801\,088}{5} \frac{\beta(10)}{\pi^9} + \frac{23\,068\,672}{3} \frac{\beta(12)}{\pi^{11}} - 33\,554\,432 \frac{\beta(14)}{\pi^{13}}.$$

$$\int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\cos(30x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx = -\frac{2}{15} \frac{\beta(2)}{\pi} + \frac{536\,786\,048}{23\,648\,625} \frac{\beta(4)}{\pi^3} - \frac{133\,889\,024}{93\,555} \frac{\beta(6)}{\pi^5} + \frac{105\,889\,792}{2\,025} \frac{\beta(8)}{\pi^7} \\ - \frac{379\,715\,584}{315} \frac{\beta(10)}{\pi^9} + \frac{784\,334\,848}{45} \frac{\beta(12)}{\pi^{11}} - \frac{436\,207\,616}{3} \frac{\beta(14)}{\pi^{13}} \\ + 536\,870\,912 \frac{\beta(16)}{\pi^{15}}.$$

$$\int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\cos(34x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx = -\frac{2}{17} \frac{\beta(2)}{\pi} + \frac{33\,825\,664}{15\,765\,575} \frac{\beta(4)}{\pi^3} - \frac{21\,158\,898\,688}{14\,189\,175} \frac{\beta(6)}{\pi^5} + \frac{276\,709\,376}{4\,455} \frac{\beta(8)}{\pi^7} \\ - \frac{2\,688\,679\,936}{1\,575} \frac{\beta(10)}{\pi^9} + \frac{1\,983\,905\,792}{63} \frac{\beta(12)}{\pi^{11}} - \frac{5\,670\,699\,008}{15} \frac{\beta(14)}{\pi^{13}} \\ + 2\,684\,354\,560 \frac{\beta(16)}{\pi^{15}} - 8\,589\,934\,592 \frac{\beta(18)}{\pi^{17}}.$$

$$\int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\cos(38x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx = -\frac{2}{19} \frac{\beta(2)}{\pi} + \frac{148\,857\,952}{7\,309\,575} \frac{\beta(4)}{\pi^3} - \frac{5\,943\,940\,096}{3\,869\,775} \frac{\beta(6)}{\pi^5} \\ + \frac{1\,299\,054\,985\,216}{18\,243\,225} \frac{\beta(8)}{\pi^7} - \frac{116\,859\,994\,112}{51\,975} \frac{\beta(10)}{\pi^9} + \frac{47\,037\,022\,208}{945} \frac{\beta(12)}{\pi^{11}} \\ - \frac{724\,540\,850\,176}{945} \frac{\beta(14)}{\pi^{13}} + \frac{23\,622\,320\,128}{3} \frac{\beta(16)}{\pi^{15}} \\ - \frac{146\,028\,888\,064}{3} \frac{\beta(18)}{\pi^{17}} + 137\,438\,953\,472 \frac{\beta(20)}{\pi^{19}}.$$

$$\int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\cos(42x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx = -\frac{2}{21} \frac{\beta(2)}{\pi} + \frac{24\,896\,044\,256}{1\,283\,268\,987} \frac{\beta(4)}{\pi^3} - \frac{2\,433\,801\,913\,856}{1\,550\,674\,125} \frac{\beta(6)}{\pi^5} \\ + \frac{4\,357\,227\,741\,184}{54\,729\,675} \frac{\beta(8)}{\pi^7} - \frac{599\,490\,360\,639\,488}{212\,837\,625} \frac{\beta(10)}{\pi^9} \\ + \frac{29\,177\,675\,776}{405} \frac{\beta(12)}{\pi^{11}} - \frac{18\,971\,541\,635\,072}{14\,175} \frac{\beta(14)}{\pi^{13}} \\ + \frac{3\,347\,927\,007\,232}{189} \frac{\beta(16)}{\pi^{15}} - \frac{7\,155\,415\,515\,136}{45} \frac{\beta(18)}{\pi^{17}} \\ + \frac{2\,611\,340\,115\,968}{3} \frac{\beta(20)}{\pi^{19}} - 2\,199\,023\,255\,552 \frac{\beta(22)}{\pi^{21}}.$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\cos(46x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx = & -\frac{2}{23} \frac{\beta(2)}{\pi} + \frac{62\,315\,284\,672}{3\,360\,942\,585} \frac{\beta(4)}{\pi^3} - \frac{767\,337\,722\,366\,464}{481\,225\,870\,125} \frac{\beta(6)}{\pi^5} \\
& + \frac{135\,500\,316\,434\,432}{1\,550\,674\,125} \frac{\beta(8)}{\pi^7} - \frac{103\,451\,451\,588\,608}{30\,405\,375} \frac{\beta(10)}{\pi^9} \\
& + \frac{379\,218\,449\,924\,096}{3\,869\,775} \frac{\beta(12)}{\pi^{11}} - \frac{109\,796\,946\,608\,128}{51\,975} \frac{\beta(14)}{\pi^{13}} \\
& + \frac{4\,569\,845\,202\,944}{135} \frac{\beta(16)}{\pi^{15}} - \frac{371\,351\,462\,346\,752}{945} \frac{\beta(18)}{\pi^{17}} \\
& + \frac{15\,668\,040\,695\,808}{5} \frac{\beta(20)}{\pi^{19}} - 15\,393\,162\,788\,864 \frac{\beta(22)}{\pi^{21}} \\
& + 35\,184\,372\,088\,832 \frac{\beta(24)}{\pi^{23}}.
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\cos(50x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx = & -\frac{2}{25} \frac{\beta(2)}{\pi} + \frac{34\,340\,355\,272\,512}{1\,932\,541\,986\,375} \frac{\beta(4)}{\pi^3} - \frac{23\,718\,982\,614\,844\,928}{14\,704\,123\,809\,375} \frac{\beta(6)}{\pi^5} \\
& + \frac{591\,009\,192\,435\,712}{6\,249\,686\,625} \frac{\beta(8)}{\pi^7} - \frac{31\,002\,043\,628\,650\,496}{7\,753\,370\,625} \frac{\beta(10)}{\pi^9} \\
& + \frac{1\,477\,920\,107\,266\,048}{11\,609\,325} \frac{\beta(12)}{\pi^{11}} - \frac{50\,788\,618\,158\,997\,504}{16\,372\,125} \frac{\beta(14)}{\pi^{13}} \\
& + \frac{257\,856\,951\,549\,952}{4\,455} \frac{\beta(16)}{\pi^{15}} - \frac{11\,567\,094\,252\,437\,504}{14\,175} \frac{\beta(18)}{\pi^{17}} \\
& + \frac{2\,658\,344\,238\,055\,424}{315} \frac{\beta(20)}{\pi^{19}} - \frac{908\,196\,604\,542\,976}{15} \frac{\beta(22)}{\pi^{21}} \\
& + \frac{809\,240\,558\,043\,136}{3} \frac{\beta(24)}{\pi^{23}} - 562\,949\,953\,421\,312 \frac{\beta(26)}{\pi^{25}}.
\end{aligned}$$

At this stage, we do two very interesting observations. Firstly, the last coefficients $\eta_{n,n}$ are always integers. In fact, on replacing p by n and bearing in mind that $d_{0,1} = 1$, one has

$$\eta_{n,n} = (-1)^{n2} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \binom{4n-2}{2n-2k-2}.$$

And by following the same lines of reasoning sketched in the Paragraph §2 of Section 4, we deduce easily

$$\boxed{\eta_{n,n} = (-1)^n 2^{4n-3}}$$

Secondly and the most interesting, we observe among these integrals that the first coefficients may adhere the pattern $-\frac{2}{2n-1}$. More computations allow to conjecture that

$$\eta_{1,n} = -\frac{1}{2^{2n-3}} \sum_{m=0}^{n-1} \frac{d_{2m,n}}{(2n-2m-2)!} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \binom{4n-2}{2n-2k-2} (2k+1)^{2n-2m-2} = -\frac{2}{2n-1}$$

We start the proof by letting first of all

$$h_{m,n} := d_{2m,n} \quad \text{and} \quad s_{r,n} := \frac{1}{(2r)!} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \binom{4n-2}{2n-2k-2} (2k+1)^{2r}$$

. We get :

$$\begin{aligned} u_n &:= \sum_{m=0}^{n-1} \frac{d_{2m,n}}{(2n-2m-2)!} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \binom{4n-2}{2n-2k-2} (2k+1)^{2n-2m-2} \\ &= \sum_{m=0}^{n-1} h_{m,n} s_{n-m-1,n} \end{aligned}$$

This last formula for u_n holds *exactly* the form taken by coefficients of the Cauchy-product formula for two series. We read here that u_n is the coefficient of x^{n-1} in the Cauchy product of the series generated by the coefficients h_m and s_m . We consider then the series

$$H_n := \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} h_{m,n} x^m \quad \text{and} \quad S_n := \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} s_{m,n} x^m$$

We write then formally

$$u_n = [x^{n-1}] H_n(x) S_n(x)$$

Now

$$\sum_{m=0}^{\infty} d_{m,n} x^m = \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} d_{2m,n} x^{2m} = \frac{x^{2n}}{\sinh^{2n} x}$$

according to the definition of the coefficients $b_{m,n}$ and $d_{m,n}$ introduced in Paragraph §2 of Section 3.

We deduce

$$H_n(x) = \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} h_{m,n} x^m = \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} d_{2m,n} x^m = \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} d_{2m,n} (\sqrt{x})^{2m} = \frac{\sqrt{x}^{2n}}{\sinh^{2n} \sqrt{x}} = \frac{x^n}{\sinh^{2n} \sqrt{x}}$$

The closed form of S_n is derived in the same spirit :

$$\begin{aligned}
S_n &= \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} s_{r,n} x^r \\
&= \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2r)!} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \binom{4n-2}{2n-2k-2} (2k+1)^{2r} x^r \\
&= \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \binom{4n-2}{2n-2k-2} \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2r)!} (2k+1)^{2r} x^r \\
&= \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \binom{4n-2}{2n-2k-2} \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2r)!} ((2k+1)\sqrt{x})^{2r} \\
S_n &= \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \binom{4n-2}{2n-2k-2} \cosh((2k+1)\sqrt{x}).
\end{aligned}$$

And with *Proposition 2*, we can deduce easily

$$S_n = 2^{4n-4} \left(\left(\cosh \frac{\sqrt{x}}{2} \right)^{4n-2} + \left(\sinh \frac{\sqrt{x}}{2} \right)^{4n-2} \right)$$

We write much more formal

$$u_n = [x^{n-1}] \frac{x^n}{\sinh^{2n} \sqrt{x}} 2^{4n-4} \left(\left(\cosh \frac{\sqrt{x}}{2} \right)^{4n-2} + \left(\sinh \frac{\sqrt{x}}{2} \right)^{4n-2} \right)$$

Since $\sinh x = x \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{x^{2k}}{(2k+1)!}$, the Taylor expansion of $\left(\sinh \frac{\sqrt{x}}{2} \right)^{4n-2}$ begins by x^{2n-1} and those of $\frac{x^n}{\sinh^{2n} \sqrt{x}}$ starts by 1. As consequence the Taylor expansion of the product $\frac{x^n}{\sinh^{2n} \sqrt{x}} \left(\sinh \frac{\sqrt{x}}{2} \right)^{4n-2}$ starts by x^{2n-1} and does not affect any coefficients of lower powers at all and for instance, the desired coefficient of x^{n-1} in the whole expression of u_n .

Thus

$$u_n = [x^{n-1}] \frac{x^n}{\sinh^{2n} \sqrt{x}} 2^{4n-4} \left(\cosh \frac{\sqrt{x}}{2} \right)^{4n-2}$$

On using the Cauchy integral formula, u_n takes the form

$$\begin{aligned}
u_n &= \frac{1}{2\pi i} \oint_{|z|=\varepsilon} \frac{2^{4n-4} z^n \left(\cosh\left(\frac{\sqrt{z}}{2}\right) \right)^{4n-2}}{\sinh^{2n} \sqrt{z}} \frac{dz}{z^n} \\
&= \frac{2^{4n-4}}{2\pi i} \oint_{|z|=\varepsilon} \frac{\left(\cosh\left(\frac{\sqrt{z}}{2}\right) \right)^{4n-2}}{\sinh^{2n} \sqrt{z}} dz
\end{aligned}$$

where ε is a positive real number small enough to enclose only the pole $z = 0$. On performing the change of variable $z = t^2$, one gets

$$u_n = \frac{2^{4n-4}}{2\pi i} \oint_{|t|=\varepsilon^{1/2}} \frac{t (\cosh(\frac{t}{2}))^{4n-2}}{\sinh^{2n} t} dt$$

The duplication formula $\sinh t = 2 \cosh(\frac{t}{2}) \sinh(\frac{t}{2})$ leads to

$$u_n = \frac{2^{2n-3}}{2\pi i} \oint_{|t|=\varepsilon^{1/2}} t \frac{(\cosh(\frac{t}{2}))^{2n-2}}{(\sinh(\frac{t}{2}))^{2n}} dt$$

The substitution $t = 2 \operatorname{arctanh} x$ yields

$$u_n = \frac{2^{2n-2}}{2\pi i} \oint_{|x|=\varepsilon} \frac{\operatorname{arctanh} x}{x^{2n}} dx$$

Now, the Taylor expansion of $\operatorname{arctanh} x$ around $x = 0$ reads

$$\operatorname{arctanh} x = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{x^{2k+1}}{2k+1}$$

which implies

$$\frac{\operatorname{arctanh} x}{x^{2n}} = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{x^{2k+1-2n}}{2k+1}$$

The residue is exactly the coefficient of x^{-1} . The power -1 is reached for $2k+1-2n = -1$, which implies $k = n-1$. On using Cauchy's residue theorem, we conclude :

$$u_n = \frac{2^{2n-2}}{2\pi i} 2\pi i \frac{1}{2n-1} = \frac{2^{2n-2}}{2n-1}$$

Which concludes the proof. We write much more formal

$$\boxed{\forall n \in \mathbb{N}^*, \sum_{m=0}^{n-1} \frac{d_{2m,n}}{(2n-2m-2)!} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \binom{4n-2}{2n-2k-2} (2k+1)^{2n-2m-2} = \frac{2^{2n-2}}{2n-1}}$$

With help of *Proposition 6*, we express $\frac{\beta(2p)}{\pi^{2p-1}}$ as linear combination of $\int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\cos((4p-2)x)}{\ln \tan x} dx$

$$\forall n \in \mathbb{N}^*, \frac{\beta(2n)}{\pi^{2n-1}} = \sum_{p=1}^n \Psi_{p,n} \int_0^{\pi/4} \frac{\cos((4p-2)x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx$$

where

$$\Psi_{p,n} := \begin{cases} \frac{1}{\eta_{p,p}} & \text{if } n = p, \\ -\frac{1}{\eta_{n,n}} \sum_{k=p}^{n-1} \eta_{k,p} \cdot \Psi_{p,k} & \text{if } p \in \llbracket 1, n \rrbracket \end{cases}$$

where

$$\eta_{p,n} = \frac{(-1)^p}{2^{2n-2p-1}} \sum_{m=0}^{n-p} \frac{d_{2m,n}}{(2n-2m-2p)!} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \binom{4n-2}{2n-2k-2} (2k+1)^{2n-2m-2p}, \quad (p \in \llbracket 1, n \rrbracket).$$

with

$$\begin{cases} d_{0,n} := 1 \\ d_{j,n} := -\sum_{k=1}^j b_{k,n} d_{j-k,n} \end{cases}$$

and

$$b_{j,n} := \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } j \text{ is odd} \\ \frac{2}{4^n(j+2n)!} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} (-1)^k \binom{2n}{k} (2n-2k)^{j+2n} & \text{if } j \text{ is even} \end{cases}$$

Examples :

$$\frac{\beta(2)}{\pi} = -\frac{1}{2} \int_0^{\pi/4} \frac{\cos(2x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx.$$

$$\frac{\beta(4)}{\pi^3} = -\frac{1}{96} \int_0^{\pi/4} \frac{\cos(2x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx + \frac{1}{32} \int_0^{\pi/4} \frac{\cos(6x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx.$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\beta(6)}{\pi^5} &= -\frac{1}{3840} \int_0^{\pi/4} \frac{\cos(2x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx + \frac{1}{512} \int_0^{\pi/4} \frac{\cos(6x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx \\ &\quad - \frac{1}{512} \int_0^{\pi/4} \frac{\cos(10x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\beta(8)}{\pi^7} &= -\frac{17}{2580480} \int_0^{\pi/4} \frac{\cos(2x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx + \frac{11}{122880} \int_0^{\pi/4} \frac{\cos(6x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx \\ &\quad - \frac{5}{24576} \int_0^{\pi/4} \frac{\cos(10x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx + \frac{1}{8192} \int_0^{\pi/4} \frac{\cos(14x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{\beta(10)}{\pi^9} = & -\frac{31}{185\,794\,560} \int_0^{\pi/4} \frac{\cos(2x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx + \frac{11}{3\,096\,576} \int_0^{\pi/4} \frac{\cos(6x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx \\ & - \frac{1}{73\,728} \int_0^{\pi/4} \frac{\cos(10x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx + \frac{7}{393\,216} \int_0^{\pi/4} \frac{\cos(14x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx \\ & - \frac{1}{131\,072} \int_0^{\pi/4} \frac{\cos(18x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx.\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{\beta(12)}{\pi^{11}} = & -\frac{691}{163\,499\,212\,800} \int_0^{\pi/4} \frac{\cos(2x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx + \frac{641}{4\,954\,521\,600} \int_0^{\pi/4} \frac{\cos(6x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx \\ & - \frac{289}{396\,361\,728} \int_0^{\pi/4} \frac{\cos(10x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx + \frac{49}{31\,457\,280} \int_0^{\pi/4} \frac{\cos(14x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx \\ & - \frac{3}{2\,097\,152} \int_0^{\pi/4} \frac{\cos(18x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx + \frac{1}{2\,097\,152} \int_0^{\pi/4} \frac{\cos(22x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx.\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{\beta(14)}{\pi^{13}} = & -\frac{5\,461}{51\,011\,754\,393\,600} \int_0^{\pi/4} \frac{\cos(2x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx + \frac{133}{29\,896\,998\,912} \int_0^{\pi/4} \frac{\cos(6x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx \\ & - \frac{467}{13\,589\,544\,960} \int_0^{\pi/4} \frac{\cos(10x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx + \frac{239}{2\,264\,924\,160} \int_0^{\pi/4} \frac{\cos(14x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx \\ & - \frac{13}{83\,886\,080} \int_0^{\pi/4} \frac{\cos(18x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx + \frac{11}{100\,663\,296} \int_0^{\pi/4} \frac{\cos(22x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx \\ & - \frac{1}{33\,554\,432} \int_0^{\pi/4} \frac{\cos(26x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx.\end{aligned}$$

§3. A closed-form expression for $\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(2kx)}{x \cosh^n(x)} dx$

We recall the condition of convergence $2k < n$ in virtue of *Proposition 8*. *Proposition 1* allows to write the following formula

$$\sin(2kx) = \sum_{j=0}^{k-1} (-1)^j \binom{2k}{2j+1} \sin^{2j+1} x \cos^{2k-2j-1} x$$

Bearing in mind that $\sinh x = -i \sin(ix)$, one becomes

$$\sinh(2kx) = \sum_{j=0}^{k-1} \binom{2k}{2j+1} \sinh^{2j+1} x \cosh^{2k-2j-1} x.$$

Which becomes following after factoring out $\sinh x$

$$\sinh(2kx) = \sinh x \sum_{j=0}^{k-1} \binom{2k}{2j+1} \sinh^{2j} x \cosh^{2k-2j-1} x.$$

On recalling that $\sinh^2 x = \cosh^2 x - 1$, the term $\sinh^{2j} x$ is expanded further to yield

$$\sinh^{2j} x = \sum_{m=0}^j (-1)^m \binom{j}{m} \cosh^{2(j-m)} x.$$

As final result, one has :

$$\sinh(2kx) = \sinh x \sum_{j=0}^{k-1} \sum_{m=0}^j (-1)^m \binom{2k}{2j+1} \binom{j}{m} \cosh^{2k-2m-1} x.$$

We put it in the target integral :

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(2kx)}{x \cosh^n(x)} dx = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x \sum_{j=0}^{k-1} \sum_{m=0}^j (-1)^m \binom{2k}{2j+1} \binom{j}{m} \cosh^{2k-2m-1} x}{x \cosh^n(x)} dx$$

On swapping the big operators under condition of convergence, one becomes

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(2kx)}{x \cosh^n(x)} dx = \sum_{j=0}^{k-1} \sum_{m=0}^j (-1)^m \binom{2k}{2j+1} \binom{j}{m} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x \cosh^{2k-2m-1} x}{x \cosh^n(x)} dx$$

Which reads

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(2kx)}{x \cosh^n(x)} dx = \sum_{j=0}^{k-1} \sum_{m=0}^j (-1)^m \binom{2k}{2j+1} \binom{j}{m} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^{n-2k+2m+1}(x)} dx$$

Now, the integral $\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^{n-2k+2m+1}(x)} dx$ is quite known from previous sections and subsections. One reads immediately that $\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(2kx)}{x \cosh^n(x)} dx$ yields a \mathbb{Q} -linear combination of $\frac{\beta(2n)}{\pi^{2n-1}}$ if n is odd and a \mathbb{Q} -linear combination of $\frac{\zeta(2n+1)}{\pi^{2n}}$ if n is even.

On applying the last formula in conjunction of previous results, we have deduce the following formulae

$$\forall (n \geq 2, 1 \leq k \leq n-1)$$

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(2kx)}{x \cosh^{2n} x} dx = \sum_{p=1}^{n-1} \Theta_{p,k,n} \frac{\zeta(2p+1)}{\pi^{2p}},$$

$$\Theta_{p,k,n} := \sum_{j=0}^{k-1} \sum_{m=0}^j (-1)^m \binom{2k}{2j+1} \binom{j}{m} \alpha_{p,0,n-k+m},$$

where

$$\alpha_{p,k,n} = (-1)^{p+n+k} 4^{p+1} \left(1 - \frac{1}{2^{2p+1}}\right) \sum_{m=p}^n c_{2n-2m,n} \frac{(2k+1)^{2m-2p}}{(2m-2p)!}.$$

with

$$\begin{cases} c_{0,n} := 1 \\ c_{j,n} := - \sum_{k=1}^j a_{k,n} c_{j-k,n} \end{cases}$$

and

$$a_{j,n} := \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } j \text{ is odd} \\ \frac{1}{4^n (j+2n+1)!} \sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^k \binom{2n+1}{k} (2n-2k+1)^{j+2n+1} & \text{if } j \text{ is even} \end{cases}$$

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(2kx)}{x \cosh^{2n+1} x} dx = \sum_{p=1}^n Z_{p,k,n} \frac{\beta(2p)}{\pi^{2p-1}}, \quad n \in \mathbb{N}^*, 1 \leq k \leq n.$$

$$Z_{p,k,n} := \sum_{j=0}^{k-1} \sum_{m=0}^j (-1)^m \binom{2k}{2j+1} \binom{j}{m} f_{p,0,n-k+m+1}, \quad 1 \leq p \leq n.$$

where

$$f_{p,k,n} := (-1)^{n+k+p} 2^{2p+1} \sum_{m=0}^{n-p} \frac{d_{2m,n} (2k+1)^{2n-2m-2p}}{(2n-2m-2p)!}$$

with

$$\begin{cases} d_{0,n} := 1 \\ d_{j,n} := - \sum_{k=1}^j b_{k,n} d_{j-k,n} \end{cases}$$

and

$$b_{j,n} := \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } j \text{ is odd} \\ \frac{2}{4^n (j+2n)!} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} (-1)^k \binom{2n}{k} (2n-2k)^{j+2n} & \text{if } j \text{ is even} \end{cases}$$

The following examples instantiate the integral $\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(2kx)}{x \cosh^n(x)} dx$

For $n = 3$,

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(2x)}{x \cosh^3 x} dx = \frac{16 \beta(2)}{\pi}$$

For $n = 4$,

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(2x)}{x \cosh^4 x} dx = 28 \frac{\zeta(3)}{\pi^2}$$

For $n = 5$,

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(2x)}{x \cosh^5 x} dx = \frac{8 \beta(2)}{3\pi} + \frac{64 \beta(4)}{\pi^3}$$

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(4x)}{x \cosh^5 x} dx = \frac{176 \beta(2)}{3\pi} - \frac{128 \beta(4)}{\pi^3}$$

For $n = 6$

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(2x)}{x \cosh^6 x} dx = \frac{28 \zeta(3)}{3\pi^2} + \frac{124 \zeta(5)}{\pi^4}$$

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(4x)}{x \cosh^6 x} dx = \frac{280 \zeta(3)}{3\pi^2} - \frac{248 \zeta(5)}{\pi^4}$$

For $n = 7$,

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(2x)}{x \cosh^7 x} dx = \frac{6 \beta(2)}{5\pi} + \frac{32 \beta(4)}{\pi^3} + \frac{256 \beta(6)}{\pi^5}$$

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(4x)}{x \cosh^7 x} dx = \frac{124 \beta(2)}{15\pi} + \frac{192 \beta(4)}{\pi^3} - \frac{512 \beta(6)}{\pi^5}$$

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(6x)}{x \cosh^7 x} dx = \frac{3 \ 254 \beta(2)}{15\pi} - \frac{928 \beta(4)}{\pi^3} + \frac{768 \beta(6)}{\pi^5}$$

For $n = 8$,

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(2x)}{x \cosh^8 x} dx = \frac{224 \zeta(3)}{45\pi^2} + \frac{248 \zeta(5)}{3\pi^4} + \frac{508 \zeta(7)}{\pi^6}$$

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(4x)}{x \cosh^8 x} dx = \frac{1 \ 232 \zeta(3)}{45\pi^2} + \frac{992 \zeta(5)}{3\pi^4} - \frac{1 \ 016 \zeta(7)}{\pi^6}$$

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(6x)}{x \cosh^8 x} dx = \frac{1568 \zeta(3)}{5\pi^2} - \frac{1736 \zeta(5)}{\pi^4} + \frac{1524 \zeta(7)}{\pi^6}$$

For $n = 9$,

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(2x)}{x \cosh^9 x} dx = \frac{5 \beta(2)}{7\pi} + \frac{296 \beta(4)}{15\pi^3} + \frac{640 \beta(6)}{3\pi^5} + \frac{1024 \beta(8)}{\pi^7}$$

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(4x)}{x \cosh^9 x} dx = \frac{118 \beta(2)}{35\pi} + \frac{1328 \beta(4)}{15\pi^3} + \frac{1792 \beta(6)}{3\pi^5} - \frac{2048 \beta(8)}{\pi^7}$$

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(6x)}{x \cosh^9 x} dx = \frac{2689 \beta(2)}{105\pi} + \frac{2856 \beta(4)}{5\pi^3} - \frac{3456 \beta(6)}{\pi^5} + \frac{3072 \beta(8)}{\pi^7}$$

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(8x)}{x \cosh^9 x} dx = \frac{5692 \beta(2)}{7\pi} - \frac{74144 \beta(4)}{15\pi^3} + \frac{28160 \beta(6)}{3\pi^5} - \frac{4096 \beta(8)}{\pi^7}$$

For $n = 10$,

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(2x)}{x \cosh^{10} x} dx = \frac{16 \zeta(3)}{5\pi^2} + \frac{868 \zeta(5)}{15\pi^4} + \frac{508 \zeta(7)}{\pi^6} + \frac{2044 \zeta(9)}{\pi^8}$$

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(4x)}{x \cosh^{10} x} dx = \frac{608 \zeta(3)}{45\pi^2} + \frac{3224 \zeta(5)}{15\pi^4} + \frac{1016 \zeta(7)}{\pi^6} - \frac{4088 \zeta(9)}{\pi^8}$$

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(6x)}{x \cosh^{10} x} dx = \frac{3568 \zeta(3)}{45\pi^2} + \frac{12524 \zeta(5)}{15\pi^4} - \frac{6604 \zeta(7)}{\pi^6} + \frac{6132 \zeta(9)}{\pi^8}$$

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(8x)}{x \cosh^{10} x} dx = \frac{48704 \zeta(3)}{45\pi^2} - \frac{44144 \zeta(5)}{5\pi^4} + \frac{18288 \zeta(7)}{\pi^6} - \frac{8176 \zeta(9)}{\pi^8}$$

Of course, we could have provided explicit expressions for ζ or β as combination of the integral $\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(2x)}{x \cosh^n(x)} dx$, as we did for the previous ones. However, for the sake of brevity and since it gives rise to larger coefficients than those already considered, we have set aside further investigations on this one.

§4. The general integral $\int_0^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh^n(pz)}{z^m \cosh^q z} dz$

All the principal integrals considered in this work may, in fact, be subsumed under the more general form

$$\int_0^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh^n(pz)}{z^m \cosh^q(z)} dz.$$

A direct evaluation by means of contour integration is, however, not undertaken here for these following reasons: *the derivatives of $\sinh^n(pz)$ expand into a large and intricate sum, rendering the computation unwieldy and integrals that have been already evaluated are strong and exhibit enough patterns to formulate our conjectures.*

Instead, we propose a more practical approach. The evaluation can be reduced to three essential steps, relying on the subclass of integrals

$$\int_0^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(pz)}{z \cosh^q(z)} dz,$$

which formed the central object of study in this manuscript. For instance,

$$\int_0^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(pz)}{z \cosh^q(z)} dz,$$

yields, under conditions of convergence satisfied, a \mathbb{Q} -linear combination of $\frac{\zeta(2n+1)}{\pi^{2n}}$ if p and q have the same parity and a \mathbb{Q} -linear combination of $\frac{\beta(2n)}{\pi^{2n-1}}$ otherwise. Thus, for values of the parameters m, n, p, q ensuring convergence, one may rigorously proceed with the analysis by decomposing the general case into such simpler instances, especially in situations where a straightforward contour integration would be prohibitively cumbersome:

- perform $m - 1$ integrations by parts with the boundary term vanishing at each step,
- linearize the numerator of the resulting integral,
- conclude with the results provided by the previous study of

$$\int_0^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(pz)}{z \cosh^n(z)} dz,$$

We classify the parameter quadruples (m, n, p, q) by parity, yielding sixteen congruence classes in $(\mathbb{Z}/2\mathbb{Z})^4$, recorded in the table below. The symbols 0 and 1 denote, respectively, the residues of the parameters modulo 2 (even/odd). For each class, a check mark is placed in the column corresponding to the linear combination to which the integral reduces; cases that do not reduce to

$$\int_0^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh(pz)}{z \cosh^q(z)} dz,$$

are indicated in the column *Out of context*.

$I(m, n, p, q)$				$\sum_n \frac{\zeta(2n+1)}{\pi^{2n}}$	$\sum_n \frac{\beta(2n)}{\pi^{2n-1}}$	Out of context
m	n	p	q	ζ	β	
0	0	0	0	✓		
0	0	0	1		✓	
0	0	1	0		✓	
0	0	1	1	✓		
0	1	0	0			✓
0	1	0	1			✓
0	1	1	0			✓
0	1	1	1			✓
1	0	0	0			✓
1	0	0	1			✓
1	0	1	0			✓
1	0	1	1			✓
1	1	0	0	✓		
1	1	0	1		✓	
1	1	1	0		✓	
1	1	1	1	✓		

Conclusion : Within the reducible cases $m \equiv n \pmod{2}$, the parity of (p, q) alone selects the resulting constants:

$$\int_0^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh^n(pz)}{z^m \cosh^q(z)} dz \in \begin{cases} \text{span} \left\{ \sum_{k \geq 0} \zeta(2k+1) \pi^{-2k} \right\}, & \text{if } m \equiv n \pmod{2} \wedge p \equiv q \pmod{2}, \\ \text{span} \left\{ \sum_{k \geq 0} \beta(2k) \pi^{-(2k-1)} \right\}, & \text{if } m \equiv n \pmod{2} \wedge p \not\equiv q \pmod{2}. \end{cases}$$

The case $m \not\equiv n \pmod{2}$ will not be pursued further here. We merely note that it encompasses structures of independent interest, which may merit a separate, dedicated investigation. Of course, one could have provided an explicit formula for each case suited to the present context. Yet, once again, we chose to set aside such verbose expressions for the simple reason that the simpler integrals developed earlier already display sufficient structural richness to support our conjectures and guide future investigations.

§5. On the general integral $\int_0^1 \frac{x^{2n-1}}{\sqrt{1-x^2} \operatorname{arctanh} x} dx \quad (n \geq 1)$

The justification of the convergence is omitted due to the behavior at $x = 1$. We assume the convergence of this integral.

We perform the change $x = \tanh u$. So, we get

$$\int_0^1 \frac{x^{2n-1}}{\sqrt{1-x^2} \operatorname{arctanh} x} dx = \int_0^\infty \frac{\sinh^{2n-1} u}{u \cosh^{2n} u} du.$$

On linearizing the numerator with a result of *Proposition 2*, we obtain

$$\int_0^1 \frac{x^{2n-1}}{\sqrt{1-x^2} \operatorname{arctanh} x} dx = \frac{1}{4^{n-1}} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} (-1)^k \binom{2n-1}{k} \int_0^\infty \frac{\sinh((2n-1-2k)u)}{u \cosh^{2n} u} du.$$

The big operators being swapped because of the finite number of convergent terms. Now, we exhibit this deep formula for the target integral

$$\forall n \in \mathbb{N}^*, \int_0^1 \frac{x^{2n-1}}{\sqrt{1-x^2} \operatorname{arctanh} x} dx = \sum_{p=1}^n u_{p,n} \frac{\beta(2p)}{\pi^{2p-1}}$$

$$u_{p,n} := (-1)^{p-1} 4^{p-n+1} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \binom{2n-1}{n-1-k} \sum_{m=0}^{n-p} d_{2m,n} \frac{(2k+1)^{2n-2m-2p}}{(2n-2m-2p)!}$$

with

$$\begin{cases} d_{0,n} := 1 \\ d_{j,n} := - \sum_{k=1}^j b_{k,n} d_{j-k,n} \end{cases}$$

and

$$b_{j,n} := \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } j \text{ is odd} \\ \frac{2}{4^n(j+2n)!} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} (-1)^k \binom{2n}{k} (2n-2k)^{j+2n} & \text{if } j \text{ is even} \end{cases}$$

Examples

$$\int_0^1 \frac{x}{\sqrt{1-x^2} \operatorname{arctanh} x} dx = 4 \frac{\beta(2)}{\pi}.$$

$$\int_0^1 \frac{x^3}{\sqrt{1-x^2} \operatorname{arctanh} x} dx = \frac{10}{3} \frac{\beta(2)}{\pi} - 16 \frac{\beta(4)}{\pi^3}.$$

$$\int_0^1 \frac{x^5}{\sqrt{1-x^2} \operatorname{arctanh} x} dx = \frac{89}{30} \frac{\beta(2)}{\pi} - 24 \frac{\beta(4)}{\pi^3} + 64 \frac{\beta(6)}{\pi^5}.$$

$$\int_0^1 \frac{x^7}{\sqrt{1-x^2} \operatorname{arctanh} x} dx = \frac{381}{140} \frac{\beta(2)}{\pi} - \frac{434}{15} \frac{\beta(4)}{\pi^3} + \frac{416}{3} \frac{\beta(6)}{\pi^5} - 256 \frac{\beta(8)}{\pi^7}.$$

$$\int_0^1 \frac{x^9}{\sqrt{1-x^2} \operatorname{arctanh} x} dx = \frac{25\,609}{10\,080} \frac{\beta(2)}{\pi} - \frac{30\,539}{945} \frac{\beta(4)}{\pi^3} + \frac{1\,912}{9} \frac{\beta(6)}{\pi^5} - \frac{2\,176}{3} \frac{\beta(8)}{\pi^7} + 1\,024 \frac{\beta(10)}{\pi^9}.$$

$$\int_0^1 \frac{x^{11}}{\sqrt{1-x^2} \operatorname{arctanh} x} dx = \frac{106\,405}{44\,352} \frac{\beta(2)}{\pi} - \frac{187\,873}{5\,400} \frac{\beta(4)}{\pi^3} + \frac{53\,356}{189} \frac{\beta(6)}{\pi^5} - \frac{6\,752}{5} \frac{\beta(8)}{\pi^7} \\ + 3\,584 \frac{\beta(10)}{\pi^9} - 4\,096 \frac{\beta(12)}{\pi^{11}}$$

$$\int_0^1 \frac{x^{13}}{\sqrt{1-x^2} \operatorname{arctanh} x} dx = \frac{1\,755\,841}{768\,768} \frac{\beta(2)}{\pi} - \frac{2\,033\,677}{55\,440} \frac{\beta(4)}{\pi^3} + \frac{1\,970\,897}{5\,670} \frac{\beta(6)}{\pi^5} \\ - \frac{56\,336}{27} \frac{\beta(8)}{\pi^7} + \frac{39\,296}{5} \frac{\beta(10)}{\pi^9} - \frac{51\,200}{3} \frac{\beta(12)}{\pi^{11}} + 16\,384 \frac{\beta(14)}{\pi^{13}}.$$

$$\int_0^1 \frac{x^{15}}{\sqrt{1-x^2} \operatorname{arctanh} x} dx = \frac{1\,441\,481}{658\,944} \frac{\beta(2)}{\pi} - \frac{19\,258\,792\,097}{504\,504\,000} \frac{\beta(4)}{\pi^3} + \frac{21\,834\,349}{53\,460} \frac{\beta(6)}{\pi^5} \\ - \frac{5\,875\,526}{2\,025} \frac{\beta(8)}{\pi^7} + \frac{4\,365\,632}{315} \frac{\beta(10)}{\pi^9} - \frac{1\,938\,944}{45} \frac{\beta(12)}{\pi^{11}} \\ + \frac{237\,568}{3} \frac{\beta(14)}{\pi^{13}} - 65\,536 \frac{\beta(16)}{\pi^{15}}.$$

We also show and prove easily that

$$\boxed{u_{n,n} = (-1)^{n-1} 4^n}$$

. With help of linear algebra, we can find some rational coefficients $j_{p,n}$ such that

$$\frac{\beta(2n)}{\pi^{2n-1}} = \sum_{p=1}^n j_{p,n} \int_0^1 \frac{x^{2p-1}}{\sqrt{1-x^2} \operatorname{arctanh} x} dx$$

For instance

$$\frac{\beta(2)}{\pi} = \frac{1}{4} \int_0^1 \frac{x}{\sqrt{1-x^2} \operatorname{arctanh} x} dx.$$

$$\frac{\beta(4)}{\pi^3} = \frac{5}{96} \int_0^1 \frac{x}{\sqrt{1-x^2} \operatorname{arctanh} x} dx - \frac{1}{16} \int_0^1 \frac{x^3}{\sqrt{1-x^2} \operatorname{arctanh} x} dx.$$

$$\frac{\beta(6)}{\pi^5} = \frac{61}{7\,680} \int_0^1 \frac{x}{\sqrt{1-x^2} \operatorname{arctanh} x} dx - \frac{3}{128} \int_0^1 \frac{x^3}{\sqrt{1-x^2} \operatorname{arctanh} x} dx + \frac{1}{64} \int_0^1 \frac{x^5}{\sqrt{1-x^2} \operatorname{arctanh} x} dx.$$

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{\beta(8)}{\pi^7} &= \frac{277}{258\,048} \int_0^1 \frac{x}{\sqrt{1-x^2} \operatorname{arctanh} x} dx - \frac{173}{30\,720} \int_0^1 \frac{x^3}{\sqrt{1-x^2} \operatorname{arctanh} x} dx \\ &+ \frac{13}{1\,536} \int_0^1 \frac{x^5}{\sqrt{1-x^2} \operatorname{arctanh} x} dx - \frac{1}{256} \int_0^1 \frac{x^7}{\sqrt{1-x^2} \operatorname{arctanh} x} dx\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{\beta(10)}{\pi^9} &= \frac{50\,521}{371\,589\,120} \int_0^1 \frac{x}{\sqrt{1-x^2} \operatorname{arctanh} x} dx - \frac{3\,403}{3\,096\,576} \int_0^1 \frac{x^3}{\sqrt{1-x^2} \operatorname{arctanh} x} dx \\ &+ \frac{203}{73\,728} \int_0^1 \frac{x^5}{\sqrt{1-x^2} \operatorname{arctanh} x} dx - \frac{17}{6\,144} \int_0^1 \frac{x^7}{\sqrt{1-x^2} \operatorname{arctanh} x} dx \\ &+ \frac{1}{1\,024} \int_0^1 \frac{x^9}{\sqrt{1-x^2} \operatorname{arctanh} x} dx\end{aligned}$$

§6. Malmsten like integral for $\frac{\beta(2n)}{\pi^{2n-1}}$ ($n \geq 1$)

As shown in an earlier subsection,

$$\forall n \in \mathbb{N}^*, \frac{\beta(2n)}{\pi^{2n-1}} = \sum_{p=1}^n \xi_{p,n} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^{2p} x} dx$$

where $\xi_{p,n}$ are some rational coefficients.

We start from the integral $\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^{2p} x} dx$. On remarking that the integrand is an even function, we reduce the domain of integration to have

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^{2p} x} dx = 2 \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^{2p} x} dx$$

On performing the substitution $x = \ln \frac{1}{t}$, one becomes

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^{2p} x} dx = 2^{2p} \int_0^1 \frac{(1-t^2)t^{2p-2}}{(1+t^2)^{2p} \ln(\frac{1}{t})} dt = -2^{2p} \int_0^1 \frac{(1-t^2)t^{2p-2}}{(1+t^2)^{2p} \ln t} dt$$

Bearing in mind that the anti-derivative of $\frac{1}{x \ln x}$ is $\ln \ln \frac{1}{x}$, an integration by part follows in this manner :

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^{2p} x} dx = -2^{2p} \left[\ln \ln \frac{1}{t} \frac{(1-t^2)t^{2p-1}}{(1+t^2)^{2p}} \right]_{t=0}^{t=1} + 2^{2p} \int_0^1 \ln \ln \frac{1}{t} \frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{(1-t^2)t^{2p-1}}{(1+t^2)^{2p}} \right) dt.$$

Now, the boundary term vanishes in virtue of *Proposition 4*. The remainder staying is given as

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^{2p} x} dx = 2^{2p} \int_0^1 \ln \ln \frac{1}{t} \frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{(1-t^2)t^{2p-1}}{(1+t^2)^{2p}} \right) dt.$$

Putting back in the expression of $\beta(2n)$ yields

$$\frac{\beta(2n)}{\pi^{2n-1}} = \sum_{p=1}^n \xi_{p,n} 2^{2p} \int_0^1 \ln \ln \frac{1}{t} \frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{(1-t^2)t^{2p-1}}{(1+t^2)^{2p}} \right) dt$$

On swapping the summation and integration operators since the sum is finite, one gets

$$\frac{\beta(2n)}{\pi^{2n-1}} = \int_0^1 \ln \ln \frac{1}{t} \sum_{p=1}^n \xi_{p,n} 2^{2p} \frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{(1-t^2)t^{2p-1}}{(1+t^2)^{2p}} \right) dt$$

And bearing in mind that the sum of derivatives is the derivative of the sum, we become

$$\frac{\beta(2n)}{\pi^{2n-1}} = \int_0^1 \ln \ln \frac{1}{t} \frac{d}{dt} \left(\sum_{p=1}^n \xi_{p,n} 2^{2p} \frac{(1-t^2)t^{2p-1}}{(1+t^2)^{2p}} \right) dt$$

Although the computation of such derivatives becomes increasingly tedious for large values of n , we have nevertheless evaluated the first few explicitly. By applying the final formula in conjunction with the coefficients $\xi_{p,n}$ as defined above, we arrive at the following conclusion:

$$\frac{\beta(2)}{\pi} = \int_0^1 \frac{u^4 - 6u^2 + 1}{2(1+u^2)^3} \ln \ln \frac{1}{u} du$$

$$\frac{\beta(4)}{\pi^3} = \int_0^1 \frac{-u^8 + 76u^6 - 230u^4 + 76u^2 - 1}{48(1+u^2)^5} \ln \ln \frac{1}{u} du$$

$$\frac{\beta(6)}{\pi^5} = \int_0^1 \frac{u^{12} - 722u^{10} + 10\,543u^8 - 23\,548u^6 + 10\,543u^4 - 722u^2 + 1}{3\,840(1+u^2)^7} \ln \ln \frac{1}{u} du$$

$$\frac{\beta(8)}{\pi^7} = \int_0^1 \frac{-u^{16} + 6\,552u^{14} - 331\,612u^{12} + 2\,485\,288u^{10} - 4\,675\,014u^8 + 2\,485\,288u^6 - 331\,612u^4 + 6\,552u^2 - 1}{645\,120(1+u^2)^9} \ln \ln \frac{1}{u} du$$

The first integral is a result attributed originally to Victor Adamchick [21] and was rediscovered by Blagouchine [1], since the three remaining ones seem to be new and to have never been addressed earlier in the literature. And like Malmsten's integrals for $\frac{\zeta(2n+1)}{\pi^{2n}}$, one sees that these $\ln \ln$ kernel integrals follow some pattern too. Although not easy to recognize by a trivial or classical formula, the coefficients involved in the numerators of these integrals are in fact *Eulerian numbers of type B* [22][23][24] and usually denoted by $B_{n,k}$ in the literature. But, in order to avoid any confusion with the Bernoulli numbers, we adopt the notation $\left\langle n \right\rangle_k^B$. These numbers build the sequence A060187 of the OEIS.

We conjecture then following :

$$\frac{\beta(2n)}{\pi^{2n-1}} = a_n \int_0^1 P_{2n}(-x^2) \ln \ln \frac{1}{x} dx$$

where $P_n(x) := \frac{1}{(1-x)^{n+1}} \sum_{k=0}^n \langle n \rangle_k^B x^k$ and a_n is a rational coefficient.

We find a series expansion for P_n by recalling this identity coming in calculus, combinatorics and generating functions[3][25][26] :

$$\frac{1}{(1-x)^{n+1}} = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \binom{n+k}{n} x^k \quad |x| < 1, n \in \mathbb{N} \quad (1)$$

And since $\langle n \rangle_k^B = 0$ if $k > n$, then we extend the sum to an series

$$\sum_{k=0}^n \langle n \rangle_k^B x^k = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \langle n \rangle_k^B x^k \quad (2)$$

With the Cauchy-product formula, we multiply the series to get:

$$P_n(x) = \left(\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \langle n \rangle_k^B x^k \right) \left(\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \binom{n+k}{n} x^k \right) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \left(\sum_{l=0}^k \binom{n+k-l}{n} \langle n \rangle_l^B \right) x^k$$

Let $L_{n,k} := \sum_{l=0}^k \binom{n+k-l}{n} \langle n \rangle_l^B$ and let expand the sum up to n like follow :

$$L_{n,k} = \sum_{l=0}^n \binom{n+k-l}{n} \langle n \rangle_l^B - \sum_{l=k+1}^n \binom{n+k-l}{n} \langle n \rangle_l^B$$

Brenti [24] and Bagno, Garber, and Novick [23] have shown that the first sum evaluates to $(2k+1)^n$. Formally, they prove that

$$\boxed{\sum_{l=0}^n \binom{n+k-l}{n} \langle n \rangle_l^B = (2k+1)^n.}$$

This identity is known in the literature as the *Worpitzky-type identity for Eulerian numbers of type B*. The second sum in the expression of $L_{n,k}$ vanishes due to the properties of the binomial coefficients. Specifically, the binomial coefficient is nonzero only when $n+k-l \geq n$, which implies $k \geq l$. However, in the second sum, the index l ranges from $k+1$ to n , which violates this condition. Therefore, the entire second sum evaluates to zero.

As consequence,

$$P_n(x) := \frac{1}{(1-x)^{n+1}} \sum_{k=0}^n \langle n \rangle_k^B x^k = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (2k+1)^n x^k$$

The Malmsten's integral becomes

$$\int_0^1 P_{2n}(-x^2) \ln \ln \frac{1}{x} dx = \int_0^1 \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (-1)^k (2k+1)^{2n} x^{2k} \ln \ln \frac{1}{x} dx = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (-1)^k (2k+1)^{2n} \int_0^1 x^{2k} \ln \ln \frac{1}{x} dx$$

The interchange of summation and integration being assumed as correct. On making use of *Proposition 5*, we get

$$\int_0^1 x^{2k} \ln \ln \frac{1}{x} dx = -\frac{\gamma + \ln(2k+1)}{2k+1}$$

We become

$$\int_0^1 P_{2n}(-x^2) \ln \ln \frac{1}{x} dx = -\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (-1)^k (2k+1)^{2n} \frac{\gamma + \ln(2k+1)}{2k+1}$$

Which reads

$$\int_0^1 P_{2n}(-x^2) \ln \ln \frac{1}{x} dx = -\gamma \underbrace{\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (-1)^k (2k+1)^{2n-1}}_{\beta(1-2n)} - \underbrace{\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (-1)^k (2k+1)^{2n} \frac{\ln(2k+1)}{2k+1}}_{\beta'(1-2n)}$$

One reads easily from the functional equation of β that $\beta(1-2n) = 0$. The value of $\beta'(1-2n)$ follows from *Proposition 10*.

We conclude

$$\int_0^1 P_{2n}(-x^2) \ln \ln \frac{1}{x} dx = \beta'(1-2n) = (-1)^{n+1} \frac{2^{2n-1} (2n-1)!}{\pi^{2n-1}} \beta(2n)$$

And we prove easily from the series expansion that

$$P_{2n}(-x^2) = \frac{\operatorname{Im}[\operatorname{Li}_{-2n}(ix)]}{x}, \quad n \in \mathbb{N}, x \in \mathbb{R}, |x| < 1.$$

We extend as consequence the Malmsten's integral given by Adamchick to all n

$$\forall n \in \mathbb{N}^*, \quad \int_0^1 \frac{\operatorname{Im}[\operatorname{Li}_{-2n}(ix)]}{x} \ln \ln \frac{1}{x} dx = (-1)^{n+1} \frac{2^{2n-1} (2n-1)!}{\pi^{2n-1}} \beta(2n)$$

§7. *B*-types and double integrals for $\frac{\beta(2n)}{\pi^{2n-1}}$

In the previous section, we have proven that

$$\int_0^1 P_{2n}(-x^2) \ln \ln \frac{1}{x} dx = (-1)^{n+1} \frac{2^{2n-1}(2n-1)!}{\pi^{2n-1}} \beta(2n)$$

$$\text{where } P_n(x) := \frac{1}{(1-x)^{n+1}} \sum_{k=0}^n \langle n \rangle_k^B x^k$$

And we show easily with the form given by the polylogarithm that

$$\int P_{2n}(-x^2) dx = x P_{2n-1}(-x^2), \quad n \geq 1.$$

By enjoying the symmetry of the *B* numbers, we deduce

$$P_{2n-1}(-x^2) = \frac{1}{(1+x^2)^{2n}} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} (-1)^k \langle 2n-1 \rangle_k^B (x^{2k} - x^{4n-2-2k})$$

An integration by parts yields

$$\left[x P_{2n-1}(-x^2) \ln \ln \frac{1}{x} \right]_0^1 - \int_0^1 x P_{2n-1}(-x^2) \frac{1}{x \ln x} dx = (-1)^{n+1} \frac{2^{2n-1}(2n-1)!}{\pi^{2n-1}} \beta(2n)$$

The boundary term vanishes in virtue of *Proposition 4*. It remains

$$- \int_0^1 P_{2n-1}(-x^2) \frac{1}{\ln x} dx = (-1)^{n+1} \frac{2^{2n-1}(2n-1)!}{\pi^{2n-1}} \beta(2n)$$

Which reads

$$- \int_0^1 \frac{1}{(1+x^2)^{2n}} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} (-1)^k \langle 2n-1 \rangle_k^B (x^{2k} - x^{4n-2-2k}) \frac{1}{\ln x} dx = (-1)^{n+1} \frac{2^{2n-1}(2n-1)!}{\pi^{2n-1}} \beta(2n)$$

On swapping the big operators

$$\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} (-1)^k \langle 2n-1 \rangle_k^B \int_0^1 \frac{x^{2k} - x^{4n-2-2k}}{(1+x^2)^{2n} \ln x} dx = (-1)^n \frac{2^{2n-1}(2n-1)!}{\pi^{2n-1}} \beta(2n)$$

The integral $\int_0^1 \frac{x^{2k} - x^{4n-2-2k}}{(1+x^2)^{2n} \ln x} dx$ is evaluated by *Proposition 9*

It follows

$$\forall n \in \mathbb{N}^*,$$

$$\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} (-1)^k \left\langle \begin{matrix} 2n-1 \\ k \end{matrix} \right\rangle^B \int_{k+\frac{1}{2}}^{2n-k-\frac{1}{2}} B\left(\frac{1}{2}; s, 2n-s\right) ds = (-1)^{n+1} \frac{2^{2n-1} (2n-1)!}{\pi^{2n-1}} \beta(2n)$$

$$\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} (-1)^k \left\langle \begin{matrix} 2n-1 \\ k \end{matrix} \right\rangle^B \int_{k+\frac{1}{2}}^{2n-k-\frac{1}{2}} \int_0^{1/2} t^{s-1} (1-t)^{2n-s-1} dt ds = (-1)^{n+1} \frac{2^{2n-1} (2n-1)!}{\pi^{2n-1}} \beta(2n)$$

§8. Another non trivial function f_n vanishing at all nonzero integers less than n

The derivation of the Malmsten-like formula for $\frac{\beta(2n)}{\pi^{2n-1}}$ lacks rigor due a single fact : *a strong and rigorous justification of the operators swap \sum and \int has been omitted.* Let's us sate right away, such a justification is much more complicated to explain for us than thought. Yet since it is hard to explain it fully, we provide another proof of the $\ln \ln 1/x$ -kernel integral by relying on the derivation from previous results.

On assuming the correctness of the first proof, we have (full derivation is given in the previous Paragraph §6)

$$\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} (-1)^k \left\langle \begin{matrix} 2n-1 \\ k \end{matrix} \right\rangle^B \int_0^1 \frac{x^{2k} - x^{4n-2-2k}}{(1+x^2)^{2n} \ln x} dx = (-1)^n \frac{2^{2n-1} (2n-1)!}{\pi^{2n-1}} \beta(2n)$$

On performing the change of variable $x = e^{-u}$, we get

$$\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} (-1)^k \left\langle \begin{matrix} 2n-1 \\ k \end{matrix} \right\rangle^B 2^{1-2n} \int_0^\infty \frac{\sinh((2n-1-2k)u)}{u \cosh^{2n} u} du = (-1)^n \frac{2^{2n-1} (2n-1)!}{\pi^{2n-1}} \beta(2n)$$

Which implies

$$\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} (-1)^k \left\langle \begin{matrix} 2n-1 \\ k \end{matrix} \right\rangle^B 2^{1-2n} \frac{1}{2} \sum_{p=1}^n f_{p,n-1-k,n} \frac{\beta(2p)}{\pi^{2p-1}} = (-1)^n \frac{2^{2n-1} (2n-1)!}{\pi^{2n-1}} \beta(2n)$$

We deduce from the definition of the coefficients $f_{p,k,n}$ (See Section 5, Paragraph §1) this equality

$$\sum_{m=0}^{n-p} \frac{d_{2m,n}}{(2n-2m-2p)!} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \left\langle \begin{matrix} 2n-1 \\ k \end{matrix} \right\rangle^B (2n-1-2k)^{2n-2m-2p} = \begin{cases} 0, & p \in \llbracket 1, n-1 \rrbracket, \\ 2^{2n-2} (2n-1)!, & p = n. \end{cases}$$

As conclusion, one may prove the general Malmsten's integral for $\frac{\beta(2p)}{\pi^{2p-1}}$ in a rigorous way independently of the summation and integration interchange by providing a proof of the last equality. The case $p = n$ is trivial and is deduced from $\sum_{k=0}^n \left\langle n \atop k \right\rangle^B = 2^n(n)!$ [24] and from the symmetry of Eulerian numbers by splitting the sum into two and manipulating the second. The case $p \in \llbracket 1, n-1 \rrbracket$ is proven with advanced tricks as follow.

We let

$$a_{p,n} := \sum_{m=0}^{n-p} \frac{d_{2m,n}}{(2n-2m-2p)!} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \left\langle 2n-1 \atop k \right\rangle^B (2n-1-2k)^{2n-2m}$$

On letting

$$h_{m,n} := d_{2m,n} \quad \text{and} \quad t_{r,n} := \frac{1}{(2r)!} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \left\langle 2n-1 \atop k \right\rangle^B (2n-1-2k)^{2r}$$

We become

$$a_{p,n} = \sum_{m=0}^{n-p} h_{m,n} t_{n-m-p,n}$$

This last expression $a_{p,n}$ is exactly the form of coefficients arising in the Cauchy product formula. As consequence, $a_{p,n}$ is the coefficient of x^{n-p} appearing in the Cauchy product of the series generated by the coefficients $h_{m,n}$ and $t_{m,n}$. On considering

$$H_n(x) := \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} h_{m,n} x^m \quad \text{and} \quad T_n(x) := \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} t_{m,n} x^m$$

we formalize the writing of $a_{p,n}$ in following manner :

$$a_{p,n} = [x^{n-p}] H_n(x) T_n(x)$$

Now

$$\sum_{m=0}^{\infty} d_{m,n} x^m = \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} d_{2m,n} x^{2m} = \frac{x^{2n}}{\sinh^{2n} x}$$

according to the definition of the coefficients $b_{m,n}$ and $d_{m,n}$ introduced in Paragraph §2 of Section 3.

We deduce

$$H_n(x) = \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} h_{m,n} x^m = \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} d_{2m,n} x^m = \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} d_{2m,n} (\sqrt{x})^{2m} = \frac{\sqrt{x}^{2n}}{\sinh^{2n} \sqrt{x}} = \frac{x^n}{\sinh^{2n} \sqrt{x}}$$

The closed form of $T_n(x)$ being harder to find, is found by paying attention to the following steps

$$t_{r,n} := \frac{1}{(2r)!} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \left\langle \begin{matrix} 2n-1 \\ k \end{matrix} \right\rangle^B (2n-1-2k)^{2r}$$

$$T_n(x) := \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} t_{m,n} x^m$$

$$T_n(x) = \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{x^m}{(2m)!} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \left\langle \begin{matrix} 2n-1 \\ k \end{matrix} \right\rangle^B (2n-1-2k)^{2m}$$

$$= \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \left\langle \begin{matrix} 2n-1 \\ k \end{matrix} \right\rangle^B \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{((2n-1-2k)^2 x)^m}{(2m)!}$$

$$= \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \left\langle \begin{matrix} 2n-1 \\ k \end{matrix} \right\rangle^B \cosh(\sqrt{x}(2n-1-2k))$$

$$= \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \left\langle \begin{matrix} 2n-1 \\ k \end{matrix} \right\rangle^B \cosh((2n-1-2k)\sqrt{x})$$

$$T_n(x) = \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \left\langle \begin{matrix} 2n-1 \\ k \end{matrix} \right\rangle^B \cosh((2n-1-2k)\sqrt{x})$$

On expanding cosh by exponential functions, we get

$$T_n(x) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \left\langle \begin{matrix} 2n-1 \\ k \end{matrix} \right\rangle^B \left(e^{(2n-1-2k)\sqrt{x}} + e^{-(2n-1-2k)\sqrt{x}} \right)$$

Which reads

$$T_n(x) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \left\langle \begin{matrix} 2n-1 \\ k \end{matrix} \right\rangle^B e^{(2n-1-2k)\sqrt{x}} + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \left\langle \begin{matrix} 2n-1 \\ k \end{matrix} \right\rangle^B e^{-(2n-1-2k)\sqrt{x}}$$

On re-indexing and reversing the order of summation of the second sum,

$$T_n(x) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \left\langle \begin{matrix} 2n-1 \\ k \end{matrix} \right\rangle^B e^{(2n-1-2k)\sqrt{x}} + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=n}^{2n-1} \left\langle \begin{matrix} 2n-1 \\ 2n-1-k \end{matrix} \right\rangle^B e^{(2n-1-2k)\sqrt{x}}$$

On recalling the symmetry of Eulerian numbers of type B, we merge into one

$$T_n(x) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=0}^{2n-1} \left\langle \begin{matrix} 2n-1 \\ k \end{matrix} \right\rangle^B e^{(2n-1-2k)\sqrt{x}}$$

We use the typ-B Eulerian Polynomials defined as

$$B_m(z) := \sum_{k=0}^m \langle m \rangle_k^B z^k.$$

As result,

$$T_n(x) = \frac{1}{2} e^{(2n-1)\sqrt{x}} B_{2n-1}(e^{-2\sqrt{x}}).$$

One has the generating function[28][29]

$$\sum_{m=0}^{\infty} B_m(z) \frac{t^m}{m!} = \frac{(1-z)e^{(1-z)t}}{1-ze^{2(1-z)t}}$$

We identify formally

$$\frac{B_{2n-1}(e^{-2\sqrt{x}})}{(2n-1)!}$$

as the coefficient of t^{2n-1} in the Taylor expansion around 0 of

$$\frac{(1-e^{-2\sqrt{x}})e^{(1-e^{-2\sqrt{x}})t}}{1-e^{-2\sqrt{x}}e^{2(1-e^{-2\sqrt{x}})t}}.$$

As consequence

$$T_n(x) = \frac{1}{2} e^{(2n-1)\sqrt{x}} (2n-1)! [t^{2n-1}] \frac{(1-e^{-2\sqrt{x}})e^{(1-e^{-2\sqrt{x}})t}}{1-e^{-2\sqrt{x}}e^{2(1-e^{-2\sqrt{x}})t}}.$$

The term $1-e^{-2\sqrt{x}}$ is factored out since it does not depends on t .

$$T_n(x) = \frac{1}{2} (1-e^{-2\sqrt{x}}) e^{(2n-1)\sqrt{x}} (2n-1)! [t^{2n-1}] \frac{e^{(1-e^{-2\sqrt{x}})t}}{1-e^{-2\sqrt{x}}e^{2(1-e^{-2\sqrt{x}})t}}.$$

On using the geometric series, we get

$$T_n(x) = \frac{1}{2} (1-e^{-2\sqrt{x}}) e^{(2n-1)\sqrt{x}} (2n-1)! [t^{2n-1}] \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} e^{-2m\sqrt{x}} e^{(1-e^{-2\sqrt{x}})(2m+1)t}.$$

The coefficients in series are linear, hence

$$T_n(x) = \frac{1}{2} (1-e^{-2\sqrt{x}}) e^{(2n-1)\sqrt{x}} (2n-1)! \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} e^{-2m\sqrt{x}} [t^{2n-1}] e^{(1-e^{-2\sqrt{x}})(2m+1)t}$$

The formula $[t^n]e^{\alpha t} = \frac{\alpha^n}{n!}$, yields

$$T_n(x) = \frac{1}{2} (1-e^{-2\sqrt{x}}) e^{(2n-1)\sqrt{x}} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} e^{-2m\sqrt{x}} ((1-e^{-2\sqrt{x}})(2m+1))^{2n-1}.$$

The term $1 - e^{-2\sqrt{x}}$ is independent of m and is factored out

$$T_n(x) = \frac{1}{2} (1 - e^{-2\sqrt{x}})^{2n} e^{(2n-1)\sqrt{x}} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} (2m+1)^{2n-1} e^{-2m\sqrt{x}}.$$

The outer term is treated to yield \sinh in the final expression as follow

$$T_n(x) = 2^{2n-1} \sinh^{2n}(\sqrt{x}) \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} (2m+1)^{2n-1} e^{-(2m+1)\sqrt{x}}.$$

On using the closed expressions of $H_n(x)$ and $T_n(x)$, $a_{p,n}$ takes the form

$$a_{p,n} = [x^{n-p}] \frac{x^n}{\sinh^{2n} \sqrt{x}} 2^{2n-1} e^{-\sqrt{x}} \sinh^{2n}(\sqrt{x}) \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} (2m+1)^{2n-1} e^{-2m\sqrt{x}}$$

On simplifying,

$$a_{p,n} = [x^{n-p}] x^n 2^{2n-1} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} (2m+1)^{2n-1} e^{-(2m+1)\sqrt{x}}$$

The formula $[x^y]x^z f(x) = [x^{y-z}]f(x)$ and the linearity of the coefficient yield

$$a_{p,n} = 2^{2n-1} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} (2m+1)^{2n-1} [x^{-p}] e^{-(2m+1)\sqrt{x}}$$

• **The case $p = 0$** : We can show easily with the formula of Taylor expansions that

$$[x^0] e^{-(2m+1)\sqrt{x}} = 1.$$

It implies then

$$a_{0,n} = 2^{2n-1} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} (2m+1)^{2n-1} = 2^{2n-1} (1 - 2^{2n-1}) \zeta(-(2n-1))$$

Relation between zeta at negative odd integers and Bernoulli numbers could be trivially deduced from the functional equation of ζ and the exact values of $\zeta(2n)$

$$\zeta(-(2n-1)) = -\frac{B_{2n}}{2n}.$$

Final compact formula

$$a_{0,n} = -\frac{2^{2n-1}(1 - 2^{2n-1})}{2n} B_{2n}.$$

- **The case** $p \in \llbracket 1, n-1 \rrbracket$: unfortunately, x^{-p} does not appear in the Taylor expansion of $e^{-(2m+1)\sqrt{x}}$ as $-p$ is strictly negative for $p \in \llbracket 1, n-1 \rrbracket$. As consequence $a_{p,n} = 0$. Which concludes the proof.

We write then more properly like a theorem

$$\forall n \in \mathbb{N}^*,$$

$$\text{Let } a_{p,n} := \sum_{m=0}^{n-p} \frac{d_{2m,n}}{(2n-2m-2p)!} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \left\langle \begin{matrix} 2n-1 \\ k \end{matrix} \right\rangle^B (2n-1-2k)^{2n-2m-2p}$$

$$\text{Then } a_{p,n} = \begin{cases} \frac{2^{2n-2}(2^{2n-1}-1)B_{2n}}{n}, & p=0, \\ 0, & p \in \llbracket 1, n-1 \rrbracket, \\ 2^{2n-2}(2n-1)!, & p=n. \end{cases}$$

Where B_{2n} denote Bernoulli numbers, $\left\langle \begin{matrix} 2n-1 \\ k \end{matrix} \right\rangle^B$ are Typ-B Eulerian numbers and $d_{2m,n}$ is the coefficient of x^{2m} in the Taylor expansion of $\frac{x^{2n}}{\sinh^{2n} x}$.

Another proof of this theorem

We use the theory of Mellin's transforms as in Paragraph §6 of Section 4. We have

$$a_{p,n} = 2^{2n-1} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} (2m+1)^{2n-1} [x^{-p}] e^{-(2m+1)\sqrt{x}}$$

On using the formula of coefficients through Mellin's transforms, one obtains

$$a_{p,n} = 2^{2n-1} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} (2m+1)^{2n-1} \text{Res}_{s=p} \mathcal{M} \left[e^{-(2m+1)\sqrt{x}} \right]$$

Which reads

$$a_{p,n} = 2^{2n-1} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} (2m+1)^{2n-1} \text{Res}_{s=p} \left(\int_0^{\infty} e^{-(2m+1)\sqrt{x}} x^{s-1} dx \right)$$

The substitution $t = (2m+1)\sqrt{x}$ yields

$$a_{p,n} = 2^{2n-1} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} (2m+1)^{2n-1} \text{Res}_{s=p} \left(\frac{2}{(2m+1)^{2s}} \int_0^{\infty} e^{-t} t^{2s-1} dt \right)$$

One recognizes the last integral as the Gamma function. As implication

$$\begin{aligned}
a_{p,n} &= 2^{2n-1} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} (2m+1)^{2n-1} \operatorname{Res}_{s=p} \left(\frac{2\Gamma(2s)}{(2m+1)^{2s}} \right) \\
&= \operatorname{Res}_{s=p} \left(2^{2n-1} \cdot 2\Gamma(2s) \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{(2m+1)^{2n-1}}{(2m+1)^{2s}} \right)
\end{aligned}$$

The last series is rewritten with the Riemann zeta function as follow

$$\boxed{a_{p,n} = \operatorname{Res}_{s=p} \left(2^{2n} \Gamma(2s) (1 - 2^{-(2s-2n+1)}) \zeta(2s - 2n + 1) \right)}$$

- **Case** $p = 0$

$\Gamma(2s)$ has a simple pole at $s = 0$ with Laurent expansion :

$$\Gamma(2s) = \frac{1}{2s} - \gamma + \dots$$

the residue of $\Gamma(2s)$ for $s = 0$ is then $\frac{1}{2}$. The term $(1 - 2^{-(2s-2n+1)}) \zeta(2s - 2n + 1)$ is regular and does not have any pole at all. As consequence

$$a_{0,n} = 2^{2n-1} (1 - 2^{2n-1}) \zeta(1 - 2n)$$

And on using the functional equation of ζ in combination with the exact values of $\zeta(2n)$, we conclude

$$a_{0,n} = - \frac{2^{2n-1} (1 - 2^{2n-1})}{2n} B_{2n}$$

- **Case** $p \in \llbracket 1, n-1 \rrbracket$

None of the functions $(1 - 2^{-(2s-2n+1)})$, $\zeta(2s-2n+1)$ and $\Gamma(2s)$ has a pole at $s = p$ when $p \in \llbracket 1, n-1 \rrbracket$. In the Mellin transform framework, only *simple* poles in s contribute residues. At $s = p \in \llbracket 1, n-1 \rrbracket$, what we see is not a *simple* pole of $\zeta(2s-2n+1)$ in s — the factor diverges to violently for every such p . The product $2^{2n-2s} \Gamma(2s+1) \zeta(2s-2n)$ does not show a *simple* pole structure here at $s = p$. The residue holds then a zero value in this case. Formally,

$$a_{p,n} = 0 \quad \text{if } p \in \llbracket 1, n-1 \rrbracket$$

- **Case** $p = n$

$\Gamma(2s)$ is regular with value $(2n-1)!$, $(1 - 2^{-(2s-2n+1)})$ is regular too with value $\frac{1}{2}$. But $\zeta(2s-2n+1)$ has a simple pole since $\zeta(1)$ is in fact the *harmonic series*. And Around $s = n$, one has indeed the Taylor expansion

$$\zeta(1 + 2(s-n)) = \frac{1}{2(s-n)} + \gamma + \dots$$

So, the residue is $\frac{1}{2}$. It follows

$$a_{n,n} = 2^{2n-2} (2n-1)!$$

§9. Properties and construction of functions f_n vanishing at all integers less than n

Throughout the document, we sometimes faced functions f_n vanishing at all integers less than n . This subsection gives more information about their construction and properties.

- Let $\phi : \mathbb{C} \mapsto \mathbb{C}$ be a function having no singularity at any integer less than a fix $n \in \mathbb{N}^*$. The function

$$\begin{aligned} f_n : \mathbb{C} &\mapsto \mathbb{C} \\ z &\mapsto \phi(z) \prod_{k=0}^{n-1} (z-k) \end{aligned}$$

vanishes $\forall k \in \llbracket 0, n-1 \rrbracket$

- Let $n \in \mathbb{N}^*$ and $\phi : \mathbb{C} \mapsto \mathbb{C}$ be a function having a *simple* zero at some $z_0 \in \mathbb{C}^*$. Then the function

$$\begin{aligned} f_n : \mathbb{C} &\mapsto \mathbb{C} \\ k &\mapsto \left. \frac{d^k}{dz^k} (\phi^n(z)) \right|_{z=z_0} \end{aligned}$$

vanishes $\forall k \in \llbracket 0, n-1 \rrbracket$

- Let $\phi : \mathbb{C} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ be a meromorphic function with a *simple zero* at some point $z_0 \in \mathbb{C}^*$. Fix $n \in \mathbb{N}^*$, and define the function

$$f_n(k) := \text{Res}_{z=z_0} \left(\frac{\phi(z)^n}{(z-z_0)^{k+1}} \right).$$

Then:

$$f_n(k) = 0 \quad \forall k \in \llbracket 0, n-1 \rrbracket.$$

6 Conjectures and Arithmetic Implications

§1. Conjectures related to the irrationality (respectively transcendence) of $\frac{\zeta(2n+1)}{\pi^{2n+1}}$

Since it has been proven that $\frac{\zeta(2n+1)}{\pi^{2n}} = \sum_{p=1}^n \chi_{p,n} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^{2p+1} x} dx$ with $\chi_{p,n} \in \mathbb{Q}$,

the irrationality of the numbers $\frac{\zeta(2n+1)}{\pi^{2n+1}}$ would follow from the following conjecture:

$$\pi \notin \text{Span}_{\mathbb{Q}} \left\{ \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^3 x} dx, \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^5 x} dx, \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^7 x} dx, \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^9 x} dx, \dots \right\}$$

Since it has been proven that $\frac{\zeta(2n+1)}{\pi^{2n}} = \sum_{p=1}^n s_{p,n} \int_0^1 \frac{x^{2p-1}}{\text{arctanh } x} dx$ with $s_{p,n} \in \mathbb{Q}$, the

irrationality of the numbers $\frac{\zeta(2n+1)}{\pi^{2n+1}}$ would follow from the following conjecture:

$$\pi \notin \text{Span}_{\mathbb{Q}} \left\{ \int_0^1 \frac{x}{\text{arctanh } x} dx, \int_0^1 \frac{x^3}{\text{arctanh } x} dx, \int_0^1 \frac{x^5}{\text{arctanh } x} dx, \int_0^1 \frac{x^7}{\text{arctanh } x} dx, \dots \right\}$$

We can go deeper with this statement : The irrationality of the numbers $\frac{\zeta(2n+1)}{\pi^{2n+1}}$ would be deduced from the following compact conjecture:

$$\forall P \in \mathbb{Z}[x] \setminus \{0\}, \quad \int_0^1 \frac{x P(x)}{\text{arctanh } x} dx \notin \pi \cdot \mathbb{Q}$$

On calling Λ_n the polynomial such that holds $\frac{\zeta(2n+1)}{\pi^{2n}} = \int_0^1 \frac{x \Lambda_n(x)}{\text{arctanh } x} dx$, we exhibit theses examples from the subsection §6 of Chapter 4:

$$\Lambda_1(x) = \frac{1}{7}.$$

$$\Lambda_2(x) = -\frac{1}{31} x^2 + \frac{2}{93}.$$

$$\Lambda_3(x) = \frac{1}{127} x^4 - \frac{4}{381} x^2 + \frac{17}{5715}.$$

$$\Lambda_4(x) = -\frac{1}{511} x^6 + \frac{2}{511} x^4 - \frac{6}{2555} x^2 + \frac{62}{160965}.$$

$$\Lambda_5(x) = \frac{1}{2047} x^8 - \frac{8}{6141} x^6 + \frac{37}{30705} x^4 - \frac{848}{1934415} x^2 + \frac{1382}{29016225}.$$

$$\Lambda_6(x) = -\frac{1}{8191} x^{10} + \frac{10}{24573} x^8 - \frac{188}{368595} x^6 + \frac{2266}{7740495} x^4 - \frac{8507}{116107425} x^2 + \frac{21844}{3831545025}.$$

$$\begin{aligned} \Lambda_7(x) &= \frac{1}{32767} x^{12} - \frac{4}{32767} x^{10} + \frac{19}{98301} x^8 - \frac{944}{6192963} x^6 \\ &+ \frac{1901}{30964815} x^4 - \frac{3868}{340612965} x^2 + \frac{929569}{1394810091675}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \Lambda_8(x) &= -\frac{1}{131071} x^{14} + \frac{14}{393213} x^{12} - \frac{134}{1966065} x^{10} + \frac{566}{8257473} x^8 \\ &- \frac{23782}{619310475} x^6 + \frac{79214}{6812415225} x^4 - \frac{46471426}{27896840346375} x^2 + \frac{6404582}{83690521039125}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \Lambda_9(x) &= \frac{1}{524287} x^{16} - \frac{16}{1572861} x^{14} + \frac{539}{23592915} x^{12} - \frac{13856}{495451215} x^{10} \\ &+ \frac{29948}{1486353645} x^8 - \frac{420832}{49049670285} x^6 + \frac{136750052}{6695279939025} x^4 \\ &- \frac{47060768}{200858399817075} x^2 + \frac{443861162}{51218891953354125}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \Lambda_{10}(x) &= -\frac{1}{2097151} x^{18} + \frac{6}{2097151} x^{16} - \frac{232}{31457265} x^{14} + \frac{3014}{283115385} x^{12} \\ &- \frac{13297}{1415576925} x^{10} + \frac{48424}{9342807705} x^8 - \frac{335177296}{191293987759875} x^6 \\ &+ \frac{64742312}{191293987759875} x^4 - \frac{518299498}{162599889595875} x^2 + \frac{18888466084}{19463206784628481875}. \end{aligned}$$

Since it has been proven that $\frac{\zeta(2n+1)}{\pi^{2n}} = \sum_{p=1}^n r_{p,n} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin(4px)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx$, with $r_{p,n} \in \mathbb{Q}$, the irrationality of the numbers $\frac{\zeta(2n+1)}{\pi^{2n+1}}$ follows from this conjecture :

$$\pi \notin \text{Span}_{\mathbb{Q}} \left\{ \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin(4x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx, \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin(8x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx, \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin(12x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx, \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin(16x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx, \dots \right\}$$

Since it has been proven that $\frac{\zeta(2n+1)}{\pi^{2n}} = \sum_{p=1}^n \Phi_{p,n} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{\tanh^{p+1} x}{x^{p+1}} dx$, with $\Phi_{p,n} \in \mathbb{Q}$, the irrationality of the numbers $\frac{\zeta(2n+1)}{\pi^{2n+1}}$ would follow from this conjecture :

$$\pi \notin \text{Span}_{\mathbb{Q}} \left\{ \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{\tanh^2 x}{x^2} dx, \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{\tanh^3 x}{x^3} dx, \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{\tanh^4 x}{x^4} dx, \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{\tanh^5 x}{x^5} dx, \dots \right\}$$

Since it has been proven that $\frac{\zeta(2n+1)}{\pi^{2n}} = \sum_{p=1}^n H_{p,n} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{\tanh^{2p} x}{x^2} dx$, with $H_{p,n} \in \mathbb{Q}$, the irrationality of the numbers $\frac{\zeta(2n+1)}{\pi^{2n+1}}$ would follow from this conjecture :

$$\pi \notin \text{Span}_{\mathbb{Q}} \left\{ \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{\tanh^2 x}{x^2} dx, \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{\tanh^4 x}{x^2} dx, \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{\tanh^6 x}{x^2} dx, \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{\tanh^8 x}{x^2} dx, \dots \right\}$$

The irrationality of $\frac{\zeta(2n+1)}{\pi^{2n+1}}$ is **equivalent** to this conjecture :

The set

$$\left\{ \pi, \int_0^1 \frac{\text{Li}_{-2n-1}(-x^2) \ln \ln \frac{1}{x}}{x} dx \right\}$$

is linearly independent over \mathbb{Z} with $n \geq 1$

Only the irrationality of the number $\frac{\zeta(3)}{\pi^3}$ follows from this conjecture :

The set

$$\left\{ \pi, \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin(4nx)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx \right\}$$

is linearly independent over \mathbb{Z} when $n \geq 1$

The irrationality of the number $\frac{\zeta(3)}{\pi^3}$ is **equivalent** to this conjecture :

The set

$$\left\{ \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin(4x)}{7 \cos(2x) + \cos(6x)} dx, \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin(4x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx \right\}$$

is linearly independent over \mathbb{Z}

Proof:

$$\begin{aligned} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} \frac{x \sin x \cos x}{\sin^4 x + \cos^4 x} dx &= \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} \frac{x \sin 2x}{2 - \sin^2 2x} dx \\ &= \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} \frac{x \sqrt{1 - \cos^2 2x}}{1 + \cos^2 2x} dx \\ &= \frac{1}{4} \int_{-1}^1 \frac{\arccos x}{1 + x^2} dx \\ &= \frac{1}{4} \left([\arccos x \arctan x]_{-1}^1 - \underbrace{\int_{-1}^1 \frac{\arctan x}{\sqrt{1 - x^2}} dx}_0 \right) \\ &= \frac{\pi^2}{16} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} \frac{x \sin x \cos x}{\sin^4 x + \cos^4 x} dx = \frac{\pi^2}{16} &\Rightarrow \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} \frac{\sin x \cos x}{\sin^4 x + \cos^4 x} dx = \frac{\pi}{4} \\ &\Rightarrow \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} \frac{\sin x \cos x}{\sin^4 x + \cos^4 x} dx = \frac{\pi}{4} \\ &\Rightarrow \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin x \cos x}{\sin^4 x + \cos^4 x} dx = \frac{\pi}{8} \\ &\Rightarrow \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin 4x}{\cos(2x) (\sin^4 x + \cos^4 x)} dx = \frac{\pi}{4} \\ &\Rightarrow \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin 4x}{7 \cos(2x) + \cos(6x)} dx = \frac{\pi}{16} (Q.E.D) \end{aligned}$$

When we recall the Fourier series $\ln(\tan x) = -2 \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{\cos 2(2k+1)x}{2k+1}$, we have all reasons to think that there does not exist a \mathbb{Z} -linear dependance between these two integrals having the same bounds of integration and the same numerator at the integrand. The existence of such a dependance would **"probably"** implies that it is possible to transform one integral to another with *integration by parts* or *interval separating*. A change of variable would change

the bounds of both integrals. Furthermore, how to transform an integral having a finite denominator to an integral having an infinite one, with finite steps of *integration by parts* or *interval separating* ? When we recall the Fourier series $\ln(\tan x) = -2 \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{\cos 2(2k+1)x}{2k+1}$, we have all reasons to think that there does not exist a \mathbb{Z} -linear dependance between these two integrals having the same bounds of integration and the same numerator at the integrand. The existence of such a dependance would **"probably"** implies that it is possible to transform one integral to another with *integration by parts* or *interval separating*. A change of variable would change the bounds of both integrals. Furthermore, how to transform an integral having a finite denominator to an integral having an infinite one, with finite steps of *integration by parts* or *interval separating* ? When we recall the Fourier series $\ln(\tan x) = -2 \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} \frac{\cos 2(2k+1)x}{2k+1}$, we have all reasons to think that there does not exist a \mathbb{Z} -linear dependance between these two integrals having the same bounds of integration and the same numerator at the integrand. The existence of such a dependance would **"probably"** implies that it is possible to transform one integral to another with *integration by parts* or *interval separating*. A change of variable would change the bounds of both integrals. Furthermore, how to transform an integral having a finite denominator to an integral having an infinite one, with finite steps of *integration by parts* or *interval separating* ? But these observations do not replace a strong proof.

From the integrals in the last conjecture, one proves $\int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} \frac{x \sin(4x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx = -\frac{7\zeta(3)}{2\pi}$ and

$$\int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} \frac{x \sin 4x}{7 \cos(2x) + \cos(6x)} dx = \frac{\pi^2}{32}$$

by making the substitution $u = \frac{\pi}{2} - x$ and enjoying the symmetry of the integrands on $[0, \frac{\pi}{2}]$ at $x = \frac{\pi}{4}$. We deduce that the irrationality of the number $\frac{\zeta(3)}{\pi^3}$ is **equivalent** to this conjecture :

The set

$$\left\{ \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} \frac{x \sin(4x)}{7 \cos(2x) + \cos(6x)} dx, \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} \frac{x \sin(4x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx \right\}$$

is linearly independent over \mathbb{Z}

As shown before, these two integrals have the same bounds of integration, the same numerator but only denominators are different. In virtue of the Fourier series of $\ln(\tan x)$, one denominator is finite whereas the other is infinite (in terms of trigonometric functions). A \mathbb{Z} -linear dependance between the two would be surprising.

Observation 1 : It is highly probable, that $\exists \varepsilon \in (0, \frac{\pi}{4})$, such that

$$\forall n \in \mathbb{N}^*, \frac{\pi}{4} - \varepsilon < \left| \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin 4nx}{\ln(\tan x)} dx \right| < \frac{\pi}{4} + \varepsilon$$

Observation 2 : The integrals

$$I_n := \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin(4nx)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx, \quad J_n := \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\cos((4n-2)x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx$$

are well-defined only when $n \in \mathbb{Z}$. Their domains of definition cannot be extended beyond the integers. Typically, functions defined solely on the integers arise from the use of the floor function, finite summations with integer bounds, or parity arguments. In contrast, the functions I_n and J_n depend exclusively on analytic integral expressions and thus exhibit the unusual property of being intrinsically restricted to integer arguments without recourse to such discrete constructs.

Observation 3 : One proves that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin(4(2n+1)x)}{\ln(\tan x)} = -\frac{\pi}{4}$. An equality

$$p \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin(4(2n+1)x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx + q \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin(4x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx = 0$$

(p, q integers) is hardly to be expected.

Observation 4 : It's highly probable that

$$\forall n \geq 5, \frac{3}{2n\pi} < \frac{7\zeta(3)}{\pi^2} + \frac{\pi}{4n} \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} f\left(\frac{k\pi}{4n}\right) < \frac{5}{2n\pi}$$

where $f(x) := \frac{\sin(4x)}{\ln(\tan x)}$

§2. Conjectures implying the irrationality(respectively transcendence) of $\frac{\beta(2n)}{\pi^{2n}}$

The irrationality of $\frac{\beta(2n)}{\pi^{2n}}$ is *equivalent* to this conjecture :

The set

$$\left\{ \pi, \int_0^1 \frac{\text{Im}[\text{Li}_{-2n}(ix)]}{x} \ln \ln \frac{1}{x} dx \right\}$$

is linearly independent over \mathbb{Z} with $n \geq 1$

Because we sketched a strong proof that $\frac{\beta(2n)}{\pi^{2n-1}} = \sum_{p=1}^n \xi_{p,n} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^{2p} x} dx$ with $\xi_{p,n} \in \mathbb{Q}$, the irrationality of the numbers $\frac{\beta(2n)}{\pi^{2n}}$ would be deduced from the following conjecture:

$$\pi \notin \text{Span}_{\mathbb{Q}} \left\{ \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^2 x} dx, \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^4 x} dx, \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^6 x} dx, \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^8 x} dx, \dots \right\}$$

Since we argued that $\frac{\beta(2n)}{\pi^{2n-1}} = \sum_{p=1}^n j_{p,n} \int_0^1 \frac{x^{2p-1}}{\sqrt{1-x^2} \operatorname{arctanh} x} dx$ with $j_{p,n} \in \mathbb{Q}$, the irrationality of the numbers $\frac{\beta(2n)}{\pi^{2n}}$ would be deduced from the following conjecture:

$$\pi \notin \text{Span}_{\mathbb{Q}} \left\{ \int_0^1 \frac{x}{\sqrt{1-x^2} \operatorname{arctanh} x} dx, \int_0^1 \frac{x^3}{\sqrt{1-x^2} \operatorname{arctanh} x} dx, \int_0^1 \frac{x^5}{\sqrt{1-x^2} \operatorname{arctanh} x} dx, \dots \right\}$$

We extend more generally to this statement : The irrationality of the numbers $\frac{\beta(2n)}{\pi^{2n}}$ would be deduced from the following conjecture:

$$\forall P \in \mathbb{Z}[x] \setminus \{0\}, \quad \int_0^1 \frac{x P(x)}{\operatorname{arctanh} x \sqrt{1-x^2}} dx \notin \pi \cdot \mathbb{Q}$$

We can find indeed for each nonzero natural integer n a polynomial Ξ_n such that holds

$$\frac{\beta(2n)}{\pi^{2n-1}} = \int_0^1 \frac{x \Xi_n(x)}{\operatorname{arctanh} x \sqrt{1-x^2}} dx$$

Examples of such polynomials are to be read from subsection §5 of chapter 5.

Since it has been proven that

$$\forall n \in \mathbb{N}^*, \quad \frac{\beta(2n)}{\pi^{2n-1}} = \sum_{p=1}^n \Psi_{p,n} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\cos((4p-2)x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx$$

, with $\Psi_{p,n} \in \mathbb{Q}$, the irrationality of the numbers $\frac{\beta(2n)}{\pi^{2n}}$ follows from this conjecture :

$$\pi \notin \text{Span}_{\mathbb{Q}} \left\{ \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\cos(2x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx, \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\cos(6x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx, \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\cos(10x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx, \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\cos(14x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx, \dots \right\}$$

We establish the following identity, which lends positive support to the validity of this conjecture. *Of course we recognize the weakness and lack of rigor of our lines of reasoning, because of the convergence and summation/integration swap.* We start from the well-known Fourier series expansion of $\ln \tan x$

$$\ln(\tan x) = -2 \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{\cos((4k+2)x)}{2k+1}, \quad 0 < x < \frac{\pi}{2}.$$

On dividing each side by $\ln \tan x$ -despite of not rigorous justification of convergence, one has

$$1 = -2 \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{\cos((4k+2)x)}{(2k+1) \ln(\tan x)}, \quad 0 < x < \frac{\pi}{2}.$$

On integrating terms by terms -despite lack of rigor, we obtain the formal identity

$$\boxed{\frac{\pi}{4} = -2 \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{2k+1} \int_0^{\pi/4} \frac{\cos((4k+2)x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx.}$$

Some computations of the first few partial sums on the right handside series tend to show that this identity may be correct. This identity does not stay in coherence with the linear dependance of the previous set stated in our last conjecture.

§3. Conjectures implying both the irrationality(respectively transcendence) of $\frac{\beta(2n)}{\pi^{2n}}$ and $\frac{\zeta(2n+1)}{\pi^{2n+1}}$

Because we sketched strong proofs that

$$\frac{\zeta(2n+1)}{\pi^{2n}} = \sum_{p=1}^n \chi_{p,n} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^{2p+1} x} dx \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{\beta(2n)}{\pi^{2n-1}} = \sum_{p=1}^n \xi_{p,n} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^{2p} x} dx$$

with $\chi_{p,n}, \xi_{p,n} \in \mathbb{Q}$, the irrationality of the numbers $\frac{\zeta(2n+1)}{\pi^{2n+1}}$ and $\frac{\beta(2n)}{\pi^{2n}}$ would be deduced **at the same time** from this **lonely** following conjecture:

$$\boxed{\pi \notin \text{Span}_{\mathbb{Q}} \left\{ \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^2 x} dx, \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^3 x} dx, \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^4 x} dx, \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{\sinh x}{x \cosh^5 x} dx, \dots \right\}}$$

Since it has been proven that $\frac{\zeta(2n+1)}{\pi^{2n}} = \sum_{p=1}^n r_{p,n} \int_0^{\pi/4} \frac{\sin(4px)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx$ and that

$$\forall n \in \mathbb{N}^*, \frac{\beta(2n)}{\pi^{2n-1}} = \sum_{p=1}^n \Psi_{p,n} \int_0^{\pi/4} \frac{\cos((4p-2)x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx$$

, with $r_{p,n}, \Psi_{p,n} \in \mathbb{Q}$, the irrationality of the numbers $\frac{\beta(2n)}{\pi^{2n}}$ and $\frac{\zeta(2n+1)}{\pi^{2n+1}}$ would be deduced from this conjecture :

$$\pi \notin \text{Span}_{\mathbb{Q}} \left\{ \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\cos(2x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx, \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin(4x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx, \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\cos(6x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx, \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin(8x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx, \dots \right\}$$

Furthermore and in the interest of the theory of Fourier series, we introduce a new vector space. The integrals $\int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin(4px)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx$ and $\int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\cos((4p-2)x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx$ evaluated in the previous sections convince us to introduce the study of the integral $\int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{f(x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx$ where f is a function of the real variable. This integral converges if and only if

$$\exists m \geq 1 : \lim_{x \rightarrow \frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{f(x)}{(x - \frac{\pi}{4})^m} \in \mathbb{R}$$

In order words, the integral $\int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{f(x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx$ converges if and only if f has a root at $x = \frac{\pi}{4}$ with multiplicity at least 1.

We consider in the same spirit this trivial theorem

$\int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{f(x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx$ is a rational (resp. algebraic) multiple of π ***if and only if*** there exists a function g so that holds :

$$f(x) = g(x) \ln(\tan x) \text{ and } \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} g(x) dx \text{ is a rational (respectively algebraic) multiple of } \pi$$

Proof :

\Rightarrow

Let $g(x) := \frac{f(x)}{\ln(\tan x)}$. It follows immediately $f(x) = g(x) \ln(\tan x)$. One has

$$\int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{f(x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx \in \mathbb{Q}\pi \Rightarrow \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} g(x) dx \in \mathbb{Q}\pi$$

\Leftarrow Is trivial

The corresponding result for algebraic multiplicity follows by essentially the same arguments.

We remind now that

$$\frac{\zeta(2n+1)}{\pi^{2n}} = \sum_{p=1}^n r_{p,n} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sin(4px)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{\beta(2n)}{\pi^{2n-1}} = \sum_{p=1}^n s_{p,n} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\cos((4p-2)x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx$$

, with $r_{p,n}, s_{p,n} \in \mathbb{Q}^*$. As proven in the previous section. Swapping the integrator and the sum yields

$$\frac{\zeta(2n+1)}{\pi^{2n}} = \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sum_{p=1}^n r_{p,n} \sin(4px)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{\beta(2n)}{\pi^{2n-1}} = \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{\sum_{p=1}^n s_{p,n} \cos((4p-2)x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx$$

Instinctively, the functions $h_n(x) := \sum_{p=1}^n r_{p,n} \sin(4px)$ and $k_n(x) := \sum_{p=1}^n s_{p,n} \cos((4p-2)x)$ cannot be written in the form $g(x) \ln(\tan x)$ with a normal common function g until

$$g(x) := \frac{\psi(x) \sum_{p=1}^n r_{p,n} \sin(4px)}{\ln(\tan x)} \quad \text{or} \quad g(x) := \frac{\psi(x) \sum_{p=1}^n s_{p,n} \cos((4p-2)x)}{\ln(\tan x)}$$

where ψ is a normal common function. The rationality of the ratios $\frac{\zeta(2n+1)}{\pi^{2n+1}}$ would be surprising. And the same line of reasoning holds for $\frac{\beta(2n)}{\pi^{2n}}$

To address the irrationality (respectively, transcendence) of the ratios $\frac{\zeta(2n+1)}{\pi^{2n+1}}$ and $\frac{\beta(2n)}{\pi^{2n}}$ in a rigorous and conclusive way, by pursuing only one idea, we propose to study the \mathbb{Q} -vector space of functions f such that

$$\int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{f(x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx \in \mathbb{Q}\pi \quad \left(\text{respectively} \quad \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{f(x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx \in \overline{\mathbb{Q}}\pi \right),$$

and to demonstrate that these functions possess at least one structural property neither shared by finite trigonometric sums of the form

$$h_n(x) := \sum_{p=1}^n a_{p,n} \sin(4px), \quad \text{with } a_{p,n} \in \mathbb{Z}.$$

nor

$$k_n(x) := \sum_{p=1}^n b_{p,n} \cos((4p-2)x), \quad \text{with } b_{p,n} \in \mathbb{Z}.$$

The last theorem ensures the existence of the functions being the solution of the equation but only their properties interest us here. For instance, they may admit an infinite Fourier expansion. We consider the form of f under two cases :

- Either f has the form $\sum_{p=1}^{\infty} [a_p \sin(4px) + b_p \cos((4p-2)x)]$ where at least one of the sets $\{a_p\}$ and $\{b_p\}$ holds infinite non zero values;
- Or f has the form $\sum_{p=1}^N [a_{p,N} \sin(4px) + b_{p,N} \cos((4p-2)x)]$ where both sets $\{a_{p,N}\}$ and $\{b_{p,N}\}$ contains at least a non zero coefficient, with N natural integer.

This reformulation of the problem is independent of any particular value of n , yet it is robust enough to imply the irrationality (respectively, transcendence) of both the ratios $\frac{\zeta(2n+1)}{\pi^{2n+1}}$ and $\frac{\beta(2n)}{\pi^{2n}}$ for all integers $n \geq 1$.

In fact, the focus of the analysis should be the integral

$$\int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \frac{f(x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx,$$

especially to exhibit when it yields a rational (respectively, algebraic) multiple of π . It is very likely that there does not exist a function $g \in L^1([0, \frac{\pi}{4}])$ such that

$$h_n(x) \quad \text{or} \quad k_n(x) = g(x) \ln(\tan x) \quad \text{and} \quad \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{4}} g(x) dx \in \mathbb{Q}\pi.$$

However, a rigorous proof of this claim remains to be established.

From the Malmsten's integrals

$$\int_0^1 \frac{\text{Im}[\text{Li}_{-2n}(ix)]}{x} \ln \ln \frac{1}{x} dx = (-1)^{n+1} \frac{2^{2n-1}(2n-1)!}{\pi^{2n-1}} \beta(2n)$$

and

$$\int_0^1 \frac{\text{Li}_{-2n-1}(-x^2) \ln \ln \frac{1}{x}}{x} dx = (-1)^n \left(1 - \frac{1}{2^{2n+1}}\right) \frac{(2n)! \zeta(2n+1)}{2 \pi^{2n}}$$

we deduce that the irrationality (respectively transcendence) of $\frac{\beta(2n)}{\pi^{2n}}$ and $\frac{\zeta(2n+1)}{\pi^{2n+1}}$ would be deduced from the following conjecture:

$$\forall P, Q \in \mathbb{Z}[x] \setminus \{0\}, \int_0^1 \frac{P(x)}{Q(x)} \ln \ln \frac{1}{x} dx \notin \pi\mathbb{Q} \quad (\text{respectively } \pi\overline{\mathbb{Q}})$$

In other words, π cannot be represented as a Malmsten's integral involving polynomials with rational (respectively algebraic) coefficients. It is not surprising at all since we could not find in Malmsten's, Adamchick's and other researchers works a Malmsten like integrals

yielding rigorously a rational multiple of π . Even the most exhaustive work of Blagouchine [1] on this class of logarithmic integrals did not explicitly give such an integral. We note in passing, that the existence of a Malmsten type integral yielding π **would follow from** the existence of Malmsten’s integrals yielding formally rational multiples of the numbers $\frac{\beta(2n+1)}{\pi^{2n}}$ ($n \in \mathbb{N}$) and $\frac{\zeta(2n)}{\pi^{2n-1}}$ ($n \geq 1$). Now, we already showed through contour integration techniques that a Malmsten’s integral leading to the class of numbers considered in this work always involves either odd zeta or even beta values. Thus, on proving rigorously the nonexistence of a Malmsten kind integral having a rational multiple of π as closed form, we prove the irrationality of the ratios $\frac{\beta(2n)}{\pi^{2n}}$ and $\frac{\zeta(2n+1)}{\pi^{2n+1}}$.

In addition, we consider the set ${}_{\beta}\Pi_{\zeta} := \left\{ \frac{\zeta(2n+1)}{\pi^{2n+1}} \mid n \in \mathbb{N}^* \right\} \cup \left\{ \frac{\beta(2n)}{\pi^{2n}} \mid n \in \mathbb{N}^* \right\}$.

When considering an arbitrary subset $\{a, b\} \subset {}_{\beta}\Pi_{\zeta}$, one might attempt to establish the irrationality of at least one of the elements a or b by invoking the assumption that distinct Malmsten-type integrals with entire coefficients cannot take equal values. However, this assumption does not hold in general.

§4. Discussion and personal perspective

The general problem addressed in this work—the arithmetic nature of the values $\zeta(2n+1)/\pi^{2n+1}$ and $\beta(2n)/\pi^{2n}$ —remains among the most tantalizing in modern number theory. Although our results do not resolve these questions, they provide structural evidence that such constants are governed by deep and coherent analytic patterns.

The integral representations derived here suggest that the logarithmic kernel $\ln(\tan x)$ and the hyperbolic families $\sinh(mx)/(x \cosh^n x)$ are not accidental artifacts, but rather part of a larger analytic framework. From a heuristic standpoint, these kernels resemble period-like objects, hinting at possible links with polylogarithms and modular forms. This perspective reinforces the idea that irrationality and transcendence in this setting may ultimately be tied to a broader theory of periods and motives.

At the same time, the work has highlighted certain obstacles: the apparent impossibility of simplifying the logarithmic kernel through elementary substitutions, the delicate convergence issues in the interchange of sums and integrals, and the difficulty of extracting effective lower bounds for the associated linear forms. These challenges underline both the richness and the resistance of the problem.

In the long term, it seems plausible that progress will come from hybrid approaches, combining analytic residue methods with arithmetic geometry, or from a deeper understanding of the algebraic structure underlying logarithmic kernels. My personal view is that the integral families presented here, despite their technical complexity, may represent a natural “bridge” between classical zeta values and the world of modular periods.

7 Conclusion

This manuscript investigates the arithmetic of the ratios $\zeta(2n+1)/\pi^{2n+1}$ and $\beta(2n)/\pi^{2n}$, whose nature (irrationality, or even transcendence) remains largely open since Euler’s works. Our approach relies on carefully designed families of logarithmic, trigonometric, and hyperbolic integrals together with a tailored residue-calculus framework. It yields explicit representations, structured identities, and numerical bounds that illuminate the architecture of these special values.

Analytically, we establish two pillars. (i) Representation formulas expressing $\zeta(2n+1)/\pi^{2n}$ (resp. $\beta(2n)/\pi^{2n-1}$) as rational combinations of integrals with the kernel $\ln(\tan x)$ over $[0, \pi/4]$, of the type

$$\int_0^{\pi/4} \frac{\sin(4px)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx,$$

$$\int_0^{\pi/4} \frac{\cos((4p-2)x)}{\ln(\tan x)} dx.$$

(ii) Parallel decompositions into hyperbolic integrals of the form

$$\int_0^\infty \frac{\sinh(mx)}{x \cosh^n x} dx.$$

Both schemes are made effective by explicit rational coefficients $(r_{p,n}, \Psi_{p,n})$ whose numerators and denominators becomes more tedious to evaluate the more the parameters of the integrals increase. They are built upon the family

$$f_{k,n}(z) = \frac{\sinh((2k+1)z)}{z \cosh^n z},$$

$$z_\ell = \frac{(2\ell+1)i\pi}{2} \quad (\ell \in \mathbb{Z}),$$

for which we carry out a detailed computation of residues at the poles, treating separately the cases of even and odd n . This analysis—based on Laurent/Taylor expansions and combinatorial identities—yields closed-form expressions and useful recurrences for the coefficients entering the hyperbolic integrals.

Arithmetically, these representations lead to linear forms (with rational coefficients) in $\{\beta(2p)/\pi^{2p-1}\}_p$ and in $\{\int_0^{\pi/4} \sin(4px)/\ln(\tan x) dx\}_p$, and they motivate minimal linear-dependence conjectures that would imply the irrationality of $\beta(2n)/\pi^{2n}$ and $\zeta(2n+1)/\pi^{2n+1}$. We further provide criteria for convergence and non-triviality of the $\ln(\tan x)$ -kernel integrals, and we highlight the impossibility of “absorbing” this kernel by a simple polynomial change of variables—an observation consistent with the general analysis of Section 6 and with the statement that π does not admit a Malmsten-type integral representation with rational/algebraic coefficients.

Concerning rigor, we separate what is proved from what is conjectured. Established: the integral identities above, the residue computations, and the rewritings into rational combinations of hyperbolic and trigonometric integrals, with control at the endpoints (notably for

$\int_0^{\pi/4} \sin(4nx)/\ln(\tan x) dx$). Conjectural: (a) linear independences (over \mathbb{Z}) among families of integrals sharing the same interval and closely related numerators or denominators; (b) the implications of these independences toward the irrationality of the normalized ζ - and β -values; (c) certain justifications of sum/integral interchanges, flagged as technical points to be secured.

Finally, several directions naturally emerge: (i) strengthening uniform estimates that authorize permutations of limit/sum/integral in contour-deformation proofs; (ii) systematizing the recurrences derived from the residues of $f_{k,n}$ to obtain effective lower bounds for linear forms; (iii) connecting the $\ln(\tan x)$ integrals to periods/modular objects and to real polylogarithms; (iv) extending the method to other L -series and to alternative logarithmic kernels of Malmsten–Blagouchine type. These avenues, intertwining complex analysis, combinatorics, and number theory, appear to offer a credible path toward broader irrationality statements.

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9 Appendix

For the computation of coefficients given in this work, we got assistance from Java SE which was very useful for fast computation. For the sake of exactitude, we used the class `BigFraction` from the library *Apache Commons Math*. The Jar file can be downloaded directly from this link <https://repo1.maven.org/maven2/org/apache/commons/commons-math3/3.6.1/commons-math3-3.6.1.jar>

```
1 package maths;
2
3 import java.math.BigInteger;
4 import java.util.HashMap;
5 import java.util.Map;
6
7 import org.apache.commons.math3.fraction.BigFraction;
8
9 public class CoefficientCalculator {
10
11     private static Map<String, BigFraction> cache0 = new HashMap<>();
12
13     private static final Map<Key, BigFraction> cache = new HashMap<>();
14
15     private record Key(int n, int j) { }
16
17     // p <= n and k < n
18     public static BigFraction computeAlpha(int p, int k, int n) {
19
20         BigFraction sign = ((p + n + k) % 2 == 0)
21             ? BigFraction.ONE
22             : BigFraction.ONE.negate();
23         BigInteger two = BigInteger.valueOf(2);
24         BigInteger pow2_2p1 = two.pow(2 * p + 1);
25         BigFraction oneMinusReciprocal = BigFraction.ONE
26             .subtract(new BigFraction(BigInteger.ONE, pow2_2p1));
27         BigInteger factorial2p = factorial(2 * p);
28
29         BigFraction prefactor = BigFraction.TWO
30             .multiply(sign)
31             .multiply(new BigFraction(pow2_2p1, BigInteger.ONE))
32             .multiply(new BigFraction(factorial2p, BigInteger.ONE))
33             .multiply(oneMinusReciprocal);
34
35
36         BigFraction sum = BigFraction.ZERO;
37         BigInteger base = BigInteger.valueOf(2L * k + 1);
38
39         for (int m = p; m <= n; m++) {
40
41             BigFraction c = computeC(2 * n - 2 * m, n);
42
43             BigInteger factorial2m = factorial(2 * m);
44             BigInteger binom = binomial(2 * m, 2 * p);
45             BigInteger pow = base.pow(2 * m - 2 * p);
46
47             BigFraction term = c
48                 .multiply(new BigFraction(binom, BigInteger.ONE))
49                 .multiply(new BigFraction(pow, BigInteger.ONE))
50                 .divide(new BigFraction(factorial2m, BigInteger.ONE));
51
52             sum = sum.add(term);
53         }
54
```

```

55     return prefactor.multiply(sum);
56 }
57
58 public static BigInteger factorial(int n) {
59     if (n < 0) throw new IllegalArgumentException("n must be >= 0");
60     BigInteger result = BigInteger.ONE;
61     for (int i = 2; i <= n; i++) {
62         result = result.multiply(BigInteger.valueOf(i));
63     }
64     return result;
65 }
66
67 public static BigInteger binomial(int n, int k) {
68     if (k < 0 || k > n) return BigInteger.ZERO;
69     BigInteger num = BigInteger.ONE;
70     BigInteger den = BigInteger.ONE;
71     for (int i = 1; i <= k; i++) {
72         num = num.multiply(BigInteger.valueOf(n - i + 1));
73         den = den.multiply(BigInteger.valueOf(i));
74     }
75     return num.divide(den);
76 }
77
78 public static BigInteger P(int m, int k, int r) {
79
80     if (r < 0 || r > m+k) return BigInteger.ZERO;
81
82     int upper1 = 2 * k + 1;
83
84     BigInteger sum = BigInteger.ZERO;
85
86     for (int q = 0; q <= upper1; q++) {
87
88         BigInteger term = binomial(upper1, q)
89             .multiply(binomial(2*m, m+k-r-q));
90         if ((q % 2) == 1) term = term.negate(); // (-1)^q
91         sum = sum.add(term);
92     }
93     return sum;
94 }
95
96 // p <= n
97
98 public static BigFraction computeQnp(int n, int p) {
99     BigFraction q = BigFraction.ZERO;
100    for (int k = 0; k < n; k++) {
101        BigFraction binom = new BigFraction(binomial(4 * n, 2 * n - 2 * k - 1));
102        for (int m = p; m <= n; m++) {
103            BigFraction c = computeC(2 * n - 2 * m, n);
104            if (2 * m < 2 * p) continue;
105
106            BigInteger sign = BigInteger.valueOf((p % 2 == 0) ? 1 : -1);
107            BigInteger pow2 = BigInteger.valueOf(2L).pow(2 * p +
108                1).subtract(BigInteger.ONE);
109            BigInteger powK = BigInteger.valueOf(2 * k + 1).pow(2 * m - 2 * p);
110
111            BigFraction term = new BigFraction(sign)
112                .multiply(c)
113                .divide(new BigFraction(factorial(2 * m)))
114                .multiply(new BigFraction(binomial(2 * m, 2 * p)))
115                .multiply(new BigFraction(pow2))
116                .multiply(new BigFraction(powK))
117                .multiply(new BigFraction(factorial(2 * p)));
118
119            q = q.add(binom.multiply(term));
120        }
121    }
122    return q.divide(new BigFraction(BigInteger.valueOf(4).pow(n)));

```

```

122     }
123
124     // j >= 0
125     public static BigFraction computeC(int j, int n) {
126         String key = j + "_" + n;
127         if (cache0.containsKey(key)) return cache0.get(key);
128         if (j == 0) return BigFraction.ONE;
129
130         BigFraction sum = BigFraction.ZERO;
131         for (int k = 1; k <= j; k++) {
132             BigFraction a = computeA(k, n);
133             BigFraction c = computeC(j - k, n);
134             sum = sum.add(a.multiply(c));
135         }
136         BigFraction result = sum.negate();
137         cache0.put(key, result);
138         return result;
139     }
140
141     // j >= n
142     public static BigFraction computeA(int j, int n) {
143
144         if (j % 2 != 0) return BigFraction.ZERO;
145
146         BigFraction sum = BigFraction.ZERO;
147
148         for (int k = 0; k <= n; k++) {
149
150             BigFraction bin = new BigFraction(binomial(2 * n + 1, k));
151
152             int base = 2 * n - 2 * k + 1;
153
154             BigInteger power = BigInteger.valueOf(base).pow(j + 2 * n + 1);
155
156             if (k % 2 != 0) power = power.negate();
157
158             sum = sum.add(bin.multiply(new BigFraction(power)));
159         }
160
161         BigInteger denom = factorial(j + 2 * n + 1).multiply(BigInteger.valueOf(4).pow(n));
162
163         return sum.divide(new BigFraction(denom));
164     }
165
166     // p <= n
167     public static BigFraction computeR(int p, int n) {
168         if (p > n || p < 1) {
169             return BigFraction.ZERO;
170         }
171         String key = p + "," + n;
172         if (cache0.containsKey(key)) {
173             return cache0.get(key);
174         }
175
176         BigFraction result;
177         BigFraction qnn = computeQnp(n, n);
178         if (p == n) {
179
180             result = BigFraction.ONE.divide(qnn);
181         } else {
182             BigFraction sum = BigFraction.ZERO;
183             for (int k = p; k <= n - 1; k++) {
184                 sum = sum.add(computeQnp(k, n).multiply(computeR(p, k)));
185             }
186             result = sum.divide(qnn).negate();
187         }
188
189         cache0.put(key, result);

```

```

190     return result;
191 }
192
193 public static BigFraction computeMalmsten(int n) {
194
195     return BigFraction.ONE_HALF
196         .pow(2*n+1)
197         .negate()
198         .add(BigInteger.ONE)
199         .multiply(BigInteger.ONE.negate().pow(n)
200             .multiply(factorial(2*n)).divide(BigInteger.TWO));
201
202 }
203
204 public static BigFraction chi(int p, int n) {
205     if (p > n || p < 1) return BigFraction.ZERO;
206
207     String key = p + "," + n;
208     if (cache0.containsKey(key)) return cache0.get(key);
209
210     BigFraction result;
211     if (p == n) {
212         result = BigFraction.ONE.divide(computeAlpha(n, 0, n));
213     } else {
214         BigFraction sum = BigFraction.ZERO;
215         for (int k = p; k <= n - 1; k++) {
216             BigFraction alpha_k0n = computeAlpha(k, 0, n);
217             BigFraction beta_pk = chi(p, k);
218             sum = sum.add(alpha_k0n.multiply(beta_pk));
219         }
220         result = sum.divide(computeAlpha(n, 0, n)).negate();
221     }
222
223     cache0.put(key, result);
224     return result;
225 }
226
227 private static BigFraction computeB(int j, int n) {
228     if (j % 2 == 1) return BigFraction.ZERO;
229     int exponent = j + 2 * n;
230     BigFraction sum = BigFraction.ZERO;
231     for (int k = 0; k < n; k++) {
232         BigInteger sign = (k % 2 == 0) ? BigInteger.ONE : BigInteger.valueOf(-1);
233         BigInteger basePow = BigInteger.valueOf(2 * n - 2 * k).pow(exponent);
234         BigFraction term = new BigFraction(binomial(2 * n, k)).multiply(new
235             BigFraction(sign.multiply(basePow)));
236         sum = sum.add(term);
237     }
238     BigInteger denom = BigInteger.valueOf(4).pow(n).multiply(factorial(exponent));
239     return new BigFraction(BigInteger.valueOf(2)).multiply(sum).divide(denom);
240 }
241
242 private static BigFraction[] computeDCoeffs(int n, int maxJ) {
243     BigFraction[] d = new BigFraction[maxJ + 1];
244     d[0] = BigFraction.ONE;
245     for (int j = 1; j <= maxJ; j++) {
246         BigFraction sum = BigFraction.ZERO;
247         for (int k = 1; k <= j; k++) {
248             BigFraction b = computeB(k, n);
249             sum = sum.add(b.multiply(d[j - k]));
250         }
251         d[j] = sum.negate();
252     }
253     return d;
254 }
255
256 public static BigFraction Gamma(int p, int n) {

```

```

257     if (n < 1 || p < 1 || p > n) {
258         throw new IllegalArgumentException("");
259     }
260
261     BigInteger fact = factorial(n - 1);
262     BigInteger pow2 = BigInteger.ONE.shiftLeft(2 * n - 2);
263     BigFraction prefactor = new BigFraction(BigInteger.ONE, fact.multiply(pow2));
264
265     BigFraction sumOverK = BigFraction.ZERO;
266     int r = n - 1;
267
268     for (int k = 0; k <= n - 1; k++) {
269         int j = 2 * k + 1 - n; // index for C_{n, 2k+1-n, n-1}
270         BigFraction C = C(n, j, r);
271         if (C.compareTo(BigFraction.ZERO) == 0) continue;
272
273         BigFraction inner = BigFraction.ZERO;
274         for (int q = 0; q <= n - 1; q++) {
275             BigFraction T = new BigFraction(P(n-k-1, k, q), BigInteger.ONE);
276             if (T.compareTo(BigFraction.ZERO) == 0) continue;
277
278             BigFraction alpha = computeAlpha(p, q, n - 1);
279             if (alpha.compareTo(BigFraction.ZERO) == 0) continue;
280
281             inner = inner.add(T.multiply(alpha));
282         }
283
284         sumOverK = sumOverK.add(C.multiply(inner));
285     }
286
287     return prefactor.multiply(sumOverK);
288 }
289
290 private static int CO(int r, int k, int n) {
291     return k > r || k < -r ? 0 : r == 0 && k == 0 ? 1 : (n+k+1)* CO(r-1,k+1,n) -
292         (n+k-1)*CO(r-1,k-1,n);
293 }
294
295 public static BigFraction C(int n, int k, int r) {
296     return fromInt(CO(r,k,n));
297 }
298
299 public static BigFraction fromInt(int s) {
300     return new BigFraction(s, 1);
301 }
302
303 public static BigFraction computeF(int p, int k, int n) {
304     int sign = ((n + k + p) % 2 == 0) ? 1 : -1;
305     BigInteger powerOfTwo = BigInteger.valueOf(2).pow(2 * p + 1);
306     BigFraction factor = new BigFraction(BigInteger.valueOf(sign).multiply(powerOfTwo),
307         BigInteger.ONE);
308
309     int maxM = n - p;
310     if (maxM < 0) return BigFraction.ZERO;
311
312     BigFraction[] dCoeffs = computeDCoeffs(n, 2 * maxM);
313
314     BigFraction sum = BigFraction.ZERO;
315     BigInteger base = BigInteger.valueOf(2 * k + 1);
316
317     for(int m = 0; m <= maxM; m++) {
318         BigFraction d = dCoeffs[2 * m];
319         int exp = 2 * n - 2 * m - 2 * p;
320         if (exp < 0) continue;
321         BigInteger power = base.pow(exp);
322         BigInteger denom = factorial(exp);
323         sum = sum.add(d.multiply(new BigFraction(power, denom)));
324     }

```

```

323
324     return factor.multiply(sum);
325 }
326
327 public static BigFraction d(int j, int n) {
328     if (j < 0 || n < 0)
329         throw new IllegalArgumentException("");
330
331     Key key = new Key(n, j);
332
333     BigFraction val = cache.get(key);
334     if (val != null)
335         return val;
336
337
338     if (j == 0) {
339         val = BigFraction.ONE;
340         cache.put(key, val);
341         return val;
342     }
343
344     BigFraction sum = BigFraction.ZERO;
345     for (int k = 1; k <= j; ++k)
346         sum = sum.add(computeB(k, n).multiply(d(j - k, n)));
347
348     val = sum.negate();
349     cache.put(key, val);
350     return val;
351 }
352
353 public static BigInteger getEulerB(int n, int k) {
354
355     if (k < 0 || k > n)
356         return BigInteger.ZERO;
357
358     else if(k == 0)
359         return BigInteger.ONE;
360
361     else
362         return BigInteger.valueOf(2*n-2*k+1).multiply(getEulerB(n-1,
363             k-1)).add(BigInteger.valueOf(2*k+1).multiply(getEulerB(n-1, k)));
364 }
365
366 public BigFraction xi(int p, int n) {
367     String key = p + "," + n;
368     if (cache0.containsKey(key)) {
369         return cache0.get(key);
370     }
371
372     BigFraction result;
373
374     if (p == n)
375         result = BigFraction.ONE.divide(computeF(n, 0, n));
376
377     else if (1 <= p && p < n) {
378
379         BigFraction sum = BigFraction.ZERO;
380         for (int k = p; k <= n - 1; k++) {
381             sum = sum.add(computeF(k, 0, n).multiply(xi(p, k)));
382         }
383         result = sum.multiply(BigFraction.ONE.divide(computeF(n, 0, n))).negate();
384     } else
385         throw new IllegalArgumentException();
386
387     cache0.put(key, result);
388
389     return result;
390 }

```

```

390
391 public static BigFraction eta(int p, int n) {
392     if (p < 1 || p > n) {
393         throw new IllegalArgumentException("p must be in {1,...,n}");
394     }
395
396     int e2 = 2 * n - 2 * p - 1;
397     BigInteger num = (p % 2 == 0) ? BigInteger.ONE : BigInteger.ONE.negate();
398     BigInteger den = BigInteger.ONE;
399
400     if (e2 >= 0)
401         den = BigInteger.ONE.shiftLeft(e2);
402
403     else
404         num = num.shiftLeft(-e2);
405
406     BigFraction prefactor = new BigFraction(num, den);
407
408     BigFraction sum = BigFraction.ZERO;
409
410     int chooseN = 4 * n - 2;
411
412     for (int m = 0; m <= n - p; m++) {
413         int e = 2 * n - 2 * m - 2 * p;
414         BigInteger factE = factorial(e);
415
416         BigInteger inner = BigInteger.ZERO;
417         for (int k = 0; k <= n - 1; k++) {
418             int chooseK = 2 * n - 2 * k - 2;
419             if (chooseK >= 0 && chooseK <= chooseN) {
420                 BigInteger bin = binomial(chooseN, chooseK);
421                 BigInteger pow = (e == 0) ? BigInteger.ONE
422                     : BigInteger.valueOf(2L * k + 1).pow(e);
423                 inner = inner.add(bin.multiply(pow));
424             }
425         }
426
427         BigFraction dTerm = d(2 * m, n);
428
429         BigFraction term = dTerm
430             .multiply(new BigFraction(inner))
431             .multiply(new BigFraction(BigInteger.ONE, factE));
432
433         sum = sum.add(term);
434     }
435
436     return prefactor.multiply(sum);
437 }
438
439 public static BigFraction Psi(int p, int n) {
440
441     if (p > n || p < 1) return BigFraction.ZERO;
442
443     String key = p + "," + n;
444
445     if (cache0.containsKey(key)) return cache0.get(key);
446
447     BigFraction result;
448
449     if (p == n)
450         result = BigFraction.ONE.divide(eta(n, n));
451
452     else {
453         BigFraction sum = BigFraction.ZERO;
454         for (int k = p; k <= n - 1; k++) {
455             BigFraction alpha_k0n = eta(k, n);
456             BigFraction beta_pk = Psi(p, k);
457             sum = sum.add(alpha_k0n.multiply(beta_pk));

```

```

458     }
459     result = sum.divide(eta(n, n)).negate();
460 }
461
462 cache0.put(key, result);
463
464 return result;
465 }
466
467 public static BigFraction Phi(int p, int n) {
468
469     if (n == p)
470         return BigFraction.ONE.divide(Gamma(n, n + 1));
471
472     BigFraction sum = BigFraction.ZERO;
473
474     for (int k = p; k <= n - 1; k++) {
475         BigFraction term = Phi(p, k).multiply(Gamma(k, n + 1));
476         sum = sum.add(term);
477     }
478     return sum.negate().divide(Gamma(n, n+1));
479 }
480
481 public static BigFraction Theta(int p, int k, int n) {
482     BigFraction sum = BigFraction.ZERO;
483
484     for (int j = 0; j <= k - 1; j++) {
485         for (int m = 0; m <= j; m++) {
486             int sign = (m % 2 == 0) ? 1 : -1;
487
488             var binom1 = binomial(2 * k, 2 * j + 1);
489             var binom2 = binomial(j, m);
490
491             BigFraction alphaVal = computeAlpha(p, 0, n - k + m);
492
493             BigFraction term = new
494                 BigFraction(sign).multiply(binom1).multiply(binom2).multiply(alphaVal);
495             sum = sum.add(term);
496         }
497     }
498     return sum;
499 }
500
501 public static BigFraction Z(int p, int k, int n) {
502
503     BigFraction sum = BigFraction.ZERO;
504
505     for (int j = 0; j <= k - 1; j++) {
506         var binom1 = binomial(2 * k, 2 * j + 1);
507         for (int m = 0; m <= j; m++) {
508             int sign = ((m & 1) == 0) ? 1 : -1;
509             var binom2 = binomial(j, m);
510             int M = n - k + m + 1;
511             BigFraction fval = computeF(p, 0, M);
512
513             BigFraction term = new BigFraction(sign)
514                 .multiply(binom1)
515                 .multiply(binom2)
516                 .multiply(fval);
517
518             sum = sum.add(term);
519         }
520     }
521
522     return sum;
523 }
524

```

```

525 public static BigFraction J(int p, int m, int n) {
526     int S = (m+n-2)/2;
527
528     BigFraction result = BigFraction.ZERO;
529
530     for (int k = 0; k <= n - 1; k++) {
531         int a = 2 * k + 1 - n;
532         int b = n - 1;
533         BigFraction Cval = C(m, a, b);
534
535         BigFraction innerSum = BigFraction.ZERO;
536         for (int r = 0; r <= S; r++) {
537             int pa = n - k - 1;
538             int pb = (m + 2 * k - n) / 2;
539             BigFraction Pval = new BigFraction(P(pa, pb, r));
540             BigFraction aval = computeAlpha(p, r, S);
541
542             innerSum = innerSum.add(Pval.multiply(aval));
543         }
544         result = result.add(Cval.multiply(innerSum));
545     }
546
547     BigFraction factor = new BigFraction(
548         BigInteger.ONE,
549         BigInteger.ONE.shiftLeft(m + n - 1)
550     );
551
552     BigInteger factorial = factorial(n - 1);
553     factor = factor.divide(new BigFraction(factorial));
554
555     return factor.multiply(result);
556 }
557
558
559 public static BigFraction u(int p, int n) {
560     if (p < 1 || p > n) throw new IllegalArgumentException("");
561
562     BigFraction sumK = BigFraction.ZERO;
563
564     for (int k = 0; k <= n - 1; k++) {
565         BigInteger binom = binomial(2 * n - 1, n - 1 - k);
566
567         BigFraction inner = BigFraction.ZERO;
568         for (int m = 0; m <= n - p; m++) {
569             int e = 2 * n - 2 * m - 2 * p;
570             BigInteger pow = BigInteger.valueOf(2L * k + 1).pow(e);
571             BigInteger fact = factorial(e);
572
573             BigFraction ratio = new BigFraction(pow, fact); // (2k+1)^e / e!
574             BigFraction d = d(2 * m, n);
575
576             inner = inner.add(d.multiply(ratio));
577         }
578
579         sumK = sumK.add(new BigFraction(binom, BigInteger.ONE).multiply(inner));
580     }
581
582     BigFraction factor = new BigFraction(4, 1).pow(p-n+1);
583     if (((p - 1) & 1) == 1) factor = factor.negate();
584
585     return factor.multiply(sumK);
586 }
587
588 public static BigFraction computeS(int p, int n) {
589     if (p > n || p < 1) {
590         return BigFraction.ZERO;
591     }
592     String key = p + "," + n;

```

```

593     if (cache0.containsKey(key)) {
594         return cache0.get(key);
595     }
596
597     BigFraction result;
598     BigFraction qnn = w(n, n);
599     if (p == n) {
600
601         result = BigFraction.ONE.divide(qnn);
602     } else {
603         BigFraction sum = BigFraction.ZERO;
604         for (int k = p; k <= n - 1; k++) {
605             sum = sum.add(w(k, n).multiply(computeS(p, k)));
606         }
607         result = sum.divide(qnn).negate();
608     }
609
610     cache0.put(key, result);
611     return result;
612 }
613
614 public static BigFraction w(int p, int n) {
615
616     BigFraction sign = ((p - 1) % 2 == 0) ? BigFraction.ONE : BigFraction.MINUS_ONE;
617
618     BigFraction denom = new BigFraction(2, 1).pow(-2*p+2*n-3);
619
620     BigFraction factor = BigFraction.ONE.subtract(
621         new BigFraction(BigInteger.ONE, BigInteger.valueOf(2).pow(2 * p + 1))
622     );
623
624     BigFraction sum_m = BigFraction.ZERO;
625
626     for (int m = p; m <= n; m++) {
627         BigFraction cm = computeC(2 * n - 2 * m, n);
628
629         BigInteger fact = factorial(2 * m - 2 * p);
630         BigFraction frac = cm.divide(new BigFraction(fact));
631
632         BigFraction sum_k = BigFraction.ZERO;
633         for (int k = 0; k <= n - 1; k++) {
634             BigInteger bin = binomial(2 * n - 1, n-1-k);
635             BigInteger pow = BigInteger.valueOf(2 * k+1).pow(2 * m - 2 * p);
636
637             sum_k = sum_k.add(new BigFraction(bin.multiply(pow)));
638         }
639
640         sum_m = sum_m.add(frac.multiply(sum_k));
641     }
642
643     return sign.multiply(factor).multiply(sum_m).divide(denom);
644 }
645
646 public static BigFraction compute_j(int p, int n) {
647     if (p > n || p < 1) {
648         return BigFraction.ZERO;
649     }
650     String key = p + "," + n;
651     if (cache0.containsKey(key)) {
652         return cache0.get(key);
653     }
654
655     BigFraction result;
656     BigFraction qnn = u(n, n);
657     if (p == n) {
658
659         result = BigFraction.ONE.divide(qnn);
660     } else {

```

```
661         BigFraction sum = BigFraction.ZERO;
662         for (int k = p; k <= n - 1; k++) {
663             sum = sum.add(u(k, n).multiply(compute_j(p, k)));
664         }
665         result = sum.divide(qnn).negate();
666     }
667
668     cache0.put(key, result);
669     return result;
670 }
671 }
```

Listing 1: Java implementation of the coefficient algorithms